
Application of the natural capital approach to the marine environment to aid decision-making

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Executive summary

The aim of this report is to improve understanding of how the natural capital approach can be applied to the marine environment and how this links to UK national policy, particularly in terms of assessing trade-offs and value for money in monitoring, protection and rebuilding of marine assets. It is important to understand better both the concept of Natural Capital (as developed for the terrestrial environment), and whether it is possible to measure and classify its components, linkages and services generated in the marine environment. This is important in order to support value for money investment and to guide both national and local decisions. The report details the outcome of a review of existing literature, data and methods, which considered different aspects of the natural capital approach as well as workshop discussions with a cross-disciplinary group of experts.

What is the natural capital approach and why is it important?

The natural capital approach is a somewhat broad term that encompasses assessment of the quantity, quality, function and value of environmental assets and the goods and services that flow from them, with the aim of ensuring the sustainable use of natural resources. Fundamentally, the approach is based on recognising the contribution of nature to human welfare, and hence improving the manner in which the natural environment is traded-off against other things that are important to society. The concept of value is central to the natural capital approach, as it seeks to better integrate environmental and economic information and thus to redress the historic trend in which natural capital and ecosystem services were undervalued and overexploited. Equally important is documenting ecological status as the characteristics of assets are usually only partially reflected in monetary values.

There is no single, universal methodology through which the natural capital approach is applied, but the core requirement is to measure the extent, status and value of natural capital assets and the services and benefits derived from them. There are a number of opportunities for implementing the natural capital approach in the context of UK policy. A particular focus of the approach has been the development of natural capital accounts, as a means of monitoring the change in natural capital over time within a framework that is comparable to economic accounts, providing a broader measure of progress. One element of the natural capital approach is to try to determine value in monetary terms, as a universal metric allows diverse services and benefits to be better compared with each other and with the wider economy. It is not always possible to monetise natural capital, and natural capital accounts using non-monetary metrics also have considerable power.

Accounts are not the only mechanism through which the natural capital approach can be applied (Figure i). It also has relevance to a number of other appraisal techniques including environmental impact assessment (for strategic environmental assessment at the programme scale and in consenting and licensing decisions for specific developments), sustainability appraisal, and regulatory impact assessment. Monetary valuation is again important for the appraisal process (as its results can be used to assess trade-offs and options through cost benefit analysis), although wider non-monetary and qualitative information are also accommodated within policy appraisal.

Figure i. Mechanisms for implementation of the natural capital approach within the UK policy framework

The natural capital approach has particular relevance to the marine environment: studies that attempt to compare the total value of global ecosystems demonstrate the high relative value of marine, coastal and transitional environments compared to their terrestrial and freshwater counterparts. Application of the approach to the marine environment presents particular challenges, but these are not insurmountable, and should not detract from the importance of continuing to seek mechanisms by which to apply the approach in practice. Specific examples of where a natural capital approach could inform management and policy decisions for the marine and coastal environment include: assessing the 'green' (managed realignment and saltmarsh creation) versus 'grey' (manmade engineering) solutions to address problems of coastal flooding and erosion; understanding and managing the trade-offs associated with different uses of the sea such as the designation of marine protected areas and the expansion of industrial sectors such as offshore wind; and taking a holistic view of fisheries management, considering the food provision and economic return of the sector in terms of the costs to other natural capital assets and ecosystem services affected by different fishing strategies.

Are existing frameworks fit for purpose?

The natural capital approach, as a broad concept, is highly relevant to inform the sustainable management of the marine environment. However, existing approaches are strongly geared to terrestrial environments and should not be adopted for the marine environment without critical evaluation. Trying to apply the existing terrestrial approach in the marine context will result in significant omissions related to critical aspects such as the three dimensional structure, the high levels of interconnectedness of processes and functions, and the fact that services users and uses are very different to the terrestrial environment.

Broadly, existing frameworks are fit for purpose in that the strong conceptual foundation provided by high level frameworks (which describe the main types of services and propose the 'cascade' from ecological components through to benefits and value) are applicable to the marine environment. Operationally, however, there are some limitations of the frameworks, particularly with regard to the category of 'intermediate' services. While the need to value only final services to avoid double counting is well recognised, developing a standardised approach to the classification and assessment of intermediate services appears unworkable as they are context specific. Also, the usefulness of intermediate services as a conceptual tool with regard to understanding underlying ecological components and their linkages through to final services and benefits is limited. The wider natural capital approach provides a framework to evaluate what are currently termed intermediate services (and wider functions and processes) as an integral (and explicit) component of ecosystem assets. Understanding of the role of ecological functions and processes in the supply of services and benefits should continue to be pursued to ensure they are adequately assessed and managed.

A standard classification system should be used in ecosystem service assessment, particularly to support applications such as accounting for which replication and comparability between assessments are essential. The Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) is recommended as the most appropriate existing framework. It clearly identifies and categorises the ecosystem endpoints (thus supporting valuation) and includes abiotic services (although it is arranged in such a way as to simplify the process of excluding abiotic services where these are not considered relevant in a particular context). CICES represents the most concerted focus of intellectual effort on ecosystem service classification (as opposed to other aspects of conceptual development or application), including consultation with and feedback from a large number of end-users. It is also popular across Europe and globally, and so has the potential to support international collaborations and comparisons, particularly across North Atlantic areas. CICES continues to evolve, and may require further testing and verification to ensure it is robust within the marine context, and to provide additional marine examples of different services to support its application. Also, although CICES has begun to dominate ecosystem service assessment, alternative classifications that consider categorization from the demand side should be explored further to determine how these could support the wider natural capital approach.

Similarly, the overarching frameworks that guide the application of specific components of the natural capital approach such as asset and risk registers and natural capital accounts appear broadly fit for purpose. However, there is a lack of specific guidance and examples for marine natural capital. Additional pilot studies are therefore required, for different goods and services, contexts and scales, to test more comprehensively the suitability of these frameworks. However, the marine and coastal habitat classifications used within natural capital frameworks in the UK policy context are not yet fit for purpose.

How can existing frameworks be improved?

It is essential that the habitats chosen as service providing 'units', and thus constituting the foundation of natural capital assessment, are selected appropriately. A consistent classification with a logical basis is required, for which the European Nature Information System (EUNIS) is recommended. For the purposes of natural capital frameworks, the broad category of 'coastal' should extend to the low water mark i.e. consistently including all supralittoral (splash zone) and littoral (intertidal) habitats. Extent and condition monitoring of coastal habitats should take account of the opportunities offered through existing terrestrial assessment programmes. The Land Cover Map and Countryside Survey both include supralittoral and littoral rock, sediment and vegetated habitats, and provide a systematic, repeated assessment at the national level that is lacking for fully submerged habitats. However, this existing monitoring would need to be modified to take account of their full intertidal extent and their function as an integral part of the marine environment.

Benthic habitat classifications should be further disaggregated to ensure vegetated habitats and biogenic reefs are adequately assessed. Classifications must also include pelagic habitats. This requires some salinity and stratification distinctions to recognise key functional aspects. Frameworks for assessment of pelagic habitats must also encompass the dynamic nature of the system, for example the spatial and temporal mobility of plankton, fish and marine mammals. Adequate classification and assessment of the pelagic system, and the interconnected nature of spatially disparate components of the wider marine environment, is a major omission in, and also a real challenge for, natural capital frameworks. Natural capital frameworks should also avoid describing the underlying assessment units as 'habitats' as this fails to recognise the breadth of ecological factors that contribute to the condition of assets and the provision of services.

Are ecological data fit for purpose? What are the key gaps in evidence?

In general, data for the UK marine environment are inconsistent, and there are significant gaps in understanding how habitats and species support the delivery of ecosystem services. Additionally, knowledge of the location and extent of habitats across most of the marine area is derived from model outputs and therefore highly uncertain. In consequence, a system of natural capital assessment based on the quality and quantity of marine benthic habitats (i.e. following terrestrial strategies such as Scotland's Natural Capital Asset Index) will be unworkable in practice at the national level. The investment that would be required to map and monitor these habitats with adequate confidence and regularity is likely to be prohibitive.

There is greater potential for the quantity and quality of marine benthic habitats to be understood and monitored at smaller spatial scales, such as for an individual protected area, where the resource requirements are less and ongoing condition assessment may be a statutory requirement. However, if such projects are not resourced on an ongoing basis, the frequency of monitoring data may be in doubt. It will be possible to learn useful lessons from the ongoing work of the Marine Pioneer, one of four projects established through the 25 Year Environment Plan, with a primary objective to explore applying a natural capital approach to decision making. Ongoing work in the North Devon and Suffolk case study sites is piloting applications including asset and risk registers and natural capital accounting.

While the lack of data from *in situ* investigation does remain a problem, there are alternatives that will allow certain data gaps to be overcome to some extent. The use of proxies based on known pressures, their impacts, and habitat sensitivity is one pragmatic approach to overcoming the lack of habitat quality information, especially in light of significant, publicly available resources on habitat sensitivity. Remote sensing also has the potential to provide cost-effective data, particularly for certain pelagic information and for mapping coastal habitats. Expert judgement is useful and necessary, but there could be benefits to standardising how it is reported (such as the method employed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) to describe confidence in the evidence and the likelihood of an outcome). Citizen science can also generate data as well as engaging the public. Better communication between those collecting and using data is essential to increase awareness of available data and to facilitate its incorporation into central databases and tools.

What are the key gaps in valuation data? Where can additional data be most usefully applied?

The most significant gaps in empirical valuation data are for regulating services including mediation of waste, toxins and nuisances; lifecycle, habitat and gene pool protection; and regulation of the chemical condition of the atmosphere and ocean. There is also a lack of values for certain cultural services, particularly marine and maritime heritage, spiritual and inspirational interactions, and health and well-being. Very few values have been derived in the context of offshore areas (and for subtidal habitats in general),

and national scale studies outside England are limited. A lack of high quality original studies further constrains the opportunities for defensible benefits transfer.

While there are significant evidence gaps across valuation data in general, these should be considered in relation to the objectives of current marine policy, particularly that within the 25 Year Environment Plan. Within that context, three priorities for new valuations are suggested: Highly Protected Marine Areas, net gain across whole systems, and the implications of plastic pollution. The 25 Year Environment Plan places net gain in the traditional context of infrastructure development, but for the marine environment this concept opens up the opportunity for a change of public mind-set to consider environmental improvements more generally.

Can the approach support assessment of value for money and trade-offs?

The individual frameworks and methods of the natural capital approach, and the way in which their outputs are used and interpreted, require further testing before it can be determined to what extent specific decision making contexts can be supported by the approach. Robust and widespread uptake of the natural capital approach will also require better understanding of the synergies and conflicts between the approach and the requirements of existing legislation. At present, the lack of robust valuation data limits the potential for assessment of the value for money associated with policy changes. Filling the gaps in empirical monetary data will be difficult to achieve rapidly and will require significant investment. Ecological information on assets should be considered alongside monetary values; the natural capital approach should be applied as a coherent whole, not through the isolated application of individual elements of it.

The natural capital approach is appropriate for the assessment of trade-offs, as it provides a structured approach to the evaluation of a wide range of benefits and the potential impacts upon them. In practice, however, greater attention needs to be paid to identifying the full suite of beneficiaries who will be affected by natural capital trade-offs. The lack of monetary values for the marine environment will limit robust cost benefit analysis, but other methods for assessing trade-offs are well established and are applicable in the natural capital context. Non-monetary information should be better used, as is already called for in existing guidance. Impacts on the quality and quantity of the asset also need to be given a similar level of attention as impacts on monetary value. Natural capital information can be incorporated into decision support tools, although more advanced tools often have significant resource requirements.

Further recommendations

Application of the natural capital approach requires a range of methods supported by different types of data and evidence, which have not been fully tested in the marine environment. Therefore, a national programme for developing methodologies for specific components of the natural capital approach (including asset registers, risk registers and accounts) should be established, bringing together policy end-users, managers, economists, ecologists, and statisticians from government (across the national and devolved administrations), statutory nature conservation bodies, NGOs and academia. This would ensure the efficient development of methods that are coherent, applicable in a range of contexts, interdisciplinary, and exemplars of best practice. The current piecemeal, sectorally 'siloed' approach is unlikely to achieve such robust outcomes.

Priorities for such a programme would be dedicated pilot studies for natural capital asset and risk registers to allow for thorough investigation of how these could be implemented in practice at different spatial and temporal scales. Experimental accounts should also be attempted for more goods and services, again at different scales. This process will identify gaps in ecological and valuation data more clearly and support the development of strategies to fill those gaps.

The Marine Pioneer programme is already working towards goals of piloting the natural capital approach and development of marine natural capital accounts. It is expected that the results of this project will supplement and support the Marine Pioneer programme and the future implementation of the wider marine objectives of the 25 Year Environment Plan.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

AIRES.....	Artificial Intelligence for Ecosystem Services
BODC.....	British Oceanographic Data Centre
CEFAS.....	Centre for Environment Fisheries and Aquaculture Science
CICES.....	Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services
DAPSI(W)R(M)...	Drivers, Activities, Pressures, State change, Impacts (Welfare), Responses (Measures)
DPSIR.....	Drivers-Pressures-State-Impact-Response
DPSWR.....	Drivers-Pressures-State-Welfare-Response
EAA.....	European Environment Agency
EEA.....	Experimental Ecosystem Accounting
EEZ.....	Exclusive Economic Zone
ESRC.....	Economic and Social Research Council
EUNIS.....	European Nature Information System
GIS.....	geographic information system
HPMA.....	Highly Protected Marine Area
InVEST.....	Integrated Valuation of Environmental Services and Tradeoffs
KIP-INCA.....	Knowledge Implementation Project on the Integrated system for Natural Capital and ecosystem services Accounting
MAES.....	Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services
MCZ.....	Marine Conservation Zone
MEA.....	Millennium Ecosystem Assessment
MENE.....	Monitor of Engagement with the Natural Environment
MMO.....	Marine Management ORganisation
MSFD.....	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NAICS.....	North American Industry Classification System
NCAC.....	Natural Capital Asset Check
NCAI.....	Natural Capital Asset Index
NEA.....	National Ecosystem Assessment
NEAFO.....	UK National Ecosystem Assessment Follow-On
NEAT.....	National Ecosystem Approach Toolkit
NESCS.....	National Ecosystem Services Classification System
NESCS-D.....	NESCS – demand side
NESCS-S.....	NESCS – supply side
ORVal.....	Outdoor Recreation Valuation (model)
QGIS.....	Quantum GIS
SDG.....	Sustainable Development Goals
SEEA.....	System of Environmental-Economic Accounting
SNA.....	System of National Accounts
SPUs.....	service providing units
S-RESS.....	Stress-Response Environmental Statistical System
TEEB.....	The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity
TIDE.....	Tidal River Development (project)
UN.....	United Nations
USEPA.....	United States Environmental Protection Agency
WAVES.....	Wealth Accounting and Valuation of Ecosystem Services

1 Aim and scope

The aim of this report is to improve understanding of how the natural capital approach can be applied to the marine environment and how this links to UK national policy, particularly in terms of assessing trade-offs and value for money in monitoring, protection and rebuilding of marine assets. The report details the outcome of a review of existing literature, data and methods, which considered different aspects of the natural capital approach in order to address the following research questions (RQs):

- RQ1:** Why is it important to consider the natural capital approach?
- RQ2:** Are existing data and frameworks fit for purpose? If not, what is required and how can this be improved?
- RQ3:** What are the key gaps in evidence to support the application of the natural capital approach in the marine environment?
- RQ4:** Where can additional primary valuation data be most usefully applied?
- RQ5:** Can an improved approach robustly aid decision makers and assess value for money associated with policy changes applied in the context of marine?
- RQ6:** Can important trade-offs be established, quantified and where possible integrated into policy decision-making tools?

The natural capital approach has largely been developed for the terrestrial environment. In evaluating fitness for purpose we consider whether these existing conceptual, assessment and appraisal frameworks and the assumptions that support them are transferable to the marine context. We consider generic issues and hence applicability across the range of policy and decision contexts.

The focus of this review is the United Kingdom, but we include international examples and case studies where these represent major initiatives in the development of natural capital approaches and tools. The literature review was supported by an international expert workshop held in June 2018, the full report from which is included in Appendix 1. The workshop provided the opportunity to discuss issues more widely with a cross-disciplinary group of experts, and so substantiate or challenge what was in the literature and highlight new sources of information. This also enabled us to test if certain perspectives and perceptions had broad support from the workshop participants and, from such consensus, to put more weight behind statements not necessarily fully supported by published literature.

Structure of the report

There are two main elements to the report. The review sections document the different frameworks, methods and data requirements for the natural capital approach, giving examples of practical application where possible. In the discussion sections, we consider the applicability, opportunities and challenges of applying these particular elements of the natural capital approach to the marine context, in order to address the specific research questions. The key conclusions and recommendations from each of these discussions are brought together, both at the end of the relevant section and to conclude the report. Where recommendations for a particular course of action (or similar directive statements) are contained within the review sections these reflect the views of the authors cited.

Table 1. The main report sections; their type (review, discussion), and the research question(s) addressed

Section	Summary	RQ
2.1	Review of the key principles of the approach	
2.2	Discussion of the broad concept of natural capital and its use in marine decision making	1
3	Review of ecosystem service frameworks and classifications	
4	Review of frameworks for other components of the approach, including: asset and risk registers, natural capital accounts and policy appraisal strategies	
5	Discussion of the applicability of the frameworks reviewed to the marine context	2
6	Discussion of improvements to habitat classifications and the need for alternative approaches	2
7	Discussion of indicators for, gaps in, and alternative strategies for collecting ecological data	2,3
8.1	Discussion of methods and methodological issues in valuing natural capital	
8.2	Review of empirical valuation data	
8.3	Discussion of the key evidence gaps that remain, and where additional primary valuation data could be most usefully applied	2–4
8.4		
9	Discussion of frameworks, data and tools in terms of assessing value for money and trade-offs	5,6
10	Summary conclusions and recommendations from the full report	1–6

2 What is the natural capital approach and why is it important?

2.1 Conceptual framework

The natural capital approach is a somewhat broad term that encompasses assessment of the quantity, quality, function and value of environmental assets and the goods and services that flow from them, with the aim of ensuring the sustainable use of natural resources. Fundamentally, the approach is based on recognising the contribution of nature to human welfare, and hence improving the manner in which the natural environment is traded-off against other things that are important to society. The concept of value is central to the natural capital approach, as it seeks to better integrate environmental and economic information and thus to redress the historic trend in which natural capital and ecosystem services were undervalued and overexploited. Equally important is documenting ecological status as the characteristics of assets are usually only partially reflected in monetary values. As the World Bank (2011) noted “*natural capital warrants special focus in the wealth management of all countries..... Losses and degradation of natural capital may lead to irreversible changes in the provision of ecosystem services and biodiversity*”.

The idea of capital (a *stock* from which *flows* of goods and services are obtained) is a core concept in economics, and has been applied for some time to the context of the natural environment (Ekins *et al.*, 2003). There is some variation in definitions used in further expanding on this concept, particularly with regard to ecosystem services. As this report centres on the UK policy context, the definitions used by the UK’s Natural Capital Committee (2017) will be adopted:

Natural capital: “*the elements of nature that directly or indirectly produce value to people, including ecosystems, species, freshwater, land, minerals, the air and oceans, as well as natural processes and functions.*”

Ecosystem services: “*functions and products from nature that can be turned into benefits with varying degrees of human input.*”

Benefits: “*changes in human welfare (or well-being) that result from the use or consumption of goods, or from the knowledge that something exists.*”

The Natural Capital Committee (2014) also sought to formalise a conceptual approach (Figure 1), which recognises that:

- There is a set of natural capital **stocks** (the assets) (e.g. clean air, soil, woodland, species).
- Each natural capital stock may provide one or more **services**; these are outputs or features of each stock (e.g. freshwater, crops, trees, wildlife).
- Services, often combined with ‘other capital inputs’, can be used to produce **goods**. Goods are what people receive and use from natural capital stocks (e.g. good health, timber, food, nature appreciation).
- ‘Goods’ are consumed / used and provide **benefits** (to people) which can be **valued** (often in monetary terms). Natural capital stocks provide many potential services with different benefits and values. These relationships may change over time and place.

Figure 1. The natural capital conceptual framework (adapted from Natural Capital Committee, 2014)

There is no single, universal methodology through which the natural capital approach is applied, but the core requirement is to measure the extent, status and value of natural capital assets and the services and benefits derived from them (Natural Capital Coalition, 2016; Natural Capital Committee, 2017). This information then provides the baseline against which the impacts of management and development options can be evaluated in the context of defined objectives for environmental exploitation, protection, maintenance and restoration. The measurement of the status of natural capital stocks (not just the marginal

valuation of current flows of services and benefits) is vital to ensure that these are maintained and can continue to provide services into the future (HM Treasury, 2018). There are a number of opportunities for implementing the natural capital approach in the context of UK policy, and these components and mechanisms (Figure 2) will be discussed in more detail in later sections of the report, in the context of the research questions posed above.

Figure 2. Mechanisms for implementation of the natural capital approach within the UK policy framework

A particular focus of the approach has been the development of natural capital accounts, as a means of monitoring the change in natural capital over time within a framework that is comparable to economic accounts, providing a broader measure of progress. One element of the natural capital approach is to try to determine value in monetary terms, as the use of a universal metric allows diverse services and benefits to be better compared with each other and with the wider economy (Natural Capital Committee, 2017). However, it is not always possible to monetise natural capital, and natural capital accounts using non-monetary metrics also have considerable power (HM Government, 2018; HM Treasury, 2018; Vardon *et al.*, 2017).

Accounts are not the only mechanism through which the natural capital approach can be applied. It also has relevance to a number of other appraisal techniques including environmental impact assessment (for strategic environmental assessment at the programme scale and in consenting and licensing decisions for specific developments), sustainability appraisal, and regulatory impact assessment. Monetary valuation is again important for the appraisal process (as its results can be used to assess trade-offs and options through cost benefit analysis), although wider non-monetary and qualitative information are also accommodated within policy appraisal. The results of assessment and appraisal can then inform the development of policies, such as for marine planning.

The natural capital approach is not without criticism; particularly that an anthropocentric philosophy is not appropriate for the management of natural resources (Goulder & Kennedy, 1997). Attempting to place a monetary value on natural resources has attracted particular, and well-documented, opposition. However, the level of acceptance of the benefits of the approach as an important tool for natural resource management is such that the Natural Environment White Paper (HM Government, 2011) entrenched the natural capital concept within UK policy, establishing the Natural Capital Committee as an advisory body to “put the value of England’s natural capital at the heart of our economic thinking” and committing to the full inclusion of natural capital in UK Environmental Accounts. The recent 25 Year Environment Plan (HM Government, 2018) reaffirmed the government’s position that the environment underpins well-being and prosperity and provides quantifiable economic benefits, and went further to express the aspiration for the UK to lead the world in the application of the natural capital approach as a tool in decision-making.

2.2 Importance of the approach in decision-making for the marine environment

The natural capital approach has particular relevance to the marine environment. Studies that attempt to compare the total value of global ecosystems demonstrate the high relative value of marine, coastal and transitional environments compared to their terrestrial and freshwater counterparts (Costanza *et al.*, 1997; de Groot *et al.*, 2012). As our knowledge of the economic value of coastal and marine systems, and their

broader contribution to well-being, remains limited at present, increasing this understanding could reveal new economic opportunities (Beaudoin & Pendleton, 2012). The UK NEA suggested that coastal margin habitats provided 3.5% of the UK's gross national income, from 0.6% of its land area (Jones *et al.*, 2011). That initiative further highlighted the changing economic trends and interactions with wider ecosystem services of capture fisheries and aquaculture, as well as the important role of the marine environment in providing waste breakdown and detoxification; climate regulation; flood, storm and coastal protection; and cultural services including recreation and heritage (Austen *et al.*, 2011).

Specific examples of where a natural capital approach could inform management and policy decisions for the marine and coastal environment include in assessing the potential for 'green' (managed realignment and saltmarsh creation) versus 'grey' (man-made engineering) solutions to address problems of coastal flooding and erosion. Options such as managed realignment and the protection of natural habitats that mitigate coastal erosion and wave overtopping already form part of the Environment Agency's strategy, but decisions around working with natural processes usually still fail to take account of non-market values (Barlow *et al.*, 2014). These decisions will become more important as the implications of climate change become more apparent.

The natural capital approach also has the potential to support understanding and managing the trade-offs associated with different, and often competing uses of the sea. The UK's Clean Growth Strategy highlights the importance of offshore wind in delivering future electricity supplies (HM Government, 2017). The natural capital approach would allow this large-scale infrastructure development to be assessed in terms of synergies and conflicts with other ecosystem services including food provision and recreation and with the wider protection of marine species and habitats, in order to determine optimal solutions. This potential for the natural capital approach applies equally to the development of other blue growth areas including aquaculture, autonomous maritime transport, and marine biotechnology. The opportunity for reforming fisheries management presented by the UK's exit from the European Union has also been identified (HM Government, 2018) and the natural capital approach would allow a holistic view of fisheries options to be taken, considering the food provision and economic return of the sector in terms of the costs to other natural capital assets and ecosystem services affected by different fishing strategies.

The UK has a network of marine protected areas (MPAs), designed to conserve important habitats and species. The natural capital approach has a central role to play documenting the extent and condition of the essential natural capital assets contained within MPAs, and the services that flow from them, and thus in informing decisions on MPA designation and management. The integration of the natural capital approach can also support movement beyond a traditional features-based approach to MPAs to more holistic assessment that considers the role of the whole site in underpinning human well-being at various scales. Adopting the natural capital approach in this MPA context could further encourage new ecosystem-based management approaches that protect and enhance 'critical natural capital assets' whilst also supporting the sustainable management of marine resources outside MPAs.

The natural capital approach can also be used to determine the cost of environmental losses, and so the level of financial compensation that could be sought, from illegal activities that damage the environment, as is being pioneered by the Environment Agency's (2018) water pollution natural capital calculator. The Marine Management Organisation (2014) already includes a public interest test within its compliance and enforcement strategy, to allow the extent of impacts on, for example, species, habitats, fish stocks, protected areas and public health to be taken account of when justifying decisions to prosecute in cases of illegal fishing, breach of licence and permit conditions and similar environmentally damaging activities. A natural capital approach akin to that taken by the Environment Agency would allow for more explicit assessment of the level of monetary compensation applicable following natural capital damage.

Application of the natural capital approach to the marine environment presents particular challenges, not least in that it suffers knowledge and governance deficits, perhaps more than any other ecosystem (Beaudoin & Pendleton, 2012). Also, coasts and seas cross borders and jurisdictions not coincident with the scale of the ecological processes, which includes interaction with terrestrial systems (Turner *et al.*, 2014), bringing challenges for management and governance. Furthermore, most effort in developing the natural capital approach has focused on terrestrial systems. The assessment framework proposed by the Natural Capital Committee, for example, has been heavily influenced by approaches to land-use management. The complexity of the marine environment (and the challenges of collecting data on it) often requires modification of methods and strategies. These challenges are not, however, insurmountable, and should not detract for the importance of continuing to seek mechanisms by which to apply the approach in practice.

3 Natural capital frameworks: ecosystem services

The concept of ecosystem services, and attempts to operationalise it, were the focus of early attention as standalone approaches, which are now being nested into a broader natural capital structure. One of the earliest frameworks to gain traction was that of the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA) (2003), which proposed four categories of ecosystem services:

- Provisioning** products obtained from ecosystems (for example, food, genetic resources and other raw materials);
- Regulating** benefits obtained from the regulation of ecosystem processes (such as climate regulation and water purification);
- Cultural** non-material benefits people obtain from ecosystems (which include recreation, education and cultural heritage);
- Supporting** those that are necessary for the production of all other ecosystem services.

While the conceptual clarity of the MEA is widely accepted, it is not considered useful for operational assessment because it fails to differentiate adequately between ecological processes, services and the benefits that arise from them, and hence the point at which value should be apportioned, creating, in particular, the risk of overestimating values due to double counting (Boyd & Banzhaf, 2007; Costanza, 2008; Fisher *et al.*, 2008; Fisher *et al.*, 2009; Ledoux & Turner, 2002; Wallace, 2007). In response, frameworks designed to facilitate economic valuation were developed; principally The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB, 2010), which incorporated the ecosystem service “cascade” concept (Figure 3). This illustrates how services form a bridge between ecological characteristics (processes, functions) and the socio-cultural context (benefits, value). TEEB dispensed with the MEA’s supporting services category in proposing a typology of 22 main service types. These were categorised within the broad MEA classes of provisioning, regulating and cultural, as well as within a new category of habitat services, which included those related to the maintenance of life cycles and genetic diversity.

Figure 3. The ecosystem services framework proposed by TEEB (2010), including the ecosystem services cascade (as adapted from Haines-Young & Potschin, 2010)

Within the wider academic literature, it was proposed that term ‘final’ services was employed to identify those which provide direct benefits and so are amenable to monetary valuation while services from which people benefit only indirectly become ‘intermediate’ services (Boyd & Banzhaf, 2007; Fisher & Turner, 2008; Fisher *et al.*, 2008). This avoids overestimation of economic values: if both the intermediate service and the final service derived from it were valued this would lead to double counting.

This approach was adopted by the UK National Ecosystem Assessment (UK NEA, 2011), which considered 16 ecosystem services (Figure 4). However, the UK NEA also maintained the MEA categorisation of provisioning, cultural, regulating and supporting services, as a means of further classifying intermediate and final services into different types. By explicitly referring to health and social values in its conceptual framework, the UK NEA approach further emphasised that economic value was only one component of the contribution the environment makes to human well-being. The UK National Ecosystem Assessment Follow-On (UK NEAFO) maintained this broad ecosystem services framework, although a marine and coastal adaptation was presented (Turner *et al.*, 2014), and is considered further in Appendix 2.

Figure 4. The National Ecosystem Assessment framework (redrawn from Mace *et al.*, 2011)

The UK NEA approached the development of an ecosystem services framework from an economic perspective, but other initiatives have focused their conceptual frameworks more from the ecological underpinnings. An EU Working Group on Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services (MAES) was established to develop a common framework and approach that could be applied consistently by all member states in meeting their obligation within the EU Biodiversity Strategy to assess the state and condition of ecosystems and their services (Maes *et al.*, 2013). The MAES framework (Figure 5) sought to build on TEEB and the UK NEA, while also integrating assessment of drivers of and responses to change, and specifically incorporating the state of the ecosystem as a key factor. In common with other frameworks, MAES also highlights the existence of multiple types of value.

Figure 5. The MAES conceptual framework (Maes *et al.*, 2013)

3.1 Standardising ecosystem service classification systems

The frameworks proposed by the MEA, TEEB and the UK NEA are primarily conceptual. They are intended to communicate ideas rather than provide a comprehensive list of all the ecosystem services that may fall within different categories and the linkages between them. Separate work has been undertaken to build on these concepts and produce standardised classifications for ecosystem services, which more closely approach the objective of an exhaustive list. The two main systems are: the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) in Europe, developed within the MAES programme, and the National Ecosystem Services Classification System (NESCS) in the United States. Neither has been developed specifically in a marine context. Although several authors have considered and refined the broad frameworks have to derive classifications and typologies for marine ecosystems, in many cases for specific UK contexts (Appendix 2). There are two main types of classifications, those for which the division between intermediate and final services is important (and so tend to follow the UK NEA), and those for which it is not a feature of the classification, which tend to follow the MEA, TEEB and CICES. This distinction primarily concerns whether the purpose of the study is ultimately to support valuation (as tends to be the case for NEA-type studies) or whether the purpose of the framework links more closely to more ecologically focussed outcomes.

Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES)

CICES (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2013; 2018) is one of the most commonly used ecosystem service classification systems globally (and particularly in Europe) and has been used by government agencies as well as academics (La Notte *et al.*, 2017). It was initiated by the European Environment Agency in 2009, with the primary objective to develop a standardised classification of ecosystem services that could be incorporated into the United Nations' System of Economic and Environmental Accounts. The most recent comprehensive revision (for CICES v5.1, released in early 2018) included a consultation and survey (to which more than 200 people contributed) as well as further reference to the wider literature (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018). The recent CICES revision also took more explicit account of its relevance for marine and coastal ecosystems, based on a review of the previous version (v4.3) and its' use in the context of developing an operational assessment framework to support EU policy needs. Further details of this process and its conclusions are not in the public domain. There is ongoing work on this topic for the European Environment Agency (Culhane *et al.*, in draft).

Due to this focus on accounting systems CICES considers only final services. CICES has a hierarchical structure, in which the highest level, "Section", maps on to the three broad ecosystem service categories from the MEA and TEEB. These are Provisioning, Cultural, and Regulation and Maintenance, with the TEEB 'habitat' category merged into the latter. Descriptions of the services become more specific with progress through the nested layers. This structure was proposed to allow flexibility for different applications,

and to take account of the challenges associated with different spatial and thematic scales. The full CICES classification has 65 defined biotic services, of which 45 have been identified as relevant to the marine environment, and a further 38 abiotic services (derived from non-living components of the environment). Examples of marine-relevant components within the CICES classification are given in Figure 6, with further details provided in Appendix 3.

Figure 6. Examples of services (with edited descriptions) showing the hierarchical structure of the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) (after Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018)

National Ecosystem Services Classification System (NESCS)

The United States Environmental Protection Agency (2015) has taken an alternative approach to the development of a comprehensive classification system for final ecosystem services, within which coastal and marine ecosystems are included. It has been designed particularly to support policy impact analyses including cost-benefit analysis of environmental regulations and accounting systems, although evidence of its application in practice is limited. While CICES took as its' foundation existing conceptual frameworks and typologies for ecosystem services, NESCS was built from the principles used in existing North American classifications and accounting systems for economic goods and services.

The NESCS structure consists of four classification groups, divided according to whether they are 'supply-side' (NESCS-S) or 'demand-side' (NESCS-D) components of ecosystem services production, and each group has within it a series of classes and sub-classes in a nested (and numerically coded) hierarchy (Figure 7). The supply side (ecological origin) categories are drawn from previous US EPA research

(Landers & Nahlik, 2013). The demand side categories link closely to established economic structures, considering the industry, household and government sectors of the economy, and use the North American Industry Classification System (NAICS) for further subdivision of the industry sector. Further examples of the structure and potential use of the NESCS system are given in Appendix 3.

Figure 7. The structure of, and examples from, the National Ecosystem Services Classification System (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2015)

4 Natural capital frameworks: assessment and appraisal

Assessment frameworks providing broad principles for how the wider natural capital approach should be implemented have also been proposed particularly, in the UK context, the Natural Capital Committee's (2017) 'How to' workbook. The Natural Capital Committee approach has strong similarities to the Natural Capital Protocol (Natural Capital Coalition, 2016), which was developed by the Natural Capital Coalition, a global collaboration of organisations and initiatives from policy, conservation bodies and non-governmental organisations, science and academia, business, civil society (currently with almost 250 members), which seeks to harmonise natural capital approaches, particularly in terms of methods and practice for individual organisations. These broad frameworks are outlined in Appendix 4. The frameworks that have been developed for specific applications of the natural capital approach (such as natural capital assets checks, accounting and appraisal), which go beyond broad, generic frameworks are described further in the remainder of this section.

4.1 Habitat classification

The foundation for current frameworks for natural capital condition assessment is definition of the underlying ecological components for which the assessment is taking place. To date, the assessment of these components follows a habitats-based approach, as developed for terrestrial systems. Therefore, the selection of an appropriate habitat classification to support natural capital assessment is fundamental.

In expanding the conceptual framework, the Natural Capital Committee (2014) proposes that the broad habitat types defined within the UK NEA (2011) are used as the basic unit for assessment as these form the basis of existing monitoring schemes, are mutually exclusive, and cover the entire country. This includes the categories of coastal margins and marine habitats (

Table 2). The potential need for disaggregation is, however, noted (Natural Capital Committee, 2014). These limitations are particularly relevant in the marine context. The absence of any categorisation of pelagic habitats is a significant failing of the UK NEA classification. An alternative typology of coastal and marine habitats has been proposed by MAES (Table 3). This links to the European Nature Information

System (EUNIS) and Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) classifications and also explicitly includes pelagic systems.

Table 2. UKNEA habitat classification for coastal margins and marine (UK NEA, 2011)

Coastal Margins	Marine
Sand dunes	Intertidal rock
Machair	Intertidal sediments
Shingle	Subtidal rock
Sea cliffs	Shallow subtidal sediment
Saltmarsh	Shelf subtidal sediment
Coastal lagoons	Deep-sea habitats

Table 3. The MAES typology of coastal and marine habitats (Erhard *et al.*, 2016)

Ecosystem type (with definition)	Representation of habitats	
	<i>Pelagic</i>	<i>Benthic</i>
<p>Marine inlets and transitional waters: ecosystems on the land-water interface under the influence of tides and with salinity higher than 0.5 ‰. They include coastal wetlands, lagoons, estuaries and other transitional waters, fjords and sea lochs as well as embayments.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low/reduced salinity water (of lagoons) - Variable salinity water (coastal wetlands, estuaries, other transitional waters) - Marine salinity water (of other inlets) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Littoral rock & biogenic reef - Littoral sediment - Shallow sublittoral rock & biogenic reef - Shallow sublittoral sediment 	
<p>Coastal: coastal, shallow, marine systems that experience significant land-based influences. These systems undergo diurnal fluctuations in temperature, salinity and turbidity, and are subject to wave disturbance. Depth is between 50 and 70 m.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coastal waters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Littoral rock & biogenic reef - Littoral sediment - Shallow sublittoral rock & biogenic reef - Shallow sublittoral sediment 	
<p>Shelf: marine systems away from coastal influence, down to the shelf break. They experience more stable temperature and salinity regimes than coastal systems, and their seabed is below wave disturbance. They are usually about 200 m deep.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shelf waters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shelf sublittoral rock & biogenic reef - Shelf sublittoral sediment 	
<p>Open Ocean: marine systems beyond the shelf break with very stable temperature and salinity regimes, in particular in the deep seabed. Depth is beyond 200 m.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oceanic waters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bathyal (upper, lower) rock & biogenic reef - Bathyal (upper, lower) sediment - Abyssal rock & biogenic reef - Abyssal sediment 	

4.2 Condition assessment

Natural capital asset register

An asset register is a key foundation of the evidence base needed to support decisions on the management of natural capital and to develop natural capital accounts. An asset register has been defined simply as “an inventory of the natural assets in an area and their condition”, for which assets could be defined according to their type, area and quality, using maps and GIS layers where possible (Natural Capital Committee, 2017). The location of an asset and how it is configured (for example the extent to which a habitat is fragmented) is also important, as this can have a significant effect on ecological functions and on benefits (Mace *et al.*, 2015; Bateman *et al.*, 2011). The Natural Capital Committee (2017) provides guidance on

(although not a formal methodology for) developing an asset register, including suggesting the types of information necessary for its completion (Table 4). The terrestrial focus is immediately apparent.

Table 4. Examples of types of information to be collected in a natural capital asset register (Natural Capital Committee, 2017)

Ecological	Socio-economic
- the boundary, extent and type of land cover	- the purpose for which the asset is being managed
- ecosystem services provided and its state as measured by quantity (extent, volume, amount), quality and location (spatial) metrics	- significant land managers in the area
- thresholds or tipping points	- major land use types
	- ownership of assets
	- assets of particular value or importance (locally/nationally)
- information on major dependencies (e.g. on other natural assets or activities outside the area)	

Natural Capital Asset Check

The UK National Ecosystem Assessment Follow On (UK NEAFO) proposed a more detailed framework for a Natural Capital Asset Check (NCAC) (Dickie *et al.*, 2014a). This has five key steps in which the current and future performance of natural capital assets are assessed in terms of their ability to support human well-being (Figure 8, with further details in Appendix 5). The authors argue that broad definitions of natural capital as encompassing the entire natural environment are not helpful in practice, and so propose that asset checks should focus on specific ‘productive combinations’, for which it is known when, how and where human welfare is supported. Also central to the NCAC are the concepts of:

- i) *integrity*: the extent and condition of the natural capital asset;
- ii) *performance*: its ability to support human welfare;
- iii) *red flags*: alerts to the proximity of thresholds and the consequences of crossing them;) and
- iv) *sustainability*: the continuation of performance into the future.

The NCAC also acknowledges that uncertainty is inevitable, and suggests this is described qualitatively using the scale proposed in the National Ecosystem Assessment:

- i) *well established*: high agreement based on significant evidence;
- ii) *established but incomplete evidence*: high agreement based on limited evidence;
- iii) *competing explanations*: low agreement, albeit with significant evidence;
- iv) *speculative*: low agreement based on limited evidence.

Figure 8. The conceptual framework for the UK National Ecosystem Assessment Natural Capital Asset Check (Dickie *et al.*, 2014a)

The UK NEAFO included pilots of the NCAC in marine and coastal systems for (i) carbon sequestration and storage in seagrass beds; (ii) saltmarsh as a nursery ground for commercial fisheries; and (iii) the Tees Estuary. These produced heavily narrative outputs, with qualitative summaries, but demonstrated that the process was feasible particularly where the natural capital asset in question was clearly defined and,

ideally, within a tightly defined geographic boundary for which there was good data availability. This is rarely the case in wider marine ecosystems.

Scotland's Natural Capital Asset Index

Other initiatives for assessing the condition of natural capital have proposed and applied methods that are more quantified and systematic. The Scottish Government first published its Natural Capital Asset Index (NCAI) in 2011, in what was reportedly the first example of a detailed attempt to measure annual changes in natural capital at the national level (Albon *et al.*, 2014). "Increase natural capital" (as measured by the NCAI) is now one of 55 National Indicators which document progress towards achieving the Scottish Government's ambition and priority outcomes (Scottish Government, 2018). The NCAI (which is reported as a single figure) uses habitats as service providing units (SPUs) and considers their area, their potential to deliver ecosystem services and the relative importance of these services in order to model their contribution to human well-being, which is monitored annually relative to 2000 (Figure 9) (Scottish Natural Heritage, 2018a, 2018b).

Figure 9. The model for Scotland's Natural Capital Asset Index (Scottish Natural Heritage, 2018a)

The potential for each habitat to deliver each service is determined using a published matrix (Burkhard *et al.*, 2014), and recorded on a ratio scale from 0 to 5 (Scottish Natural Heritage, 2018a). The ecosystem services are then weighted (by expert judgement) according to their relative importance, firstly across the three broad CICES sections (regulating, provisioning and maintenance, cultural) and then for each group or class within that section. In addition to the habitat area and its broad potential to deliver ecosystem services, changes in habitat quality (defined as its actual ability to deliver ecosystem services now and into the future) are also monitored, using a series of indicators. These indicators are weighted according to six criteria: the type of indicator, date first available, frequency of updates, spatial coverage, correlation (e.g. of an impact indicator with habitat state) and annual fluctuations (e.g. due to weather) (Scottish Natural Heritage, 2018a). Finally, the NCAI highlights where there are evidence gaps, in terms of the available data on each indicator for each habitat/ecosystem service combination.

Marine habitats do not form part of the NCAI, due to a lack of information equivalent to that available for terrestrial habitats. The NCAI does cover coastal habitats above the spring high tide limit which are normally only affected by spray or splash (coastal dunes and sandy shores (incorporating machair); coastal shingle; and rock cliffs, ledges and shores). A scoping study on the feasibility of a marine NCAI for Scotland was published in February 2019 (Tillin *et al.*, 2019).

Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystem Services (MAES)

The EU MAES initiative has developed a framework (Erhard *et al.*, 2016), which illustrates how data and maps on habitat, condition, ecosystem services and the drivers and pressures by which they are affected can be brought together in the mapping and assessment of ecosystem condition (Figure 10). The framework also highlights where key data gaps are expected. MAES also provides definitions related to these concepts, where "ecosystem condition refers to the physical, chemical and biological condition or quality of an ecosystem at a particular point in time", and "pressure refers to a human induced process that alters the condition of ecosystems" (Maes *et al.*, 2018).

Within the MAES initiative, a series of pilots at the EU level, including one for marine ecosystems, was undertaken to test their analytical framework, develop indicators (for pressures and for ecosystem condition) and ensure consistency. The work integrated key indicators used for existing policy purposes such as the Habitats, Birds, Water Framework and Marine Strategy Framework Directives, and sought to provide examples of how policy questions could be addressed using the approach (Erhard *et al.*, 2016; Maes *et al.*, 2018). Further discussion of indicators for marine natural capital can be found in Section 7.1.

Figure 10. The MAES framework for ecosystem condition assessment and mapping (from Erhard *et al.*, 2016)

Risk register

The Natural Capital Committee (2013) proposes that the assets at greatest risk from unsustainable use and poor management should be identified in order to prioritise natural capital investment decisions, and a regularly updated risk register that systematically documents the threats to assets and benefits is proposed as an important tool for this process. A risk register should document the likelihood of changes in the delivery of benefits and the scale of impact of such changes (Natural Capital Committee, 2017). A methodology for developing a risk register, and a preliminary high level assessment at the national scale, was developed by Mace *et al.* (2015) as part of the Natural Capital Committee's work.

In the risk register proposed by (Mace *et al.*, 2015), there are three main characteristics that determine the elements of natural capital that should be included, namely: they (i) are changing or likely to change at measurable rates over policy-relevant timescales (decades); (ii) have some actual or potential relevance to human welfare, now or in the future; and (iii) are plausibly subject to management by people in some way to restore or recover, or to restrict use to non-significant rates of loss, or for use by future generations. There are also three principal steps in compiling the risk register: (1) define natural asset classes; (2) determine asset-benefit relationships; and (3) establish targets and acceptability limits.

Mace *et al.* (2015) further describe the relationship between the status of each asset and the benefits it provides as being comprised of three dimensions: the quantity, quality and spatial configuration (defined as the location and/or spatial patterning and fragmentation of the asset) as these are all significant in determining the degree to which deterioration in the condition of the asset will affect benefit delivery. The form of the relationship between assets and benefits, the rate and predictability of decline in asset status, and the proximity to ecological thresholds is critical to compiling the risk register.

Developing a risk register requires the specification of limits beyond which change is unacceptable. Mace *et al.* (2015) assume that targets and acceptability levels reflect the requirements of society and are likely to relate to policy targets and related status indicators such as those for bathing water quality and the condition assessments for protected habitats. It is assumed that a precautionary margin would be included in such targets. Finally, Mace *et al.* (2015) propose that the risk register should include a measure of uncertainty: robustness of evidence and agreement between assessors, which can be presented as the intensity of the shading in the risk output matrix.

Mace *et al.* (2015) defined their natural asset classes by following the UK NEA broad habitat types, which include two marine categories: coastal margins (coastal dunes and sandy shore, saltmarsh, estuaries and

lagoons) and marine (intertidal rock, intertidal sediment, subtidal rock, shallow subtidal sediment, deep sea bed, and pelagic water column). Further details of the asset-benefit relationships assumed for these habitats are provided in Appendix 6. Limited data was used in the risk assessment and the judgement of where the boundaries lie between risk categories seems somewhat subjective.

As yet, the development of risk registers for natural capital does not appear to be common practice, although one further example was identified. In their risk register for the Anglian Water Combined Services Area, Lovett *et al.* (2018) replicated the approach taken by Mace *et al.* (2015), but added a further dimension in using GIS to map the pressures on natural capital in the area, which were identified using a modified Drivers-Pressures-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR) framework, and highlighted in the results matrix where positive impacts occur. A discussion on DPSIR and other causal frameworks in the natural capital context is provided in Appendix 7.

The possibility for extending the risk register concept (which includes only assets and benefits) to incorporate a threat assessment for ecosystem services is also being explored. Maron *et al.* (2017) have proposed a framework that considers the risk that ecosystem services will fail to meet the demand by society, using threat categories based on the IUCN Red List system (Table 5). As yet, however, this is an initial conceptual exploration and has not been tested in practice.

Table 5. A proposed Threat Categorisation Framework for ecosystem services (Maron *et al.*, 2017)

Category	Definition	Threshold
Functionally extinct	Service no longer supplied in the region and is practically unrecoverable	Lost
Dormant	Service no longer supplied in the region but is potentially recoverable	
Critically endangered	Current levels of demand exceed supply and the ratio of supply to demand declining or expected to decline	Undersupplied
Endangered	Current levels of demand exceed supply; ratio of supply to demand is stable but supply is declining	
Stable but undersupplied	Current levels of demand exceed supply; neither supply nor ratio of supply to demand declining	
Vulnerable	Ratio of supply to demand is declining or expected to decline such that supply is likely to be insufficient to meet demand within a set time horizon	At risk
Least concern	Supply currently meets or exceeds demand, and does not meet the criteria for Vulnerable	Secure
Data deficient	Inadequate information is available about either or both of supply and demand to assess the level of threat	n/a

4.3 Natural capital accounting

Overarching framework

The accounting element of the natural capital approach has been the focus of significant effort in response to national and international policy drivers. Natural capital accounting has been defined as “a tool to measure the changes in the stock and condition of natural capital at a variety of scales and to integrate the value of ecosystem services into accounting and reporting systems” (European Commission & European Environment Agency, 2016). Broadly, the accounting framework includes assessment of both stocks and flows, in monetary and non-monetary terms (Figure 11). The non-monetary accounts consider the extent and quality of stocks, and quantities (rather than values) of ecosystem services and thus overlap with concepts of a natural capital asset register and condition assessment, with the distinction that the expectation with accounts is that these parameters would be quantified and recorded at regular intervals (usually annually). For a coherent natural capital approach the same fundamental principles should be applied to asset registers and accounts (Dickie *et al.*, 2014a).

Non-monetary accounts

Monetary accounts

Figure 11. The main components of natural capital accounts (ONS & Defra, 2017)

System of Environmental-Economic Accounting (SEEA)

The United Nations has led efforts to meet commitments for integrated environmental and economic accounts contained within Agenda 21 of the Conference on Environment and Development held in Rio in 1992. This has been through the System of Environmental-Economic Accounting (SEEA), intended as an international standard to support the consistent presentation of accounting information and so facilitate comparison between countries (United Nations, 1993; United Nations *et al.*, 2014b). It is important nationally that a consistent and standardised approach to environmental accounting is adopted, again to enable comparisons (for example between years) but also to avoid double counting within national accounts. The SEEA comprises a Central Framework, which links closely to the international System of National Accounts (SNA) (European Commission *et al.*, 2008), and provides for environmental assets to be incorporated in terms of individual resources (e.g. timber and water) in both monetary and physical terms. An early case study involved developing the approach for fisheries (United Nations & Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2004), in an attempt to address the limitation within the SNA that fish stocks were recorded only in terms of income and did not record stock depletion (and hence potential over-exploitation).

The SEEA is evolving through the complementary Experimental Ecosystem Accounting (EEA) (United Nations *et al.*, 2014a), which has not yet developed to an international standard, but is proposed as a framework to be tested and developed as countries attempt to implement national systems (and is currently (2018) under revision). The EEA adopts the same principles as the SEEA central framework but broadens the perspective to consider ecosystem services and the relationship between stocks and flows. Assessment of stocks is spatial and based on land cover types. The EEA uses the Food and Agriculture Organisation Land Cover Classification System (FAO, 2009) within which there is the single category of coastal water bodies. Flows are considered in terms of provisioning, regulating and cultural ecosystem services (flows between the environment and people), but also the intra- and inter-ecosystem flows (between different ecosystem assets, i.e. supporting services). The benefits derived from these flows are categorised according to whether they are part of the economic activity documented within the SNA, or outside this (and generally not traded on markets). Initially, the EEA proposed CICES as the classification system for ecosystem services, but this is currently under review, with ongoing discussions to develop a classification purely for natural capital accounting purposes (SEEA, 2018).

Wealth Accounting and Valuation of Ecosystem Services (WAVES)

The World Bank-led Wealth Accounting and Valuation of Ecosystem Services (WAVES) (Vardon *et al.*, 2017) is a global partnership that aims to mainstream natural resources into development planning and national accounts. However, it contrasts with the SEEA in seeking a shift in emphasis from ‘supply side’ generation of accounts (technical focus) to ‘demand side’ support for decision makers in improving natural capital policy (decision-centred focus) (Table 6). Thus, WAVES highlights the different policy dimensions and tools, institutional contexts, the role of power structures, and the need for institutional reform in order to address complex problems and to progress from themed accounts for certain types of key natural resources to reaching full natural capital accounts.

Table 6. The shift in emphasis in the implementation of natural capital accounting proposed by the Wealth Accounting and Valuation of Ecosystem Services (WAVES) initiative (Vardon *et al.*, 2017)

From ...	To...
Technical focus – get natural capital accounts (NCA) methods and data right	Decision focus – get natural capital policy right
Supply side – NCA production is separate from policy production; NCA struggles to get policy uptake	Demand side – policy players engage with NCA players, and thus shape NCA purpose/focus
Government focus on policy – as a government domain, that is, “what government wants”	Stakeholder view of policy – what business, civil society, and government want, and how they agree
Focus on formal policy decision – NCA trying to change one policy decision or plan	Enable policy discourse by many – NCA helping debate and review as well as making decisions

Data provision – NCA producers putting out raw data and hoping they will be used	Information demand – “policy entrepreneurship”, or getting policy relevant information to many users
NCA is a “magic bullet” – promoted on its own	NCA works with complementary tools
Experimental – one-off approaches	Mandated – comprehensive and routine NCA system

The WAVES report suggests that natural capital accounts have a role throughout the policy cycle (of problem identification, response, implementation, monitoring and review), but stresses that full natural capital accounts are not necessary for successful analysis of policy measures. WAVES proposes ten principles for natural capital accounting (Table 7), and provides examples of global experience in natural capital accounting. These show how it has been used for policy monitoring and review; long-term national development and green growth plans; to analyse specific policy issues around water, forestry, mining, energy and the costs of El Niño; and to address trade-offs and competition between sectors. Accounts for marine and coastal resources are notably lacking from the examples provided in WAVES reporting, which gives only brief reference to those for fisheries and aquaculture in Guatemala (Castaneda *et al.*, 2017) and pilots and scoping studies in the UK and Sweden (Barter, 2017; Steinbach, 2017), although the expectation for these to be included in the future was noted, at least for Costa Rica (Gutiérrez-Espeleta, 2017).

Table 7. The WAVES ten principles of natural capital accounting (Vardon *et al.*, 2017)

<p>Comprehensive:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Inclusive</i> – Acknowledging the diverse stakeholders concerned with decisions affecting natural capital, responding to their information demands, respecting different notions of value, and using appropriate means of engagement 2. <i>Collaborative</i> – Linking the producers of NCA, the users of NCA for policy analysis and the policy makers using the NCA results, and building their mutual understanding, trust, and ability to work together 3. <i>Holistic</i> – Adopting a comprehensive, multi/interdisciplinary approach to the economic and environmental dimensions of natural capital and to their complex links with policy and practice
<p>Purposeful:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. <i>Decision-centred</i> – Providing relevant and timely information for indicator development and policy analysis to improve and implement decisions with implications for natural capital 5. <i>Demand-led</i> – Providing information actually demanded or needed by decision makers at specific levels
<p>Trustworthy:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. <i>Transparent and open</i> – Enabling and encouraging public access and use of NCA, with clear communication of the results and their interpretation including limitations of the data sources, methods, and/or coverage 7. <i>Credible</i> – Compiling, assessing, and streamlining data from all available sources, and deploying objective and consistent science and methodologies
<p>Mainstreamed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. <i>Enduring</i> – With adequate, predictable resourcing over time; continuous application and availability; and building increasingly rich time series of data 9. <i>Continuously improving</i> – Learning focused, networked across practitioners and users, testing new approaches, and evolving systems to better manage uncertainty, embrace innovation, and take advantage of emerging opportunities 10. <i>Embedded</i> – NCA production and use becoming part of the machinery of government and business, building capacity, improving institutional integration for sustainable development, and incorporating NCA use in procedures and decision-support mechanisms

Knowledge Implementation Project on the Integrated system for Natural Capital and ecosystem services Accounting (KIP-INCA)

At the EU level, the Knowledge Implementation Project on the Integrated system for Natural Capital and ecosystem services Accounting (KIP-INCA) is an ongoing programme that seeks to produce physical and monetary accounts for the EU, and has close links to the MAES initiative and CICES (European Commission & European Environment Agency, 2016). Some key aspirations for the EU accounts are given in Table 8.

Reference to marine issues is more prominent in KIP-INCA than the SEEA or WAVES. A workshop held as part of this project (Anon, 2016) noted that, while specific guidance under the SEEA EEA on developing accounts for marine ecosystems was lacking, the generic guidance was applicable with some adjustment. The analytic challenge of accounting for species that move on a daily or seasonable basis was highlighted in particular. The workshop also concluded that existing data and knowledge were sufficient to begin pilot accounts around particular case studies in the short-term. The role for remote sensing and modelling in condition assessment for some ecosystem components and the potential for use of MSFD descriptors for good environmental status, where these are underpinned by quantified indicators, was also identified (European Commission & European Environment Agency, 2016). Further details of marine scoping and pilot studies are provided below.

Table 8. Aspiration for aspects of the EU natural capital accounts to be developed within KIP-INCA (European Commission & European Environment Agency, 2016)

<p>Physical accounts should ideally be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Representative of key ecosystem functions / MAES ecosystem types; • Targeted on functional ecological units (river basins, mountain areas etc.); • Aligned with key EU policy targets (as spelled out in the 7th EAP and the EU Biodiversity Strategy to 2020); • Possible to update on a yearly/regular basis; • Transparent and easily communicable.
<p>Parameters for condition monitoring should ideally:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Match critical pressures on, and fundamental changes in, ecosystem condition; • Be applicable and comparable across all MAES ecosystem types, as far as is feasible; • Include ecosystem-specific condition parameters where appropriate or necessary; • Be of a manageable number per ecosystem type (e.g. in the range of 3–5) to avoid complicating the construction and calculation of the overall account too much; • Be underpinned by data sets that allow a reliable quantitative analysis of trends at suitable spatial and temporal scale.
<p>The basket of ecosystem service to be tracked within accounts should ideally represent:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All or most of the 12 main MAES ecosystem types; • All main divisions of CICES (the ‘Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services’); • Key ecosystem functions / types of ecosystem (capital) stock and flows; • Ecosystem services with a high communication or social value; • Consideration of multiple ecosystem services simultaneously.
<p>The selected ecosystem services should allow the following questions to be answered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the biological resource base for fundamental economic sectors / our survival sustainable (e.g. track outputs from agriculture, forestry, fisheries, drinking water etc.)? • What is the impact of key environmental policy areas on ecosystem service flows (e.g. water policy, climate policy, biodiversity policy, the MSFD/fisheries policy etc.)? • What are key trade-offs between different ecosystem service types (e.g. provisioning – cultural, provisioning – regulating etc.)?

UK national accounts

The SEEA has been an important source of technical guidance for the development of UK natural capital accounts (ONS & Defra, 2017), which have in turn informed EU and global initiatives such as WAVES and KIP-INCA. At the national level in the UK, the Office for National Statistics (ONS) has published the concepts and methodology behind its approach to natural capital accounting, which contains 45 explicit principles (ONS & Defra, 2017). These include the need for consistency between national and spatially disaggregated accounts; transparency in confidence estimates, gaps and other uncertainties; and the aspiration for annual accounts of flows, while asset accounts can be updated less frequently, depending on the likelihood of change. The principles also call for condition accounts to consider volume estimates, biodiversity indicators, soil indicators, ecological condition, spatial configuration, access and management practices. Disservices or negative externalities arising from ecosystem functioning are excluded from

accounts. The principles stress that the aim is to expand the boundaries of national accounts to include a greater range of services and assets rather than to capture the total value for the natural environment. The dependence of monetary accounts on physical accounting, and hence the need to develop both in parallel is also emphasised.

The ONS recently published experimental ecosystem service accounts for the period 1997 to 2015 (ONS, 2018), which comprise accounts for provisioning services (energy, minerals, timber, agricultural production, caught fish, water), regulating services (carbon sequestration, air filtration in the context of pollution removed by vegetation) and cultural services (the environment as a setting for outdoor recreation). This includes marine examples through wild caught fish (aquaculture is excluded as being a produced rather than natural asset) and recreation, for which data is derived from The Monitor of Engagement with the Natural Environment (MENE) survey and includes coasts and beaches.

A study was also undertaken to explore one element of national level accounting, that of ecosystem accounts for protected areas, which was prepared for DEFRA and the Scottish Government (White *et al.*, 2015a,b). Marine habitats were excluded but the accounts did include limited coastal margin habitats (supralittoral (splash zone) rock and sediment, and saltmarsh). Monetary values were reported for assets and services related to livestock (resource rent), air quality (avoided cost), climate regulation (abatement cost) and recreation (willingness to pay). This work also showed that coastal margins had the highest monetary value per unit area (almost three times that of the next most highly valued habitat type) compared with the other land types considered.

Corporate natural capital accounting

In addition to national-level accounts, the Natural Capital Committee (2013) also advocates corporate natural capital accounting to support understanding amongst businesses, land owners and land managers of the risks to their supply chains and future growth opportunities from the deterioration of natural capital. This has similarities with the Natural Capital Protocol (Natural Capital Coalition, 2016), The ONS notes that there should be consistency between national accounts and those prepared at smaller spatial scales (ONS & Defra, 2017). Guidance for accounting at the corporate level has been developed, but this is a primarily descriptive framework because “*a prescriptive approach is not desirable given the potential diversity of organisations and natural capital assets and their uses, to which the framework could be applied*” (eftec *et al.*, 2015). The key reporting statements of corporate natural capital accounts are a balance sheet to report the value of assets and the costs associated with maintaining them, and a statement of change in the assets over the accounting period. These are supported, as is the case for national accounts, with a natural capital asset register, and physical and monetary flow accounts as well as a maintenance cost schedule.

Pilot corporate natural capital accounts were produced during the development of the guidance for four business and land owners. These were largely terrestrial, but included one example focussed on a utility company and its maintenance of four designated bathing waters (eftec *et al.*, 2015). Other examples of corporate natural capital accounts are emerging, with varying degrees of detail, including for forestry (Forest Enterprise England, 2017) and green spaces managed by local authorities (eftec & Jon Sheaff and Associates, 2017; Vivid Economics, 2017). Nature reserves and protected areas have also been a focus of pilot corporate natural capital accounts. The account compiled for the RSPB (2017) includes extent and population trend data for marine and coastal habitats and species, but not explicit monetary values for marine elements of the overall assets and liabilities.

4.4 Marine natural capital accounts

The initial roadmap for the development of the UK's natural capital accounts (ONS, 2012) highlighted the difficulties in producing accounts for marine and coastal environments, including conceptual challenges and the lack of systematic data. While it was considered feasible to construct a marine account focussing on fish stocks early in the process, the development of accounts for coastal habitats was scheduled for later implementation. Scoping and pilot studies specifically for marine natural capital accounting have been undertaken, which mostly consider the issues in producing such accounts rather than providing robust account records.

Work commissioned by DEFRA (eftec, 2015) and by the ONS (2016) scoped, respectively, issues in the development of marine and coastal margin accounts for the UK. Both proposed combined accounts that integrate at least some coastal areas within the sphere of ‘marine’ accounts, although there were differences in defining which coastal areas should be included. eftec (2015) placed the landward boundary at the mean high water mark, while ONS (2016) took a more ecologically-based approach and included the six coastal margin habitats listed in the UKNEA (Jones *et al.*, 2011). The geographic extent of the

marine area was defined by eftec (2015) as the limit of the UK's marine waters. This provides an appropriate boundary from the perspective of property rights and governance jurisdiction, although the authors note that this does not coincide with the ecosystem boundary. The ecosystem is more appropriately described by the large marine ecosystem areas of the Celtic and North Seas.

In providing some initial exploratory monetary accounts, these scoping studies considered only a limited set of ecosystem services. Both featured carbon sequestration and recreation, while the marine study (eftec, 2015) also considered fish, and the coastal margin study (ONS, 2016) added sea defence and air quality regulation. The set of specified habitats was also limited. The coastal habitats were sand dunes, machair, saltmarsh, shingle, sea cliffs and coastal lagoons. Saltmarsh also featured in the marine scoping study, together with offshore sediments in two depth ranges and maerl beds as well as general marine. The marine accounts (eftec, 2015) stressed that the terrestrial approach based on spatial accounting units may not be entirely appropriate in the marine environment, as it is more fully three dimensional, data-poor, more dynamic and the variables in production functions vary over time and space. In exploring a more water column based accounting unit, the value of the North Sea carbon pump (an interaction between the North Sea and deeper North Atlantic waters) to carbon sequestration was calculated.

The marine scoping exercise (eftec, 2015) further considers how to take account of the spatial disparity between essential supporting factors (such as nursery habitats) and the delivery of final services, and also the role of use and management practices in affecting the condition and availability of the stock. A logic chain approach was therefore proposed, to define all the relevant factors and their role in the delivery of services and benefits (Figure 12). The inclusion of an adapted SEEA table within the accounts to summarise who generates and uses ecosystem services, was also proposed. This included categories of enterprises, households, Government, and also added Rest of the World, to bring in some acknowledgement the beneficiaries may be located beyond national boundaries.

Figure 12. An example of the logic chain concept for capturing the full range of factors affecting the delivery of benefits (eftec, 2015)

At the European level, a horizon scanning exercise has been carried out to establish priorities for marine natural capital accounts (Weatherdon, 2018). This was undertaken primarily from the perspective of integrating ecological information collected as part of EU policy obligations into extent and condition accounts rather than from the perspective of reporting economic values. This proposed a three-tiered approach:

- In the short-term: initial “headlines” that identify the current state of knowledge related to the account of interest;
- In the medium term: ‘technical’ marine accounts that use global and/or European datasets or indicators on critical aspects of the feature’s condition (and/or pressures and impacts);
- In the long-term: ‘proper’ marine accounts derived from national datasets and/or targeted monitoring programmes, with full stock and service accounts that draw from a portfolio of sources of spatial and contextual information.

Using ‘Good Environmental Status’ indicators from the MSFD is identified as a “quick win” and seagrasses and deep-sea corals were also mentioned as “keystone habitats” for further investigation. The report also highlighted the need for priority actions to develop methodological approaches for ecosystem extent and

condition and also to determine condition thresholds necessary for the delivery of services. It was further suggested that management measures (such as inclusion within protected areas) and vulnerability (e.g. European Red List designation) could be used in early accounts as proxies for extent and condition in data-poor areas, although quantifiable, spatially explicit measurements would ultimately be needed, in order to develop full stock and service accounts.

Related work within the KIP-INCA project has developed experimental seagrass account which aligns with existing habitat classification systems as well as the CICES classification for ecosystem services (Weatherdon *et al.*, 2017). This focused on the extent and condition components, while also noting the contribution of seagrass to certain ecosystem services, namely carbon sequestration, food provisioning, water flow stabilisation, nurseries for commercial fish, and mass stabilisation and erosion control. A key conclusion of the study was that there is strong potential for seagrass accounts. The possibilities of using proxies for ecosystem condition such as levels of protection were discussed, and it was noted that this does not necessarily provide an adequate condition assessment as the habitat within a protected area may be degraded, recovering or healthy. Assessment of the types and levels of pressure on the habitat was also suggested as a proxy for condition.

Marine natural capital accounts for the Dutch North Sea area have also been scoped but not trialled (Graveland *et al.*, 2017). As with the UK scoping studies, a boundary at the extent of Dutch national economic territory is proposed and the issue of whether to include coastal habitats considered. The authors further propose a hierarchy that differentiates distinct habitat types within broad habitat classes, noting the need for aggregation at the national level, the potential lack of information across all asset subclasses, and the requirement for the specific ecosystem types to be included in accounts to be determined in consultation with stakeholders that will use the accounts. The MAES marine ecosystem typology (with its broad categories of inlets/transitional, coastal, shelf, and open ocean) and CICES are endorsed as classification frameworks, with the MSFD monitoring requirements suggested as a starting point for the development of extent and condition indicators. In a departure from the SEEA guidance (see above), the inclusion of disservices, in terms of how they reduce the condition of other assets and services, is advocated. Pro-forma example accounts tables are provided, although as there is no attempt to populate these the suggestions are rather generic, the challenges of attempting to complete them are not addressed, and concrete recommendations are few.

Beyond Europe, the Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS, 2017) has produced experimental accounts for the Great Barrier Reef area, again based on SEEA-EEA, and which include extent, condition and monetary information. The marine condition component focuses on water quality, coral, seagrass and fish abundance, and the ecosystem services considered are fishing and aquaculture, and tourism. The ABS will be engaging in a consultation process with key stakeholders as the accounts evolve further.

4.5 Policy appraisal

Policy appraisal is not a framework specific to natural capital, but it does provide a key mechanism through which natural capital information can be incorporated into the wider decision-making process. In the context of UK national policy, the Green Book (HM Treasury, 2018) defines appraisal as “*the process of assessing the costs, benefits and risks of alternative ways to meet government objectives. It helps decision makers to understand the potential effects, trade-offs and overall impact of options by providing an objective evidence base for decision-making*”. The Green Book provides comprehensive, approved guidance, methods and tools for the appraisal process, which apply “*to all proposals that concern public spending, taxation, changes to regulations, and changes to the use of existing public assets and resources.*” There are two main policy appraisal processes: the development of business cases to justify spending proposals, and Impact Assessments which evaluate the implications of new legislation or other policy changes. Less formal approaches can be applied to smaller scale or non-regulatory policies, programmes and projects.

The remainder of this section will focus on the two main appraisal processes described by the Green Book, in order to provide background for two specific research questions (*Can an improved approach robustly aid decision makers and assess value for money associated with policy changes applied in the context of marine? Can important trade-offs be established, quantified and where possible integrated into policy decision-making tools?*). However, it is also important to emphasise that other assessment and appraisal mechanisms (such as sustainability appraisal, strategic environmental assessment and environmental impact assessment) could also be framed in the natural capital context. Wider environmental management often requires the causality between changes in the social (human) system and changes in ecological systems to be identified. How this can be attempted in relation to natural capital is discussed further in Appendix 7.

Assessment of economic implications is central to the policy appraisal process; the economic dimension is described within the Green Book as “*the analytical heart of a business case.*” Furthermore, the guidance states that costs and benefits should be monetised where possible. However, the Green Book repeatedly emphasises that not all costs and benefits can be monetised or even quantified, but that these unmonetisable and unquantifiable factors must be appropriately accounted for. The use of scenarios and multicriteria decision analysis is recommended when dealing with non-monetary information. The Green Book also highlights that attempts to consolidate non-monetary information in summary measures (particularly a single number) may fail to capture adequately the full impacts of different options. Non-monetary techniques are primarily recommended for use in the evaluation of the preliminary long list of options. At the final stage of appraising short-listed options, cost benefit analysis is identified as the appropriate technique together with descriptions of unmonetizable impacts.

In addition to general guidance on the appraisal process, the Green Book makes specific reference to the natural capital context: “*the natural capital framework does not replace existing approaches to appraising and valuing environmental effects. Rather, by providing a more comprehensive framework within which to develop and appraise policy, it suggests additional options to meet policy goals and enables all options to be assessed more accurately for potential improvements and/or damage to the environment.*” In identifying the implications for natural capital, the guidance points out that appraisal requires an understanding of the biological and physical changes as well as economic valuation; that impacts and values are often geographically specific; and that the future scarcity values for goods and services are likely to rise over time. It is also emphasised that sustainable use should be considered, which requires assessment of the underlying asset (particularly in terms of ecological tipping points) as well as the marginal valuation of service loss, and the consideration of cumulative effects. An outline process for identifying the implications of policy interventions on natural capital is also defined (Table 9).

Table 9. The four step approach defined within the Green Book policy appraisal guidance to identify whether and how an intervention may affect natural capital and its benefits (HM Treasury, 2018)

<p>□ Step 1 – identify the environmental context of the proposal (“what and where?”):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Identify scale, location, outputs and spatial reach of the intervention; ○ what types of land cover and natural system will the proposal affect, directly or indirectly (e.g. farmland, urban green space, woodland, freshwaters, moorland, coastal margins)?
<p>□ Step 2 – consider bio-physical effects on natural assets (“how?”):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ which natural assets (such as land use, water bodies, species, wildlife habitats and soils) are specifically likely to be affected? ○ this step facilitates the assessment of relevant welfare effects in Step 3, as well as informing on the physical sustainability of natural stocks.
<p>□ Step 3 – consider the social welfare implications of the bio-physical effects identified in Step 2 (“what consequences?”):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ how are environmental goods and services to society affected by the changes to the assets? These goods and services may be classified as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. “provisioning” services such as supply of food, fuel, fibre and water which typically have market values. ii. “regulating” services such as water quality and quantity regulation, climate regulation, pollination, air quality regulation. iii. “cultural” services such as landscape and environmental spaces for recreation amenity, and cultural heritage. ○ “regulating” and “cultural” services do not typically have direct market values. The effects should be identified as far as possible and proportionately quantified and monetised. Unmonetised factors should be treated as recommended for all interventions.
<p>□ Step 4 – consider uncertainties and implementation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ environmental effects may be uncertain. Therefore, consideration needs to be given to quantifying these uncertainties as risks that must be costed and managed, so that they can be minimised, mitigated or where possible avoided. ○ critical factors should be identified and arrangements for monitoring included as part of intervention proposals in order to manage risks and optimise outcomes. ○ identification of mitigating measures is particularly important so that risks to natural assets can be minimised and benefits maximised.

The Green Book provides further, brief guidance (and in some cases indicative value estimates) related to valuing specific elements of natural capital including air quality, noise, waste, recreation, amenity value, landscape, water quality, flood risk and coastal erosion, vulnerability to climate change and biodiversity. The guidance also signposts other tools and sources of environmental valuation evidence. It names DEFRA’s Environmental Valuation Look-up Tool and the international Environmental Valuation Reference Inventory, both of which contain a small number of valuations for marine and coastal goods and services (and are discussed further in Section 4.6).

Where explicit reference to natural capital is made within the Green Book, this is primarily in the context of determining how policy decisions will impact upon it. In its third report, the Natural Capital Committee (2015) has a more specific focus on the use of the natural capital approach in justifying investment decisions, i.e. further expanding on how it could be used in developing a business case for fulfilling the objective stated in the Environment White Paper (HM Government, 2011) “to be the first generation to leave the natural environment in a better state than it inherited”. They provide a generic framework outlining the steps required to develop a natural capital investment programme (Figure 13), and also report their findings that, regarding marine and coastal natural capital, a strong economic case exists for creating intertidal habitats to meet objectives set out in Shoreline Management Plans and for restoring commercial fish stocks.

Figure 13. The steps in developing a strategy and programme of investment in natural capital (Natural Capital Committee, 2015)

4.6 Tools and resources to support application of the natural capital approach to policy

Generic resources exist designed for practitioners wishing to implement natural capital and ecosystem service assessment and valuation. The National Ecosystem Approach Toolkit (NEAT) hosted by the Ecosystems Knowledge Network, for example, was developed during the UK NEAFO (Scott *et al.*, 2014). This provides a comprehensive resource for selecting and using tools to apply an ecosystem approach to policies, plans, projects or programmes, and includes tools for valuation, cost benefit analysis, ecosystem mapping and performing a natural capital asset check (as proposed in the UK NEAFO by Dickie *et al.*, 2014a) amongst others. Scotland’s Natural Capital Asset Index also includes spreadsheets into which data on ecosystem area, service potential, service weighting, and indicators of quality can be entered to generate the index.

The Environment Agency has developed a methodology, and a supporting calculator tool, to determine the costs in monetary terms of pollution impacts on natural capital, which is designed to inform directly the Enforcement Undertaking offer made by the party responsible for the incident. Natural England’s Ecosystem Services Transfer Toolkit allows users to select a management measure for a given habitat and

see, on a five point scale, the direction and strength of changes in the delivery of ecosystem services across 19 categories (where appropriate evidence exists). The tool includes range of management measures for coastal and marine habitats, including examples related to fisheries, marine protected areas, energy, coastal defence, dredging, and wastewater discharge. The Outdoor Recreation Valuation (ORVal) model (Day & Smith, 2018) is an online tool that can be used to estimate the welfare value of visits to greenspace, including beaches.

Certain tools are also incorporating the concept of environmental net gain (which, on land refers to a development leaving biodiversity in a better state than before) as well as natural capital and ecosystem services. The Natural Capital Planning Tool is designed to enable local authorities, planners and developers to see more clearly the relative impacts of planning and development options on natural capital and so improve mitigation of negative effects and, ideally, take the opportunity to enhance natural capital assets. Coastal habitats do feature within the tool, although no case studies of coastal developments are available as yet. Natural England, with the support of academic partners, is also developing the Eco-metric to measure the ecosystem services delivered from net gains in biodiversity under different development options or scenarios of land use change. As with so many tools, this is being designed initially for terrestrial systems, with hopes for later pilots to determine its applicability for marine ecosystems.

Like much of the natural capital approach, there are fewer tools developed specifically for marine applications and within these, the definition of ‘tool’ is quite broad, and covers recommendations, guidance and methods, as well as models. Examples of some advanced marine-specific tools (TIDE, InVEST, AIRES) are given in Appendix 8. There are also several databases of published values for goods and services, although, again, these often have only limited entries relevant to UK marine and coastal assets (Table 10). The Environment Agency’s Benefits Inventory provides additional useful information including a matrix showing the services provided by the different broadscale habitats listed in NEA, and has a further direct link to the decision-making process as it includes a template for an Appraisal Summary Table (as required in regulatory Impact Assessment).

Table 10. Databases that include published values for UK marine and coastal goods and services

Database	Link	Number of UK marine or coastal studies (individual values)
DEFRA/eftec Environmental Value Look-up Tool	http://sciencesearch.defra.gov.uk/Default.aspx?Menu=Menu&Module=More&Location=None&Completed=0&ProjectID=19514	6
The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity	http://www.teebweb.org/publication/tthe-economics-of-ecosystems-and-biodiversity-valuation-database-manual/	7 (41)
Marine Ecosystem Services Partnership	http://map.marineecosystems-services.org/	42 (44)
National Ocean Economics Program	http://www.ocean-economics.org/	33
Environmental Valuation Reference Inventory	http://www.evri.ca/	48
ICES Marine and Coastal Cultural Ecosystem Services Knowledge Repository	http://www.ices.dk/community/groups/Pages/WGRMES-knowledge-repository-2.aspx	5
Environment Agency Benefits Inventory		9 (15)

5 Are existing frameworks fit for purpose?

5.1 Ecosystem service frameworks

The importance of conceptual frameworks such as the MEA, TEEB and the UK NEA in developing the ecosystem services component of the natural capital approach cannot be overstated. They have led to a broad convergence around (i) high-level classification of services within the provisioning, regulating and cultural categories, and (ii) propounding the fundamental principles that only endpoints should be valued and that value comprises much more than the economic component. However, researchers have rarely used these overarching frameworks for ecosystem service assessment in practice without first modifying them to suit the individual circumstances of the assessment being undertaken (as demonstrated by the examples in Appendix 2). This suggests that these frameworks provide a strong conceptual basis for ecosystem service assessment, but do not provide a standard operational classification that can be universally applied in practice.

It has been argued that the development of a standard classification framework is essential, to prevent confusion, maximise accessibility and increase the comparability and transferability of assessments between different locations, issues and scales (Beaumont *et al.*, 2007; Haines-Young & Potschin, 2010; Saunders *et al.*, 2010; Wallace, 2007). However, the difficulties of successfully developing a universally accepted, operationally effective classification system are also well documented, with some authors questioning whether this could ever be achieved (Costanza, 2008; de Groot *et al.*, 2002; Fisher *et al.*, 2009). There seems to be most potential for developing standardised classifications for final services, goods and benefits, and significant progress has been achieved here through CICES.

Developing a universal classification that aims to distinguish between final and intermediate/supporting services, or to classify this latter group, remains highly problematic. This is recognised within CICES, which does not attempt to classify the factors that underpin the supply of final services, and avoids the terms 'supporting' and 'intermediate' entirely (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018). Wider issues have been raised with the intermediate services category more generally. Even within the UK NEA, which proposes adoption of this characterisation, it has been noted that services can be intermediate or final depending on the context (Mace *et al.*, 2011). Unpolluted water, for example, is a final service to a bather, but an intermediate service to someone consuming shellfish. The need to clearly identify which components of the ecosystem should be valued in order to avoid double counting is not in doubt, but it has been argued that the intermediate services classification (which has its origins in the economic literature) is overly reductionist from the ecological perspective and is not useful in describing the phenomena that underpin ecosystem services (La Notte *et al.*, 2017; Potschin-Young *et al.*, 2017). From the practical perspective, it has also been noted that the available data by which the underlying ecosystem components are assessed may not strictly relate to intermediate services, and so adopting that terminology would be misleading (Dickie *et al.*, 2014b).

The discussion on how to deal with ecological functions and processes appears to have come full circle. Key foundations for the development of the ecosystem services approach were the recognition that the environment was undervalued because many of the linkages between essential ecosystem components and human welfare were indirect (de Groot *et al.*, 2002), and that continued failure to recognise the role and importance of supporting services could prevent effective management and contribute to continued environmental decline (Beaumont *et al.*, 2008; Ledoux & Turner, 2002). It was therefore argued that the definition of 'services' should be sufficiently wide to include the supporting functions, and hence highlight the importance of maintaining the integrity of the whole ecosystem (Fisher & Turner, 2008).

Attempts to operationalise frameworks which include intermediate services have demonstrated the limitations of this concept in practice, leading to suggestions that the underpinning factors that result in the supply of services could be better represented by concepts other than that of services, and documented in alternative ecosystem accounts (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018). The wider natural capital approach now provides this alternative framework to integrate different measures of ecosystem condition with the assessment and valuation of final ecosystem services. This does not mean that what are currently described as intermediate or supporting services should be ignored or hidden, or that an understanding of all the links in the chain from assets to benefits should no longer be pursued. The opposite is in fact the case. What is required is a shift of emphasis away from attempting to define intermediate services to, instead, explicitly recognising the role of ecological processes and functions in generating final services and benefits. Bateman and Wheeler (2018) have already adapted the UK NEA conceptual framework to remove the term 'intermediate services' and instead make explicit reference to ecological processes as a component of natural capital assets.

There has also been a lack of consistency in whether abiotic services are included within ecosystem service frameworks. These are derived from non-living components of ecosystems and include water for industrial use, energy and the provision of space and waterways (such as for military activity, shipping and for the transit and landfall of cables and pipelines). The reason for the exclusion of abiotic services may relate to an objective of frameworks such as the MEA and TEEB to document the value of biodiversity, which thus leads to a focus on the services provided by living organisms. In wider contexts, such as environmental impact assessment, a failure to consider abiotic benefits such as energy, shipping and aggregate extraction, would lead to inadequate treatment of all the relevant issues that may arise from a proposed new development. Feedback collated for the latest revision of CICES showed that more than half of users felt that services from the abiotic components of the ecosystem should be included within the framework, which has been expanded in response (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018).

It is also worth noting that a defining feature of ecosystem services is the demand side, but this is absent from most classifications systems that attempt to link directly to policy and management (with the exception of the United States Environmental Protection Agency's (2015) National Ecosystem Services Classification System). The issue of integrating demand has not been overlooked in the wider academic literature, however. Early, and highly cited, examples of methods for the assessment and mapping of integrated ecosystem service supply and demand include Burkhard *et al.* (2012), and a recent review (Wei *et al.*, 2017) provides 38 examples of integrated assessments, although these are primarily (if not entirely) in the terrestrial context.

Conclusions

Broadly, ecosystem service frameworks are fit for purpose, in that the strong conceptual foundation provided by high level frameworks such as the MEA, TEEB and UK NEA (which describe the main types of services and propose the 'cascade' from ecological components through to benefits and value) are applicable to the marine environment. Operationally, however, there are some limitations of the frameworks, particularly with regard to the category of 'intermediate' services. While the need to value only final services to avoid double counting is well recognised, developing a standardised approach to the classification and assessment of intermediate services appears unworkable as they are context specific. Also, the usefulness of intermediate services as a conceptual tool with regard to understanding underlying ecological components and their linkages through to final services and benefits is limited. The wider natural capital approach provides a framework to evaluate what are currently termed intermediate services (and wider functions and processes) as an integral (and explicit) component of ecosystem assets. Understanding of the role of ecological functions and processes in the supply of services and benefits should continue to be pursued to ensure they are adequately assessed and managed.

A standard classification system should be used in ecosystem service assessment, particularly to support applications such as accounting for which replication and comparability between assessments are essential. CICES is recommended as an appropriate framework. It clearly identifies and categorises the ecosystem endpoints (thus supporting valuation) and includes abiotic services (although is arranged in such a way as to simplify the process of excluding abiotic services where these are not considered relevant in a particular context). CICES represents the most concerted focus of intellectual effort on ecosystem service classification (as opposed to other aspects of conceptual development or application), including consultation with and feedback from large number of end-users. It is also popular across Europe and globally, and so has the potential to support international collaborations and comparisons, particularly across North Atlantic areas. CICES continues to evolve, and may require further testing and verification to ensure it is robust within the marine context, and to provide additional marine examples of different services to support its application. Ongoing work by the European Environment Agency (Culhane *et al.*, in draft) should provide further insight. Although CICES has begun to dominate ecosystem service assessment, alternative classifications that consider categorization from the demand side should be explored further to determine how these could support the wider natural capital approach.

5.2 Assessment frameworks

Most of the available guidance, scoping and pilot studies have a clear bias towards the terrestrial environment. The Natural Capital Committee (2017) guidance, for example, includes only terrestrial examples, and acknowledges that equivalent systems for, for example, defining land use types (as opposed to habitat classifications) in asset registers will need to be developed for marine areas. The difficulties in developing natural capital asset registers or condition assessments applicable across all ecosystems are exemplified by Scotland's Natural Capital Asset Index (NCAI). This does not include marine habitats at all, and those considered coastal are found above the spring high water level. During the scoping

phase for the NCAI the possibilities of including Scottish territorial waters including estuaries were explored (Hambrey & Armstrong, 2010). However, offshore marine habitats were excluded from the published index, with the recommendation that a separate marine index was produced (Blaney & Fairley, 2012), for which a scoping exercise is currently underway.

The lack of marine examples does not mean that the frameworks are not fit for purpose. However, it does mean that it is not possible to evaluate the frameworks comprehensively in the marine context. Dedicated pilot studies for the marine and coastal environment at national, regional, local and site scales are required to test the applicability of the different approaches. Mace *et al.* (2015), for example, proposed a general framework for a risk register and they did not conduct detailed assessment for marine and coastal assets. As such, some of their assumptions and conclusions in relation to marine and coastal assets warrant further investigation and challenge around, for example, their assumption of no/negligible relationship between quality of the marine environment and delivery of equitable climate benefits. The work of Lovett *et al.* (2018) also highlights that risk registers will change according to the spatial scale of the assessment.

As illustrated by Section 4.4, the development of monetary natural capital accounts has provided the greatest number of marine and coastal examples. Certain habitats and services (fisheries, carbon sequestration, recreation, saltmarsh, and sea defence) have featured most frequently in scoping studies and pilot accounts to date, presumably as they are the most straightforward and most amenable to the direct transfer of terrestrial approaches. There is a pressing need to explore how other services and marine components could be incorporated for different policy contexts and scales. Using methods not related to habitat extent are likely to be required for this, and it could be misleading solely to estimate the value of relatively trivial services simply because they have the best data and ignore more important services where valuation is more challenging (eftec, 2015).

A key characteristic of Mace *et al.*'s (2015) framework for risk registers is that the assets included “*are plausibly subject to management by people in some way to restore or recover, or to restrict use to non-significant rates of loss, or for use by future generations.*” In the pelagic environment in particular, many of the factors affecting the quality of, and threats to, assets (and the benefits they deliver) occur at the global scale. It is important, therefore, that this element of the framework is not interpreted to mean that risks which require international management can be considered irrelevant at national (and smaller) levels when priorities and investment decisions are being decided.

Mace *et al.* (2015) note that the delivery of benefits is based on complex interactions and interdependencies between natural capital assets. The format of the risk register they propose is set up to highlight the risk to benefits, at the point at which the benefit is delivered. However, particularly in the marine environment, this is not necessarily where the source of the risk occurs. For example, Mace *et al.* (2015) highlight how the quantity of food from the marine environment may be affected by the loss of saltmarsh nursery habitats, which are classified within coastal margins. The risk register therefore needs to be supported by further supplementary tables where the source of the risk is explicitly defined. This will be of particular use in supporting cost effective investment decisions, as it will potentially highlight how addressing key threats can secure or improve the delivery of multiple benefits. Finally, Mace *et al.* (2015) use policy targets as thresholds for risk. However, these may not be sufficient to manage ecological risk, and so targets for natural capital assets should be based on ecological knowledge.

More effort has been dedicated to developing terrestrial natural capital accounts, but certain overarching lessons learned from these experiences have particular relevance to the marine context. These include the need to assess whether the feasible level of detail for the accounts suits the policy issue at stake, and the potential mismatch between the availability of information and the level at which decisions are made (Ruijs & van der Esch, 2017). It has also been suggested that the regular production of environmental accounts has not been matched by corresponding progress in using the accounts to make better decisions (Burnett, 2017). In the policy context, Natural England assessed the applicability of using corporate natural capital accounting to monitor nature reserves (Clark, 2017). Managers found the exercise useful for identifying the goods and services reserves provide, but taking an accounting approach to monitoring would be complex and resource intensive, and would only partially represent the value of the reserves, creating the risk that summary information could be misused. Simpler alternatives for monitoring within a natural capital framework were considered more suitable.

Most progress to formalise natural capital assessment frameworks has been made for flows (as a result of two decades of research in developing ecosystem service approaches) and latterly effort has focused on monetary benefits in response to the need for economic accounts. Frameworks for the assessment of natural capital stocks are less well developed. These have been explored in the creation of asset and risk registers and physical accounts, but as yet there have been few pilot studies, and so no coalescence

around best practice. However, while there are few examples of stock assessment frameworks badged as natural capital, there are well established approaches used more widely for conservation and management purposes, such as condition assessments for Sites of Special Scientific Interest and monitoring for Good Environmental Status. There is a need for a detailed review of such existing approaches and programmes to develop best practice for natural capital assessment, which links to the other components of the approach.

Conclusions

The overarching frameworks that guide the application of specific components of the natural capital approach such as asset and risk registers and natural capital accounts appear broadly fit for purpose. However, there is a lack of specific guidance and examples for marine natural capital. Additional pilot studies are therefore required, for different goods and services, contexts and scales, to test more comprehensively the suitability of these frameworks.

5.3 Habitat classifications

The classifications of coastal and marine habitats that have been developed across different natural capital applications to date are generally very coarse. As was noted in the development of risk registers, broad habitat types are an inadequate representation of natural capital (Mace *et al.*, 2015). One limitation is that broad classifications do not consider different sediment types and key functional groups of organisms are not represented; for example, mud and sand habitats support different ecosystem services, and subtidal sediments with oyster reefs will function very differently to those without (Potts *et al.*, 2014). The disaggregation of vegetated habitats from broader sedimentary habitats is a step forward (although is often proposed only for saltmarsh). There is a limit to the number of distinct habitats that can feasibly and cost-effectively be considered within natural capital assessments and reporting, although this will vary with the scale and purpose of the activity. However, vegetated habitats and biogenic reefs (intertidal and subtidal) are fundamental habitats.

Generally in the development of frameworks, efforts by EU agencies have been focused towards the more ecological components of natural capital, while the UK has had a stronger focus on the monetary component. The habitat classification in the EU MAES programme (Maes *et al.*, 2013) is most systematic in its selection of the broad habitat categories, and it does include biogenic reefs, although it lacks the disaggregation of vegetated habitats. MAES is also unique in considering pelagic habitats alongside benthic, with different salinities differentiated as well as different marine zones (e.g. coastal, shelf and oceanic). This is fundamental to an adequate habitat classification framework; it begins to acknowledge the role of the water column in the supply and distribution of services, and also that the current system which has been derived from a land cover perspective is inadequate for the marine environment.

Conclusions

The marine and coastal habitat classifications used within natural capital frameworks in the UK policy context are not yet fit for purpose. We explore mechanisms to provide a more suitable habitat classification for marine and coastal systems in the following section.

6 How can existing habitat classification frameworks be improved?

6.1 Coastal habitats

The choice of habitat classification underlies the other components within the natural capital approach: habitats are the fundamental 'units' around which asset and risk registers and accounts are developed. Coastal habitats in particular and how to classify them has been identified as an issue in the development of accounts (eftec, 2015; ONS, 2016). Established systems exist for the classification of coastal habitats, principally the European Nature Information System (EUNIS) which distinguishes splash zone habitats such as dunes (supralittoral, and classified as coastal) from intertidal (littoral) and fully submerged (infralittoral and below) both of which fall under the marine category. EUNIS also provides classifications for saline water bodies. The UK NEA coastal margin classification (Jones *et al.*, 2011) is a hybrid of four supralittoral and one littoral habitat, as well as coastal lagoons, but its justification for why these were chosen as the "main" coastal habitats is not clear. Classifications such as EUNIS, which have a more robust and systematic basis for categorisation are more useful.

The development of pilot accounts has also raised issues of whether coastal habitats should be considered within marine accounts or together with terrestrial natural capital. The former was proposed by eftec (2015)

and ONS (2016), while the latter was broadly the case in the development of the Scotland's Natural Capital Asset Index (although no littoral habitats were included). From a pragmatic perspective, the argument for combined terrestrial and coastal accounts is perhaps stronger. The Land Cover Map and Countryside Survey both include supralittoral and littoral rock, sediment and vegetated habitats (including mudflats, a key intertidal habitat missing from the NEA coastal classification) and so these will be mapped and assessed in the same way as terrestrial habitats. Fully submerged habitats lack this systematic, repeated assessment at the national level and will require entirely different extent and condition monitoring. However, littoral habitats are also an integral component of the marine environment. Therefore the condition assessment would have to take account of the tidal state (to ensure the full extent of the intertidal was appropriately mapped) and be expanded to reflect the role of the intertidal zone in supporting marine services (such as how saltmarsh serves as a nursery habitat for commercial fish species).

Alternatively, perhaps its unique position at the interface between terrestrial and marine, and with ecological and economic links to both, suggests that the coastal zone does require a separate assessment and accounting process. The coastal margin is small compared to the overall marine area, and changes in its extent will have only fractional effect on overall extent of the marine ecosystem (eftec, 2015). Yet, coastal habitats are under significant pressure, which is likely to increase under climate change at the same time as the services provided in terms of hazard protection become more important. A separate account would ensure these changes were highlighted and not lost within a wider marine account. A similar argument holds for ensuring that key marine habitats that have particular functional roles or disproportionate value are disaggregated to avoid changes to them being lost within a catch-all marine category.

6.2 Disaggregation of broadscale habitats

In order to define an appropriate habitat classification system it is necessary to understand how different habitats deliver particular components of natural capital and thus which are distinct in natural capital terms and where emphasis should be placed. Fletcher *et al.* (2012) conducted a literature review to provide baseline understanding of the marine ecosystem services provided by the broad scale habitats and features of conservation importance that were likely to be protected by Marine Conservation Zones (MCZs) and some European Marine Site features (e.g. saline lagoons, submarine structures made by leaking gases and submerged and partially submerged sea caves). Each feature was reviewed to identify the beneficial ecosystem processes and ecosystem services using a systematic search method. This approach was extended and elaborated by Potts *et al.*, (2014) to include features from other marine protected area (MPA) designations. A similar approach for broader-scale habitats using a slightly different ecosystem services typology was included in the UK NEAFO (Turner *et al.*, 2014). These studies produced structured assessment matrices for habitats and species, with scores on the importance of particular features supplying services, goods and benefits which were populated using peer reviewed and grey literature and expert opinion.

We used these matrices as the starting point for an assessment of which habitats should be identified within a marine natural capital classification. Data from Potts *et al.* (2014) was used, since this includes data from Fletcher *et al.* (2012) but has additional features and ecosystem services categories and it has been subjected to peer review. However, there are a large number of habitats within these matrices. Therefore in order to prioritise the habitats for inclusion in the classification, we scored each according to the extent to which it supported different ecosystem services, or levels of service delivery, compared to its parent broadscale habitat. The final matrix is contained in Appendix 9 (an extract of which is provided in Table 11). The ecosystem services provided by the marine features follow the UKNEA classification (as used by Potts *et al.*, 2014); correspondence to the CICES classification is also shown in Appendix 9. Confidence in the evidence from which the ecosystem service scores is reported in Potts *et al.* (2014).

From this process, it became clear that algal dominated habitats should be considered separately from underlying rock, and that biogenic reefs are distinct from sediments with less structured biological communities. For biogenic habitats, the ecosystem services provided are different according the biota forming the reefs. Bivalve reefs such as blue mussel and horse mussel beds provide different services to the reefs generated by honeycomb and ross worms, which is related to the different functioning of these biologically mediated habitats.

Table 11. Correspondence between broadscale habitats and habitats protected under EU and national legislation with their provision of ecosystem services (ES)

Feature (Bold type represents broadscale habitats, normal type represents habitat features of conservation importance)	Natural capital functions and processes							Regulating Services			
	Primary production	Larval and juvenile supply	Nutrient cycling	Water cycling	Formation of species habitat	Formation of physical barriers	Formation of seascape	Biological control	Natural hazard regulation	Waste breakdown and detoxification	Carbon sequestration
High energy intertidal rock	3	3	1	0	3	3	1		3	0	1
Tide-swept algal communities	0	1	2	0	1	1	1		1	3	2
Peat and clay exposures		2		0	1	2					
Littoral chalk communities	2	2		0	1	3				0	
Moderate energy intertidal rock	2	2	1	0	3	3			3	0	1
Intertidal under boulder communities	1	0		0	1	2			2	0	
Low energy intertidal rock	1	1	1	0	3	3			3	0	1
Estuarine rocky habitats	1	1		0	1	0			1	0	
Sea loch egg wrack beds	2	1	2	0	1	1			1	3	2
Submerged or partially submerged sea caves				0	0	3			3	0	1
Intertidal biogenic reefs	3	2	2	0	3	2	1		2	2	2
Blue Mussel beds	2	0	0	0	1	1	1		1	0	0
Honeycomb worm <i>Sabellaria alveolata</i> reef		1	2	0	0	2			0	2	2

Key

 Scale of ES supplied: 3 Significant 2 Moderate 1 Low 0 None/negligible Not assessed

Scores from Potts et al. (2014).

 Greyscale = **parent broadscale habitat**, or **no difference** in ES provision between feature and parent broadscale habitat

 Purple = **difference** in ES provision of protected habitat from parent broadscale habitat:

 Highly differentiated Moderately differentiated Slightly differentiated

Note: scores in purple cells remain those for the scale of ES supplied (from Potts et al., 2014)

 Orange = Mean difference in ES score class >1 (+ve or -ve) compared to parent broadscale habitat

6.3 Recommended habitat classification for marine and coastal natural capital

Table 12 outlines the minimum number of marine and coastal categories that we believe should be used for natural capital assessment, based on previous work and understanding of the ecosystem services provided by these broad habitat types. This classification closely follows MAES (Maes et al., 2013), but, in terms of defining broad zones, we do not separate marine inlets and transitional waters from coastal areas. This is because they share the same benthic habitat types. Also, separation of the splash zone from the intertidal is potentially more important, given how coastal habitats are currently monitored within UK national land cover assessments. However, the extent and condition assessment for littoral coastal habitats needs to take account of their full intertidal extent and their function as an integral part of the marine environment.

Across coastal, shelf and deep sea zones, vegetated and macroalgal-dominated habitats as well as biogenic reefs are disaggregated due to their disproportionate contribution to the supply of ecosystem services compared with rock or sedimentary habitats (Appendix 9). There is also an argument for different types of sedimentary habitats (mud, sand and coarse substrates, for example) to be separated. We have proposed this for intertidal sediments, given that the different classes are already monitored separately during land cover assessments. However, there are more issues around data availability for subtidal areas (see Section 7), and so the broad habitat was not disaggregated beyond the separation of rock from sedimentary sea-beds. There are different types of vegetated and biogenic habitats, which will vary depending on location and conditions. A full list of all possible habitat types, was not considered useful for the purposes of this discussion and so only examples (of widespread habitats) are presented in Table 12.

We further follow MAES in including a pelagic habitat for each zone below the coastal margin. Further disaggregation of the pelagic habitats should be considered, particularly according to the low, variable and fully marine salinity that is found within transitional and coastal waters, and thus the unique features of, for

example, lagoons and estuaries. Shelf waters should be considered in terms of vertical mixing (well mixed, seasonally stratified, permanently stratified), and depth layers will have a bearing on open ocean waters, particularly in relation to light penetration and hence the capacity for primary production.

Increasing the level of disaggregation has the potential to increase data requirements, and this must be balanced against the practical and financial constraints on doing so. However, vegetated habitats and biogenic reefs are potentially better studied and monitored than broader scale habitats as they are often already identified as being of ecological importance. For example, biogenic reefs and the saltmarsh species *Salicornia* (as well as machair and vegetated sea cliffs) are among the marine and coastal habitats listed in Annex I of the Habitats Directive, and mussel, oyster and maerl beds, together with *Sabellaria* worm reefs and seagrass are some Features of Conservation Importance within Marine Conservation Zones. Linking natural capital assessment to ongoing monitoring programmes is very important to ensure cost-effective data collection.

Table 12. Recommended marine habitat categories for assessments at a national scale

Zone	Habitat type	Classification	
		EUNIS	Land cover map/ Countryside survey
Coastal margin (splash zone)	Sand dunes	B1 Coastal dunes & sandy shores	Supralittoral sediment
	Machair	B1.9 Machair	
	Shingle	B2 Coastal shingle	Supralittoral rock
	Sea cliffs	B3 Rock cliffs, ledges & shores	
Coastal (intertidal)	Littoral rock	A1 Littoral rock	Littoral rock
	Littoral sediment	A2 Littoral sediment	Littoral sediment:
	Mudflat	A2.3 Littoral mud	mud
	Saltmarsh	A2.5 Coastal saltmarshes	saltmarsh
	Littoral seagrass	A2.61 Littoral seagrass beds	<i>no explicit reference</i>
	Biogenic reef, <i>for example</i> <i>Sabellaria</i> reefs	A2.7 Littoral biogenic reefs	<i>no explicit reference</i>
	<i>Mussel</i> beds	A2.71 Littoral <i>Sabellaria</i> reefs	
		A2.72 Littoral mussel beds	
Transitional & coastal waters			
Shelf	Sublittoral rock	A3/4 Infra/circalittoral rock	n/a
	Sublittoral sediment	A5 Sublittoral sediment	
	Sublittoral vegetated habitats <i>for example</i> <i>Maerl</i>	A5.5 Sublittoral macrophyte-dominated sediment	
	<i>Macroalgae</i>	A5.51 <i>Maerl</i> beds	
	<i>Seagrass</i>	A3.21–2/A5.52 <i>Kelp & seaweed</i>	
	Biogenic reef, <i>for example</i> <i>Native oyster</i> reefs	A5.52 <i>Sublittoral seagrass</i>	
		A5.6 Sublittoral biogenic reef	
	A5.64 <i>Ostrea edulis</i> beds		
Shelf waters			
Open Ocean	Deep sea rock	A6.1 Deep sea rock	n/a
	Deep sea sediment	A6.3-5 Deep sea sediment	
	Deep sea corals	A6.61 Deep sea corals	
	Oceanic waters		

6.4 The need for alternative approaches

The use of defined, discrete, spatially-bound habitats as service providing ‘units’ illustrates the way in which the natural capital approach has been developed primarily from land cover mapping approaches in the terrestrial environment. This methodology remains appropriate for benthic components of coastal and marine systems, although (as will be discussed in Section 7) issues of data availability can be a significant barrier to its effective use in practice. However, this approach does not recognise certain key aspects of marine systems. In particular, large numbers of species (from plankton to whales) move horizontally and vertically through the water column on different spatial scales and may use different habitats (benthic and pelagic) for different phases of their lifecycle. Also, not all environmental change manifests in relation to changes in spatial extent. Phytoplankton, for example, have a seasonal succession of blooms, which used to be matched to seasonal succession of higher species that could consume them including larval fish of

commercial importance and small fish important for seabirds. Climate change is affecting the timing of blooms, which is reducing the productivity and survival of some fish and bird species in UK waters. These issues may be particularly apparent as challenges for the marine environment, but they are relevant to terrestrial systems which also support migratory species (particularly birds) and face issues of how phenology might be affected by climate change. As yet, however, the natural capital approach does not adequately account for these factors, and determining mechanisms by which it can do so is an important area for further research.

Researchers focussing specifically on marine systems have attempted to take a different approach to defining the ecological interactions required for service provision. Culhane *et al.* (2018) begin to develop an approach that systematically describes and documents the combinations of habitats (benthic and pelagic) and specific biotic groups that are necessary for the supply of ecosystem services. Their approach allows for mobile species (and other biotic groups) to be linked to spatial units while also reflecting that these associations may be temporary (e.g. for feeding) and/or occur at specific lifecycle stages. Culhane *et al.* (2018) took account of four key aspects in defining species-habitat linkages: (i) fully capturing the functioning of biodiversity that underpins service supply; (ii) reflecting that biota can vary in their functioning between habitats and locations and the reliance of mobile species on multiple habitats; (iii) accounting for the differences between taxa in their vulnerability to human pressures; and (iv) making the approach relevant to assessment currently carried out under existing environmental regulation. Further testing of this approach would be required to determine its applicability in practice and in specific decision making contexts.

Culhane *et al.*'s (2018) research reflects that natural capital is a broad concept, and different factors influence asset quality and ecosystem service provision. In recognition of this, it is recommended that the units of assessment are not described as 'habitats'. While 'Service Providing Unit' lacks the recognition factor of 'habitat', it does support appropriately wide definition and has some traction in the academic literature (e.g. Luck *et al.*, 2003; Culhane *et al.*, 2018).

The way the ocean is exploited and managed also differs from the terrestrial environment and this may require further alternative approaches in applying the natural capital approach in policy and decision making for marine systems. In particular, the marine environment is a common pool resource. The rival and non-excludable nature of common pool resources (as occurs in, for example, fisheries) adds additional complexity to governance and to the development of mechanisms such as Payments for Ecosystem Services schemes (Fisher *et al.*, 2010). In the absence of defined boundaries and property rights, a different approach of management and data gathering strategies may need to be designed for the future.

6.5 Conclusions

It is essential that the habitats chosen as service providing 'units', and thus constituting the foundation of natural capital assessment, are selected appropriately. A consistent classification with a logical basis is required, for which EUNIS is recommended. For the purposes of natural capital frameworks, the broad category of 'coastal' should extend to the low water mark (i.e. consistently including all supralittoral and littoral habitats). Unless they are to be considered entirely separately, coastal habitats should be included within terrestrial assessment programmes (rather than marine), in recognition of the national monitoring systems that already span land and coastal habitats, but extent and condition monitoring must be modified to ensure that it encompasses the full intertidal extent and marine functional aspects.

Benthic habitat classifications should be further disaggregated to ensure vegetated habitats and biogenic reefs are adequately assessed. Classifications must also include pelagic habitats. This requires some salinity and stratification distinctions to recognise key functional aspects. Frameworks for assessment of pelagic habitats must also encompass the dynamic nature of the system, for example the spatial and temporal mobility of plankton, fish and marine mammals. Adequate classification and assessment of the pelagic system, and the interconnected nature of spatially disparate components of the wider marine environment, is a major omission in, and also a real challenge for, frameworks for the natural capital approach. Natural capital frameworks should also avoid describing the underlying assessment units as 'habitats' as this fails to recognise the breadth of ecological factors that contribute to the condition of assets and the provision of services.

7 Ecological data

7.1 Selecting appropriate indicators

Appropriate measurement and monitoring is a further essential component of the natural capital approach. The metrics for measuring the elements of natural capital have also been considered (Natural Capital Committee, 2014). Those for natural capital stocks should reflect the key features of the asset, such as species richness, abundance and distribution; habitat area and condition; and metrics applied for national monitoring of environmental quality. In considering the implications shown by change in these metrics, the Natural Capital Committee makes particular reference to the need for thresholds and safe limits for sustainable use to be determined as part of the approach. The selection and analysis of indicators can contribute to the development of a more detailed understanding of the links between natural capital assets and flows of ecosystem services as a whole, potentially leading to more informed management plans and a transparent decision-making process (Ashley et al, 2018).

As with the development of frameworks, the ecosystem services component of the natural capital approach has been the focus of most attention, and a number of studies have considered indicators for marine ecosystem services (Atkins *et al.*, 2015; Hattam *et al.*, 2015; Maes *et al.*, 2018, Lusardi *et al.*, in press). Indicators are proxies for complex phenomena and can be used to reflect the provision of a service and how it is changing over time (Hattam *et al.*, 2015). Indicators can support management activities as well as contribute to studies aiming to understand and value changes in ecosystem service provision (Niemeijer & de Groot, 2008).

Liquete *et al.* (2013) used a meta-analysis to systemically review the current status and future prospects for the assessment of marine and coastal ecosystems services. They identified 145 publications that specifically assess marine ecosystem services, mainly with a focus on mangroves and coastal wetlands in Europe and North America. From this they created a catalogue of 476 ecosystem service indicators and identified gaps in knowledge. Most indicators related to a limited set of ecosystem services and benefits, including food provision (fisheries), water purification, coastal protection and recreation/tourism. However, this rigorous systematic review provides a foundation for the development of future ecosystem service assessments in the marine environment.

Within the European marine context, both Böhnke-Henrichs *et al.* (2013) and Hattam *et al.* (2015) have identified sets of marine ecosystem service indicators within the TEEB framework. Böhnke-Henrichs *et al.* (2013) point out that the lack of a well-structured, systematic classification and assessment of marine ecosystem services has resulted in the lack of application of the concept to marine planning and management. They found consistency in the literature for indicators for certain service types (e.g. 'sea food', 'raw materials', and 'climate regulation'), but the measures for other services were diverse (e.g. 'waste treatment', 'coastal erosion', and 'recreation and leisure'). Some ecosystem service types did not have indicators (e.g. 'genetic resources', 'ornamental resources', and 'biological control'); suitable indicators were suggested.

Hattam *et al.* (2015) reviewed indicators for different service types, and applied them to a case study (Dogger Bank) and conclude that:

- food provision indicators are well established and relatively easy to quantify;
- indicators for regulating services are used to track degradation, often after damage has occurred; and are not able to anticipate or predict future changes;
- few indicators have been developed for cultural services, with most studies focussing on recreation and tourism; indicators were also unclear on definitions, purpose and understanding of processes measured (changes in indicators may reflect human preferences rather than ecosystem state).

Furthermore, the need to distinguish between indicators of ecological processes contributing to the delivery of ecosystem services and indicators of benefits that reveal realised human use or enjoyment of an ecosystem service was identified. The authors argued that it is only when these two indicator types are combined that change can be detected and appropriate management actions taken.

Atkins *et al.* (2015) identified a set of ecosystem service indicators for ecosystem components and processes, intermediate services, final services and goods/benefits applicable in a practical way to UK coastal and marine systems. In addition, they identify national level data sources available to support indicator use for the UK. These indicators express quantity (e.g. abundance, extent) and quality (e.g. condition, production) at a given point in time, and also changes in ecosystem services to reflect the

trajectory and/or behaviour of ecosystem service provision. This consideration of the temporal scale is key to understanding change in either stocks (natural capital assets) or flows of benefits.

Indicators from the above studies that could inform natural capital assessment have been aggregated (Appendix 10) and example UK sources have been supplied to determine the likely availability of data in practice. In addition, where there are known policy drivers for monitoring that could drive data collection, these have also been included. Given the inconsistencies between different analytical frameworks for ecosystem services, only broad CICES classes or what approximate to 'Final ecosystem services' in the UK NEA classification have been included.

Few studies have attempted to identify indicators directly in the context of the natural capital approach for systems marine, even though in the terrestrial this is comparatively well developed. Natural England (Lusardi *et al.*, in press) have identified indicators for some coastal margin and marine components (Appendix 11), which link to the quality, quantity and spatial configuration attributes defined in the risk register approach of Mace *et al.* (2015). Vegetated habitats and some key biogenic habitats have been drawn out to be considered separately, which matches with the recommended in the improved habitat classification framework above.

If natural capital asset registers and condition assessments are to be feasible it is likely they will need to link to ongoing data collection programmes. Data used in government-led programmes has been highlighted as being most appropriate for extent and condition assessments in national accounts, as non-centralised data may lack the necessary comparability and consistency (Weatherdon *et al.*, 2017). However, it is not yet well understood how effective data from statutory monitoring programmes meets the requirements of specific assessment processes (such as natural capital accounting).

The different natural capital habitat classifications were aligned with MSFD benthic broad habitat types to identify commonality in the typology between the different classifications. The reason that MSFD benthic broad habitat types was used as the comparator is because future data collation will be conducted at this hierarchical level. Thus there may be an opportunity to use habitat condition data to assess future marginal changes to biotic marine seabed assets. The other classifications that were compared to MSFD broad habitat types were: UKNEA, UKNEAFO, MAES plus OSPAR threatened and declining habitats and MCZ habitats of conservation importance were also included since many of these conservation priority habitats comprise complex structures and processes which support ecosystem service provision (Appendix 12). The key points are that MSFD only concerns benthic habitats; transitional and coastal margin habitats are not featured. They are both represented in the MAES classification while the UK NEA and UKNEAFO include coastal margins but not transitional waters. There is generally good correspondence between MAES and MSFD broad habitat types aside from the lack of differentiation between infralittoral and circalittoral in MAES, this is important because of primary production that takes place in the infralittoral (e.g. kelp forests vs deeper aphotic animal dominated communities). In addition key vegetated habitats are identified in the UKNEAFO such as kelp forests and seagrass beds. By contrast the UKNEA and UKNEAFO has much broader categorisation, with just one class of deep sea habitat compared with 6 subtypes identified in MSFD broad habitat types and MAES.

7.2 Are existing ecological data fit for purpose? What are the key gaps in evidence?

The availability of data is a key challenge, particularly in the marine environment, as was highlighted across studies that have scoped different elements of the natural capital approach. The lack of annual data was highlighted as the main weakness for marine indicators in Scotland's NCAI (Hambrey & Armstrong, 2010). Inconsistent data collection across most marine species groups was a similar issue for the development of a risk register (Mace *et al.*, 2015). The Natural Capital Asset Check is has large data requirements and requires a high level of expertise to implement, and the usefulness of the approach can be limited if these are not available (Dickie *et al.*, 2014a).

The MAES framework has been applied in practice at the European level, across eight broad ecosystem types, including marine (Erhard *et al.*, 2016), and again demonstrates how issues with the availability of the required evidence can limit the scope of a condition assessment. The four marine ecosystem types proposed in the MAES typology (namely marine inlets and transitional waters, coastal, shelf, and open ocean (Maes *et al.*, 2013) were aggregated into a single marine assessment due to a lack of data. Only two terrestrial categories were similarly combined.

At a more local level, the issue of data availability was raised repeatedly within pilot marine natural capital accounts and scoping studies. Flood protection and erosion control were considered difficult to account for due to context specificity (eftec, 2015; RSPB, 2017; White *et al.*, 2015b). Certain habitats have the capacity

to provide flood protection, but whether or not they are likely to do so depends on the flood risk and also the existence and type of existing management measures. The combination of this data is often lacking for specific locations. More generally for the marine environment, the absence of spatial and/or time series data, as well as the lack of understanding of the links between extent, condition and the value of benefits was noted (eftec, 2015; ONS, 2016; Weatherdon, 2018; Weatherdon *et al.*, 2017).

Ecosystem services is one of the most studied components of the natural capital approach, but literature reviews have concluded that here again the evidence base supporting linkages between marine features and ecosystem services is highly inconsistent; with some features offering the potential for relatively strong conclusions whereas others offered little or no evidence (Fletcher *et al.*, 2012). Substantially more evidence was related to:

- habitats than species (the evidence base for individual species for both processes and ecosystem services was very limited with no evidence at all for most species);
- beneficial ecosystem processes than ecosystem services;
- certain processes such as primary and secondary production, larval/gamete supply, food web dynamics, formation of species habitat and species diversification; and
- commercial fisheries (food provisioning) than other ecosystem services.

Overall, matrices identifying which marine features are associated with which ecosystem services have only included broad scale habitats and features designated in MPAs, and are thus not comprehensive in terms of the marine features assessed and reviewed. Arguably, they are most valuable in quickly identifying the strong associations with high confidence or conversely highlighting the gaps in our knowledge, which are particularly extensive in terms of the ecosystem services provided by marine species (Burdon *et al.*, 2017; Fletcher *et al.*, 2012; Potts *et al.*, 2014). At the time of writing, there is insufficient understanding to fully implement a matrix-based approach to assess all ecosystem service types from all marine features, but it could play an important role in highlighting where to direct future empirical work.

Even more fundamentally, there is a lack of confidence in the baseline data that can inform on the extent of natural capital assets; outside of designated sites the only available data are often modelled predictions, or stock assessment surveys designed to provide data on commercial fish (Rees *et al.*, 2018). Similarly, the condition of many marine ecosystems is unknown, and where information does exist it may not be sufficiently geo-referenced to allow mapping (Erhard *et al.*, 2016). This considerable information gap between spatial assessments of marine and terrestrial ecosystem services is widely acknowledged (Liquete *et al.*, 2013). The situation is better within MPAs where detailed data is more likely to be available as the extent of features have previously been surveyed and condition assessments undertaken for designated habitats and species features (Rees *et al.*, 2018).

Perhaps more positively, participants at the international workshop suggested that adopting the natural capital approach provides the opportunity to re-think and re-focus future marine data collection. Environmental monitoring is currently focused on regulation and assessment in relation to EU Directives. This monitoring can align with natural capital, for example Good Environmental Status within the Marine Strategy Framework Directive incorporates traditional fishery measures such as Maximum Sustainable Yield with others like precautionary biomass. However, the natural capital approach provides the opportunity to think more broadly about why we are interested in monitoring and assessing assets, beyond requirements to do so for a specific policy.

Conclusions

In general, data for the UK marine environment are inconsistent, and there are significant gaps in understanding how habitats and species support the delivery of ecosystem services. Additionally, knowledge of the location and extent of habitats across most of the marine area is derived from model outputs and therefore highly uncertain. In consequence, a system of natural capital assessment based on the quality and quantity of marine benthic habitats (i.e. following terrestrial strategies such as the NCAI) will be unworkable in practice at the national level. The investment that would be required to map and monitor these habitats with adequate confidence and regularity using current approaches is likely to be prohibitive. Future innovations and advances in technology may reduce costs and increase opportunities.

There is greater potential for the quantity and quality of marine benthic habitats to be understood and monitored at smaller spatial scales, such as for an individual protected area, where the resource requirements are less and ongoing condition assessment may be a statutory requirement. However, if such projects are not resourced on an ongoing basis, the frequency of monitoring data may be in doubt. Also, marine protected areas may not be (indeed are potentially unlikely to be) representative of the wider

environment. The Marine Pioneer project is one of four Pioneers established through the 25 Year Environment Plan (HM Government 2018), a primary objective of which is to explore applying a natural capital approach to decision making. Ongoing work in the North Devon and Suffolk case study sites is piloting applications including asset and risk registers and natural capital accounting. There are significant synergies between the approaches discussed in this report and the practical work within the Marine Pioneer, which is being facilitated through the NERC-funded South West Partnership for the Environment and Economic Prosperity (SWEEP). It will be possible to learn useful lessons from these integrated projects.

7.3 How can the availability of appropriate ecological data be improved?

Sensitivity as a proxy for condition assessment

Key to understanding the relationship between coastal and marine habitats, ecosystem services and natural capital is the ability to incorporate some measure of condition or 'ecosystem status' into mapping applications (Maes *et al.*, 2012). However our understanding of the relationship between the condition of ecosystems and the services that they deliver is poorly understood and widely debated, in both terrestrial and marine systems (Maes *et al.*, 2012). Changes in ecosystems and their services are often non-linear and can often be accelerating, abrupt and potentially irreversible (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). In the absence of direct extent and condition data the use of proxies, particularly pressure indicators such as abrasion caused by fishing, is a possible alternative solution (eftec, 2015; Weatherdon, 2018), which has considerable potential when combined with sensitivity information.

Some attempts have been made to consider the sensitivity of goods and services to pressures. For example, Salomidi *et al.* (2012) used expert judgement to assess the goods and services from 56 European seabed biotopes at the scale of EUNIS level 4 (biotopes that comprise seabed type, exposure regime and key and characterising organisms) to human activities. Additionally, Dickie, *et al.* (2014b) modelled changes in a subset of benthic ecosystem services resulting from abrasion from demersal fisheries activity. Hooper *et al.* (2017), identified the relative sensitivity of three ecosystem services (nursery habitat, carbon sequestration and waste remediation) to fishing pressure, to map the level of risk to subtidal sedimentary habitats.

Hooper *et al.* (2017) also concluded that the sensitivity of the services was closely linked to the sensitivity of the benthic habitat as a whole. A much larger body of evidence exists on habitat sensitivity: for the UK, the sensitivity of over 500 different benthic habitats to physical, chemical and biological pressures has been reviewed (Tillin *et al.*, 2010; Tillin, Tyler-Walters *et al.*, 2014). This information has been used in the conservation advice for marine protected areas (Advice on Operations) provided by Statutory Nature Conservation Bodies as well as widely applied in environmental impact assessment, and is publicly available through the Marine Evidence based Sensitivity Assessment (MarESA) website.

Certain types of pressure information can also be (relatively) readily obtained. Although not without limitations, Vessel Monitoring System (VMS) data is gathered on an ongoing basis (and will become more comprehensive with the roll out of an inshore system), which provides information on the spatial distribution and density of fishing activities, the impacts of which on the quality of benthic habitats are well studied. Information on the spatial distribution and impacts of other pressures, such as from infrastructure development (e.g. cables and pipelines, energy installations) is also available.

There may also be application for using sensitivity information as a proxy for asset condition for pelagic habitats. To our knowledge this has not been attempted to date, but information on the impacts of pressures on the condition of pelagic habitats and how this may affect ecosystem service supply may be extrapolated from information on pressures. For example it may be possible to use modelled plumes of pollution from the terrestrial environment entering at point source into the marine environment to inform analyses in a similar way to using pressures as proxies for the condition of seabed habitat assets

Alternative data collection methods and access issues

Models have been proposed as a means to fill certain evidence gaps (eftec, 2015; European Commission & European Environment Agency, 2016; Weatherdon *et al.*, 2017), although the accuracy of process-based models was questioned (eftec, 2015). Modelling was not considered a fully adequate replacement for in situ data and hence of limited application in long-term accounts (Weatherdon *et al.*, 2017). The role for remote sensing was also identified (European Commission & European Environment Agency, 2016). Remote sensing has the potential to provide cost effective information on key pelagic indicators such as primary productivity, sea surface temperature, and occurrence of harmful algal blooms, and also to monitor

the quality and quantity of coastal habitats when exposed at low tide. There is also a potential role for high level indicators (such as those currently under development through the 25 Year Environment Plan) in assessing the status of the marine environment.

Expert judgement may also be used in the absence of full knowledge of the system, for example in compiling a risk register (Mace *et al.*, 2015). A robust risk register requires clear definition of the relationships, thresholds, levels of acceptability, and rates of change and how these inform the perceived level of risk, to reduce subjectivity in the assessments. The input of multiple experts (thought workshops and/or connection to existing working groups) will be important in these definitions. As knowledge about these factors will vary between habitats and contexts, systematic terminology (such as that employed by the IPCC to describe confidence in the evidence and the likelihood of an outcome) could be used. Citizen science can also generate useful data, as well as serving as a tool to engage the public. Initiatives such as the Wetland Birds Survey exemplify the possibilities for long term data sets to be generated through volunteer-based programmes. Lessons can be learned from existing marine and coastal projects such as CoCoast (University of Newcastle), Shore Thing (Marine Biological Association), Seasearch (Marine Conservation Society).

The need to use existing data more effectively was a recurring theme at the international workshop, which prompted discussion on the related need to improve access to these data and the lack of awareness within the academic community of data held by DEFRA and statutory agencies (and vice versa). In the context of marine planning and transboundary issues, it was noted that different agencies and administrations each hold databases with economic information but there is no communication between them, and data collected by the Office for National Statistics has not been incorporated into marine planning datasets.

The Natural Capital Committee (2017) provides a list of datasets, which it notes is not exhaustive and will continue to be updated, but which contains very few examples for the marine context. The list does include the MAGIC interactive mapping website managed by Natural England (although its marine features are not signposted) as well as Environment Agency and the Centre for Environment Fisheries and Aquaculture Science (CEFAS) data on the quality of estuarine, bathing and shellfish waters. The Marine Management Organisation's marine planning evidence database and interactive map (Marine Management Organisation, 2016) brings together multiple spatially-referenced datasets on marine assets and uses, including habitat types and protection levels, fishing effort, energy and other infrastructure, shipping and aggregate extraction and therefore should be highlighted as a key tool in the development of marine natural capital asset registers. This database is likely to have gaps however, particularly as it relies on information being uploaded to it by interested parties. Additional data is likely to be found in repositories such as the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) and the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC)-funded UK Data Archive. As yet, however, no mechanism appears to exist to synthesise this data and incorporate it into the MMO database.

Conclusions

While the lack of data from *in situ* investigation does remain a problem, there are alternatives that will allow certain data gaps to be overcome to some extent. The use of proxies based on known pressures, their impacts, and habitat sensitivity is one pragmatic approach to overcoming the lack of habitat quality information, especially in light of significant, publicly available resources on habitat sensitivity. Remote sensing also has the potential to provide cost effective data, particularly for certain pelagic information and for mapping coastal habitats. Expert judgement is useful and necessary, but there could be benefits to standardising how it is reported (such as the method employed by the IPCC to describe confidence in the evidence and the likelihood of an outcome). Citizen science can also generate data as well as engaging the public. Better communication between those collecting and using data is essential to increase awareness of available data and to facilitate its incorporation into central databases and tools.

8 Valuing marine natural capital

8.1 Methods and methodological issues

The natural environment and its contribution to human health and well-being can be perceived and valued by people in quite distinct or contradictory ways (Pascual *et al.*, 2017). Thus, the methods and approaches used to generate natural capital and ecosystem service values are extensive. Methods can range from monetary to non-monetary and capture specific values or the Total Economic Value including non-use values. There is an extensive literature on the appropriate use, advantages and limitations of different valuation methods including guidance provided in the UK government context (e.g. Defra, 2007; eftcc &

Environmental Futures Ltd, 2006; Fujiwama & Campbell, 2011; HM Treasury, 2018) and useful summary tables (e.g. Christie *et al.*, 2012). Harrison *et al.* (2018) further provide some useful decision trees to aid in the selection of ecosystem service assessments including biophysical or socio-cultural assessments or monetary valuation. Appendix 13 provides a brief description of key valuation methods employed by studies deriving values for UK marine and coastal features (see Section 8.2).

Development of methods to value environmental goods and services predate the ecosystem services and natural capital frameworks. A large literature exists on the methodology of the contingent valuation method (Bateman *et al.*, 2002; Carson & Hanemann 2005; Johnston *et al.*, 2017; Mitchell & Carson, 1989), choice experiments (Kanninen, 2006), the travel cost method (Ward & Beal, 2000), hedonic pricing (Palmquist, 1999), production function (Barbier, 2011, 2012) and other approaches. Within each approach, methodological debates are continuing to take place (Hausman, 2012; Hoyos, 2010; Kling *et al.*, 2012), and numerous issues are being discussed. A review of these general debates would go beyond the scope of this report and the reader is referred to the literature referenced here and above. Instead, the focus will remain on the marine and coastal environment, where valuation approaches face a set of specific methodological issues.

Marine ecosystems are more spatially dynamic than ecosystems on land. Different species and other ecosystem components can be very mobile within the water column, both horizontally and vertically across space. Attempts to synthesise large numbers of value points in preparation for benefits transfer have standardised values down to monetary units per spatial and temporal unit (usually per hectare per year) (Chaikumbung *et al.* 2016, de Groot *et al.* 2012; Mehvar *et al.* 2018). Consequently, valuation tools such as InVEST or ARIES typically use land-use or land cover types as the main input variable to determine ecosystem service flow. While this procedure may be appropriate for many coastal and some offshore ecosystem services, it is questionable for many other offshore marine ecosystem services, such as cultural services of wide-roaming species (such as whales, seabirds) or provisioning services of certain fish species that are highly mobile (for example, cod and herring).

Limited understanding of detailed ecosystem functioning, particularly in offshore environments, may hamper the applicability of valuation methods. Production function approaches to valuing regulating services require a sufficient understanding of the contributions of these services to the production of marketable goods. While such approaches have been successfully applied for near-shore ecosystems (Barbier, 2015a, 2015b), their application to offshore and deep-sea habitats is more challenging. Coastal and particularly marine ecosystems are often very unfamiliar to members of the general public (Jefferson *et al.*, 2014, Rose *et al.*, 2008). There is less engagement with these environments than with examples of terrestrial ecosystems, such as woodlands, parks and rural landscapes (Sandorf *et al.*, 2016). For offshore ecosystems there is the additional issue that people do not visit these sites, which precludes, or at least severely hampers, the application of travel cost approaches.

When using stated preference methods, survey materials need careful development and pretesting before surveys can be implemented, which requires interdisciplinary collaboration between economists and marine scientists (Börger *et al.*, 2018) and guidelines on stated preference techniques are available (e.g. Johnston *et al.*, 2017). When valuing marine ecosystem services, finding a simple yet accurate description of the services and underlying natural science information is extremely challenging. Information has to be presented such that it is both easy to understand and at the same time accurately depicts the changes in ecological indicators that are to be valued. The latter criterion has been described as 'ecological content validity' (Johnston *et al.*, 2012). When ecosystem information is complex, researchers often resort to describing changes in terms of broad levels such as high, medium and low. Values elicited on this basis cannot be mapped directly onto ecological changes and therefore not be included in natural capital accounts.

In addition, methodological research around choice experiments has shown that a low level of familiarity with the good lowers the precision of the valuation estimate (LaRiviere *et al.*, 2014). Values also reflect socio-cultural experiences and so, particularly for unfamiliar environments, may be significantly influenced by the information to which people are exposed. This demonstrates the crucial role of information provision during the valuation survey. The availability of substitutes (alternatives that provide the same or similar change in well-being) also affects values. The effect of the availability of substitutes on value elicitation has been investigated in terrestrial settings (De Valck *et al.*, 2017; Schaafsma & Brouwer, 2013) but remains unexplored for marine goods and services.

8.2 Empirical valuations of UK marine and coastal features

A literature review of existing marine and coastal valuation studies was carried out between April and June 2018. The aim was to identify the current state of marine and coastal ecosystem service valuation within the UK (and the Republic of Ireland) and highlight the evidence gaps. The overall criteria for the review were to include only marine and coastal studies from transitional to offshore zones, and only monetary and non-monetary valuation studies with primary data. Appendix 14 contains more information on the review methodology. It is important to note that the scope of this literature review did not include capturing general market data such as those published for UK sea fisheries. Details of the studies reviewed are provided in Appendix 15.

The search strategy initially yielded 1794 studies. As is typical in systematic review, this was substantially reduced after two rounds of title, abstract and full text screening, to 59 studies (46 peer-reviewed and 13 grey literature, the results from which are described below). Studies were undertaken from 1994 to 2018 with the highest frequency of publications in 2013, and a secondary peak in 2011. The time lag between data collection and publication ranged between 0 years (i.e. published same year as data collection) and 12 years with a mode of 2 years. The number of monetary values generated in any one study ranged from 0 (for non-monetary valuation) to 56 values with 46 studies providing more than one value. A total of 355 monetary values were obtained from the review, with a mean (median) of 6 (3) values per study. A range of methods were used in the studies, with some using multiple methods. Stated preference was the most common type of valuation method employed, while cost-based approaches and non-monetary valuation approaches were rarely used in the UK to value marine and coastal natural capital (Table 13).

Table 13. The methods used in valuation studies from 1994 to 2018 and the number of values derived for UK coastal and marine goods and services. (Note: some studies applied multiple methods)

Valuation method type	Number of		Specific monetary valuation method	Number of	
	Studies	Values		Studies	Values
Stated preference	34	261	Contingent valuation	20	87
Revealed preference	13	40	Choice modelling	14	174
Price-based approach	11	46	Market prices/analysis	10	44
Non-monetary	9	9	Travel cost	11	33
			Avoidance/prevention cost	1	7
			Hedonic pricing	1	2
			Production function approach	1	2

Some studies were country-specific, while others considered the UK-wide scale (n=6). England was the most frequently studied country (n=30), followed by Wales (n=16), The Republic of Ireland and Scotland (each n=9). Both the Republic of Ireland and Wales showed a predominance of national scale studies. There was evidence of a high frequency of local scale studies in England. There were similar number of national scale studies per country, except for Scotland; this is likely due to some studies covering more than one country. Most of the valuation studies were based on coastal habitat (36 studies, 265 values) and inshore (26 studies, 162 values). There were substantially fewer studies on the transition zone (8 studies, 67 values) and offshore (7 studies, 89 values).

The links between the studies and specific policies or management issues were explored, initially by considering who financed the study. Funding was acknowledged in 41 studies with a total of 34 different funders. The most commonly mentioned funders were the Economic and Social Research Council (10 studies) and Defra and NERC (each funding 7 studies). Other funders supporting more than one study included the European Union, Natural England and the Welsh Government. A total of 31 studies mentioned between them 13 specific policies as either motivating the study or in the discussion of results. Of these, the most frequent were EU policies and UK or national policies and to a lesser extent global policies, with additional studies making reference to generic policies. The most frequently mentioned policies were the UK Marine and Coastal Act (n=6), the EU Water Framework Directive (n=5), the EU Habitats Directive (n=4), and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (n=3). Even where explicit reference to specific policies was not made, the studies were usually framed within general policy or management contexts. Designated sites (such as Marine Conservation Zones and Natura 2000 sites) and wider environmental protection were particularly common themes.

The connection between the values determined and how these would be used specifically to support the implementation of the named policy was often weak. Following Laurans *et al.* (2013), the studies were allocated to one of three categories:

- i) Cursory reference to a potential use of ecosystem service valuation: in introduction and/or conclusion, the authors merely mention the fact that economic valuations (their own or others’) could actually be used, without more precision.
- ii) Analysis of the use issue: the core of the paper is use of ecosystem service valuation, i.e. the focus is, once economic valuations are produced, on how their results are used by stakeholders: which stakeholders, in which context, for which purpose, with which results etc.
- iii) Documentation of use cases: case studies that follow the subsequent use of an economic valuation by some stakeholders.

Thirty six studies made only a cursory reference to policy, 13 conducted a more thorough analysis of the use issue, and only one study was designed specifically around a management measure (the potential implementation of regulations on recreational bass fishing). In terms of the ecosystem services valued within these policy and management contexts, cultural services (particularly recreation, and non-use values) were dominant (Table 14). A larger number of individual values have been determined for regulating services compared to provisioning services, although more categories within the latter group have been considered. Valuations have been undertaken in relation to different species and habitats (Table 15). Most studies have considered the environment in general terms, beaches and/or the coastline, and coastal water. Fish, marine mammals, sand dunes, and saltmarsh have featured relatively frequently, although even these in only a handful of studies. This presentation of the data also shows how a single study can be responsible for generating values for a relatively large number of individual species and/or habitats.

Table 14. The ecosystem services valued in UK marine and coastal studies

	Ecosystem service	Number of		
		Studies	Values	
CULTURAL	<i>Recreation:</i>			
	General	12	43	
	Sea angling	9	58	
	Wildlife watching	7	17	
	Scuba diving	3	23	
	Surfing	3	14	
	Other water-based	4	6	
	Clean bathing water	3	13	
	<i>Non-use</i>	15	89	
	Visual amenity	3	4	
	Research & education	1	8	
	Health	3	15	
	PROVISIONING	<i>Food:</i>		
		Capture fisheries	3	5
Aquaculture		1	1	
Seafood		1	1	
Shellfish		1	1	
<i>Other materials:</i>				
Medicinal products		1	3	
Seaweed and biotech		1	1	
<i>Energy:</i>				
Oil and Gas		1	1	
Renewable energy	1	1		
REGULATING	<i>Hazard reduction:</i>			
	Flood risk	3	19	
	Sea defence	1	4	
	Climate regulation	2	10	
	Pest control (Invasives)	2	3	

Table 15. The habitats and species featuring within UK marine and coastal valuation studies

Habitat/species	Number of	
	Studies	Values
General environment	20	64
Beach/Coast	12	47
Coastal water	9	46
Saltmarsh	4	27
Sand dune	4	16
Intertidal mudflat	3	17
Maritime cliffs	2	14
Shingle	2	14
Coastal and flood plain	2	14
Wetland	2	13
Machair	1	1
Rocky seafloor in estuary	1	1
Estuary	1	1
Infralittoral rock habitats	1	10
Deep sea	1	9
Infralittoral sand/gravel habitats	1	6
Infralittoral mud habitats	1	3
Offshore sand bank	1	5
Fish	7	28
Seabirds	4	7
Marine mammals	3	7
Marine wildlife	2	16
Seal	2	4
Algae	2	3
Cetaceans	1	3
Endangered/vulnerable species	1	2
Octopus	1	2
Invertebrates	1	2

8.3 What are the key gaps in valuation evidence to support the application of the natural capital approach in the marine environment?

In addition to the evidence gaps related to ecological data already discussed (see Section 7.2), the lack of valuation data for many marine services and habitats has been highlighted as a challenge that inhibits the

use of ecosystem service values to support policy decisions, for example in the context of marine planning (Börger *et al.* 2014a). The review above demonstrates that a wide range of natural capital valuation studies have been carried out for marine and coastal environments but clear evidence gaps remain. The gaps in valuation for provisioning services are not as significant as is suggested by the review; the scope of that exercise did not encompass assessment of the market values for goods and services such as fish, seafood, aggregates, and other products, which are readily obtainable. The review instead incorporated studies that had gone further than reporting market statistics and, for example, considered provisioning services in other ways, such as the marginal value of sustainable fish certification schemes, and the impact of microplastics or other pollution on safe food supplies.

That there were relatively few non-monetary values may also be explained by the scope and approach of the review, which was primarily focussed towards studies generating monetary, or at least quantified, information. A study with wider parameters and employing alternative techniques (such as content analysis) would better detect studies that capture the broader concept of value and report in qualitative terms.

Cultural ecosystem services were the most frequently valued, but these studies were mainly on recreation, and particularly on angling and wildlife watching. Thus, there are gaps in the valuation of other cultural services, including other forms of recreation (sailing and kayaking for example), as well as marine and maritime heritage, spiritual and inspirational interactions, and health and well-being.

In terms of regulating services, valuation has focused mainly on hazard mitigation and, to a degree, climate regulation in terms of carbon sequestration, although even these services are represented by only a very small number of studies. The absence of any values for services within the CICES categories of mediation of waste, toxins and nuisances; lifecycle, habitat and gene pool protection; and regulation of the chemical condition of the atmosphere and ocean is particularly significant given the importance of these services. With the focus of existing studies on recreation and hazard mitigation, it is not surprising that marine mammals and saltmarsh are amongst the most common species and habitats to feature in the valuation data. There is a further significant evidence gap around subtidal habitats. Deep sea habitats have been valued, but beyond cold water coral, there remains a significant gap in evidence for services derived offshore.

There may be several reasons for data gaps, the most obvious being that those services that are most difficult to measure are likely to be neglected in favour of more straightforward contexts. The priorities of funders will also be reflected in published work, suggesting that to date there has not been a strong driver, or the necessary resource, to obtain a wide range of values from the marine environment. There is also the issue of the motivation for academics to undertake valuation studies. When environmental valuation of itself was fairly novel, there were greater opportunities to publish valuation studies in respected peer-reviewed journals. More recently, research in this field requires additional novelty, such as methodological development, limiting publication opportunities for studies that simply value different services using established methods. This perhaps explains why the publication of empirical valuations appears to have peaked during the period 2011 to 2013.

It is not always necessary to have empirical values directly derived for every context. Benefits transfer (in which values generated in one location or situation are transferred to another) is seen as being essential to the practical use of valuation data in policy-making (Defra, 2007). However, benefits transfer requires robust underlying empirical studies (ideally several for the good being considered) that have a strong theoretical basis, and are similar to the proposed transfer situation in terms of both the biophysical dimensions of the good and the welfare dimensions of the beneficiaries (Johnson *et al.*, 2015). Studies should also be less than 10 years old to be considered reliable estimates. Johnson *et al.* (2015) further point out that the trend for academic publications to focus on aspects such as methodological development, and the wider failure to provide necessary details about the study and the data generated, may reduce the usefulness of the values elicited as empirical estimates that can be used in benefits transfer.

The issues of evidence gaps was discussed at the international workshop, including some discussion on the relative merits of valuation methods, as in order to influence the agenda it is necessary to use the method policy makers feel is appropriate. At the international level, policy makers can be very sceptical about stated preference (for legislative and other reasons), and prefer production function and cost-based approaches. However, at the UK level, stated preference studies are accepted as a means of determining welfare value and worth to society as a whole, rather than trying to use a market exchange rate value. Caveats apply here also, however, particularly the need for data to be robust and peer-reviewed. The need to use existing data more effectively, to improve access to these data, and to raise awareness within and between statutory agencies and academic institutions of what data is held was also highlighted at the workshop.

It was further stressed at the international workshop that the evidence required depends on the decision context: simply raising awareness may be sufficient without needing monetary valuation, and high level information can be enough for developing national policy. However, evidence requirements become more stringent when specific decisions are made or these may be open to legal challenges. Scenarios of different risks, and model outputs have a role as tools to support decision making but again, policy makers and managers need to be clear about what evidence is required for decision making and how much uncertainty is acceptable. The gaps in valuation data to support marine decisions cannot all be attended to in a short space of time.

Conclusions

The most significant gaps in empirical valuation data are for regulating services including mediation of waste, toxins and nuisances; lifecycle, habitat and gene pool protection; and regulation of the chemical condition of the atmosphere and ocean. There is also a lack of values for certain cultural services, particularly marine and maritime heritage, spiritual and inspirational interactions, and health and well-being. Very few values have been derived in the context of offshore areas (and for subtidal habitats in general), and national scale studies outside England are limited. A lack of high quality original studies further constrains the opportunities for defensible benefits transfer.

8.4 Where could new valuations be most usefully applied?

Participants at the international workshop discussed specific priorities for new valuation data, and noted that significant effort had already been directed towards valuing fisheries and recreation. Values of saltmarsh in the context of flood risk management were also considered to be fairly well understood. Two priority areas for new valuation data were determined: health and well-being, and the benefits of management interventions at the marine protected area (MPA) scale. The latter was considered particularly important due to the need for this information for policy appraisal and Impact Assessment, and when communicating with affected industry sectors. Several issues that could be explored in this context were mentioned, including determining the welfare values associated with changing ecosystem services as a result of MPA management measures, economic measures for related industries (jobs, value added, production per sector), and the possibility of introducing a weighting scale (as is currently done in cost benefit analysis with respect to the benefits of technological innovation) to better reflect the difficulties in quantifying the importance of MPAs in protecting critical habitat.

The review demonstrated the absence of monetary values across a wide range of marine species, habitats and contexts. There are two principal factors that need to be taken into account when prioritising how to fill these data gaps for the purposes of supporting decision-making. Firstly, any valuations undertaken for management and policy purposes tend to require that clear linkages can be made from particular assets, processes and functions to changes in welfare. Also, the specific policy and management contexts in which any new valuations would be applied must be identified and understood. The 25 Year Environment Plan is a strong driver for environmental policy, particularly in the context of natural capital, and so provides the most appropriate overarching framework.

The 25 Year Environment Plan gives weight to the workshop outcome that MPAs could be an appropriate focus for new valuation data, given the commitment within the Plan to “*complete our ecologically coherent network of well-managed marine protected areas*” and to “*move to a wholesite approach to protect sites of greatest biodiversity interest*”. Such a focus would be timely, as completion of network refers to the potential designation of the third tranche of Marine Conservation Zones, on which consultation is currently taking place. An issue of particular importance is the designation of Highly Protected Marine Areas (HPMAs), and the consultation document contains an explicit request for “*new evidence that would help establish whether the added ecological benefits of HPMAs, beyond those of other MPAs, would outweigh the added costs to sea users and for enforcement*” (Defra, 2018). A particular focus on offshore HPMAs (and their value over and above MPAs with more limited protection) would also address the evidence gap for offshore environments. A specific decision context should, however, be defined in conjunction with those responsible for designating and managing MPAs.

A further potential context for new valuation data relates to the concepts of whole-site (and potentially whole-systems) management, and more broadly the emphasis placed by the 25 Year Environment Plan on embedding an environmental net gain principle. The 25 Year Environment Plan uses this in the traditional context of infrastructure development, but for the marine environment this concept opens up the opportunity for a change of public mind-set to consider environmental improvements more generally. Values amongst members of the public for improvements to the health and functioning of the marine environment at the systems level could therefore be explored, moving away from protection targeted at

specific species or habitats towards the gain of more naturally functioning whole ecosystems. However, the issue of credibly linking management options, ecological improvements and welfare changes would need to be carefully considered. Also, this context is potentially challenging to frame in the context of a willingness-to-pay scenario, and so robust quantitative results may be difficult to obtain.

The issue of marine litter also features heavily within the 25 Year Environment Plan, and as such new valuation data related to plastics could be used in the context of justifying investment decisions to support stated commitments. The impacts of plastic on charismatic species resonate with the general public, but existence values for marine mammals and seabirds are relatively well documented and potentially amenable to benefits transfer. Perhaps more applicable would be to use this context to determine existence values for less charismatic species, or to assess the implications of plastic pollution for perceptions of food safety and consumption choices for seafood, supporting consideration of the value of health outcomes from safe and clean seas.

Conclusions

While there are significant evidence gaps across valuation data in general, these should be considered in relation to the objectives of current marine policy, particularly that within the 25 Year Environment Plan. Within this context, three priorities for new valuations are suggested: Highly Protected Marine Areas, net gain across whole systems, and the implications of plastic pollution. There remains also the potential to link different elements of these in a single study.

9 Assessing value for money and trade-offs

9.1 Can an improved approach robustly aid decision makers and assess value for money associated with policy changes applied in the context of marine?

The international workshop concluded that an advantage of the natural capital approach is that it provides a holistic process that can employ broad information in making the case for a policy intervention. The approach provides disciplined steps to ensure a decision is well thought through, it can also be used to measure the impact of a policy decision. Natural capital assessment may also highlight environmental gains from industrial activity, such as for co-location benefits offered by the development of offshore renewables.

Broadly, therefore, a modified framework for marine natural capital that appropriately classifies habitats, and further accounts for the dynamic, interconnected and mobile nature of marine ecosystems, should be a robust tool to support decision makers. However, its application in practice may face obstacles, not all of which stem from the approach itself. The UK NEAFO noted the critical role of policy appraisal in incorporating ecosystem knowledge in the policy process, but it also highlighted that there are significant barriers to embedding an ecosystem services framework within appraisal at all scales from practitioner behaviour, institutional culture and practice, to the wider social and political context (Russel *et al.*, 2014). This lack of willingness to apply the ecosystem service framework may similarly restrict practical use of the natural capital approach unless there is a cultural shift. The 25 Year Environment Plan signals the need for such change. There is also often a disconnect between those managing and using ecosystem services and those managing the underlying natural capital that ensures their delivery.

International experts at the workshop also felt that the decision-making process presents a significant challenge, which needs to be solved otherwise progress of the natural capital approach will be slow and partial. At present, the approach is supported by aspirations in, for example, the Natural Environment White Paper (HM Government, 2011), but its use is not mandated in any decision-making process, and some preclude it (the Habitats Directive, for example, is very prescriptive). Participants further expressed the view that this is potentially the biggest impediment to implementation of the natural capital approach. Taking the approach forward in practice requires further assessment of how it relates to existing environmental decision-making, and how the thinking, processes and evidence requirement around this decision-making can be developed. The marine planning process, which currently does not require or take into account the natural capital approach, was one policy area identified for which future iterations could be adapted to support uptake of the approach.

Further testing and refinement of specific applications within the approach is also required. For example, care is required in producing and interpreting summary outputs for asset and risk registers. Using a high level single metric (which, for example, brings together all coastal or all marine habitats) could mask significant changes and opposing trends within the individual components of that broad group. Furthermore, caution should be applied in interpreting asset and risk registers across broad habitat types.

The differences in for example data, understanding of relationships and thresholds, and targets between the habitat types will affect how the risks are defined and confidence in outcomes. It would be inappropriate therefore to “trade-off” between habitats in determining investment and management priorities.

The lack of robust monetary values for marine goods and services (see Section 8.2) is a particular barrier that limits how effectively value for money associated with policy changes could be assessed. Firstly, monetary values have only been determined for a limited range of marine goods and services, and multiple studies that duplicate the same valuation context are rare. This lack of replication makes it difficult to assess the robustness of published values, as do quality issues that have been identified within individual valuation studies. The decision-making process allows for a degree of uncertainty in value estimates, but confidence levels still need to be provided. However, appropriate statistics (for example sample sizes, confidence estimates and payment frequency and/or duration) were often omitted in the empirical studies reviewed, which casts doubt on the reliability and robustness of the data. Valuation methods should be replicable and transparent but we found that certain studies failed to provide sufficient information on, for example, their sampling strategy. Poor definition of the exact nature of the marginal change being valued also limits how well published values can be used in policy. Studies often also provided high level values that do not lend themselves to specific policy applications, and many studies carried out so far estimated total values instead of marginal values of the incremental change based on the per-unit shift in an ecosystem service. Furthermore, the contribution of natural capital was not always separated from other capital inputs. As was noted at the international workshop, without robust underlying valuation data there is little opportunity for benefits transfer.

This lack of robust monetary values limits the ability to achieve, in marine systems, the vision of the Natural Capital Committee (2013), which prioritises monetary valuation and cost benefit analysis linked to natural capital investment plans. The Natural Capital Committee (2013) argues strongly for more funding to allow further monetary valuation to be undertaken, as this “*is almost always outweighed by the costs of failing to do so, which leads to poor decisions and inefficient or even inappropriate investments of public funds.*” However, the scale of need for empirical valuation within the marine environment is particularly significant, and will be difficult to address in the short-term.

It is also important to bear in mind that the characteristics of an ecological asset are usually only partially reflected in the monetary values of the goods and services derived from it. Monetary valuation should therefore not be seen as a stand-alone, or even necessarily the most important, factor in decisions for managing marine natural capital. Information on the quantity, quality and location of the assets from which the goods and benefits are derived should be considered in tandem with valuation data.

Conclusions

The individual frameworks and methods of the natural capital approach, and the way in which their outputs are used and interpreted, require further testing before it can be determined to what extent specific decision making contexts can be supported by the approach. Robust and widespread uptake of the natural capital approach will also require better understanding of the synergies and conflicts between the approach and the requirements of existing legislation. At present, the lack of robust valuation data limits the potential for assessment of the value for money associated with policy changes. Filling the gaps in empirical monetary data will be difficult to achieve rapidly and will require significant investment. Ecological information on assets should be considered alongside monetary values; the natural capital approach should be applied as a coherent whole, not through the isolated application of individual elements of it.

9.2 Can important trade-offs be established, quantified and where possible integrated into policy decision-making tools?

As the workshop participants noted, the natural capital approach is a structured way to consider services, who the beneficiaries are, and where the trade-offs occur. A further advantage is that it looks at multiple benefits and can be used as a tool to engage local people to ensure the full suite of benefits is accounted for. Both costs and benefits are encompassed within the natural capital approach. It can give confidence to decision makers in making choices that disadvantage vocal industry sectors, as the wider cultural benefits of an intervention can be demonstrated.

However, robust assessment of trade-offs requires accurate understanding of who benefits and who bears the costs, but usually not enough effort is applied in defining the full range of stakeholders, representing a significant gap. The question of whether benefits to different parts of society should be weighted, in order to address the imbalance of influence between dominant stakeholders and small, dispersed beneficiaries was also raised. Better understanding of economic thresholds for different sectors and the substitution

possibilities is also required. It was also suggested that the stimulus provided by natural capital for economic activity was not well tracked, for example how increased diving activity within MPAs leads to an increase in dive businesses.

Workshop participants further highlighted a fundamental risk of cost benefit analysis in that the costs tend to be more easily and comprehensively valued than the benefits, about which less is known. More broadly, the idea of focussing on trade-offs (which tend to follow from monetary valuation and cost benefit analysis) was also questioned. It was considered to be a narrow focus, as account should also be taken of the dependencies and complementarities between different aspects of natural capital, both between the assets and between the ecosystem services and the economic activity supported.

As with the assessment of value for money, at a conceptual level the natural capital approach should support the effective evaluation of trade-offs, but the lack of robust quantified evidence is a significant barrier to effectively evaluating cost benefit analysis. In the absence of a full suite of monetary values, greater account needs to be taken of non-monetary factors. Mechanisms exist for this within natural capital frameworks (which have an equal emphasis on biophysical measurement) and in guidance such as the Green Book (HM Treasury, 2018), but traditionally this has not been done well in practice. For example, regulatory Impact Assessment should incorporate economic, environmental and social information. However, half of 249 Impact Assessments fitting sustainable development criteria ignored or undertook inadequate treatment of social and environmental impacts, while only 16% were judged to have treated economic information with low rigour (Tinch *et al.*, 2014). Practitioners themselves agreed that environmental and social impacts that are not monetised are underweighted or overlooked in appraisal (Tinch *et al.*, 2014). A cultural shift is therefore required to ensure that non-monetary values and qualitative information is appropriately incorporated, which could be supported by stronger guidance, as has already been recommended by the National Audit Office (2011).

The 2018 edition of the Green Book (HM Treasury, 2018) demonstrates that guidance is evolving, as this now provides a generic template for appraisal summary tables that provides explicitly for information on “*significant unmonetisable costs/benefits*” and “*significant unquantifiable factors*” to be recorded. However, previous appraisal summary tables have contained narrative information related to impacts that cannot be quantified or monetised, as do Impact Assessments, so of itself this is unlikely to address the problems raised by Tinch *et al.* (2014) and the National Audit Office (2011). While these summary tables are useful in presenting the necessary information, further mechanisms are required to compare and assess trade-offs between monetised and non-monetised information, of which multicriteria analysis is the most powerful (Spackman, 2013).

Templates for building public sector business cases (HM Treasury, 2013) formalise the reporting of weights and scores for non-financial benefits, thus helping to formalise recommendations that structured multicriteria decision analysis be undertaken. The key findings summary table as proposed in the guidance, however, as with the top line summary in impact assessment tables, still contains only monetary information. There is scope, therefore, to improve templates such that within headline summaries monetised, non-monetised and unquantified costs/benefits are given weightings relative to each other, or at least reported in a standardised, qualitative format. Beyond the public sector, the Marine Socio Economics Project co-ordinated by the New Economics Foundation in partnership with environmental NGOs produced an infographic impact assessment for marine conservation zones which provides a visual representation of monetary, quantified and narrative information (New Economics Foundation *et al.*, 2015). Appraisal is often led by economists, and improved interdisciplinary working also has the potential to allow for better integration of non-monetary information (Spackman, 2013).

Going further, there is the opportunity for impact assessment to be reframed such that it becomes a force for supporting environmental sustainability. Previously the appraisal process has been aligned to government strategies for, for example, cutting red tape and reducing regulatory burdens (Russel *et al.*, 2014). Thus, with sufficient political will, the appraisal process could be used as a tool for improving assessment of how policy, across all sectors of government, impacts on natural capital.

Information relevant to trade-offs can be integrated into other decision-making tools beyond appraisal mechanisms, and indeed assessment of trade-offs is a fundamental purpose of models such as the Natural Capital Project’s InVEST. However, using models for ecosystem service assessment requires at least some expertise in modelling and (where the outputs are spatial) GIS, and tends to have high resource requirements. Bagstad *et al.* (2013) calculated that 275 (InVEST) to 800 (AIRES) person-hours were required for a pilot study on the San Pedro river, although it was noted that improved availability of the relevant input data could reduce this to 80 person-hours. Further development of these (and other) tools

would benefit from improved interfacing with specific experts and local contexts, but also that funding and incentives are needed to support the development of modelling tools (Waage *et al.*, 2011).

Conclusions

The natural capital approach is appropriate for the assessment of trade-offs, as it provides a structured approach to the evaluation of a wide range of benefits and the potential impacts upon them. In practice, however, greater attention needs to be paid to identifying the full suite of beneficiaries who will be affected by natural capital trade-offs. The lack of monetary values for the marine environment will limit robust cost benefit analysis, but other methods for assessing trade-offs are well established and are applicable in the natural capital context. Non-monetary information should be better used, as is already called for in guidance. Impacts on the quality and quantity of the asset also need to be given a similar level of attention as impacts on monetary value. Natural capital information can be incorporated into decision support tools, although some of the more advanced tools have significant resource requirements.

10 Summary conclusions and recommendations

- The natural capital approach, as a broad concept, is highly relevant to inform the sustainable management of the marine environment. However, existing approaches are strongly geared to terrestrial environments and should not be adopted for the marine environment without critical evaluation. Trying to apply the existing terrestrial approach in the marine context will result in significant omissions related to critical aspects such as the three dimensional structure, the high levels of interconnectedness of processes and functions, and the fact that services users and uses are very different to the terrestrial environment.
- Ecosystem services has received more attention than other components of the natural capital approach and significant effort, over decades, has gone into the development of frameworks. These are fit for purpose, and the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) should be adopted as an appropriate standardised classification system for marine ecosystem services.
- Although CICES has begun to dominate ecosystem service assessment, alternative classifications that consider categorization from the demand side should be explored further to determine how these could support the wider natural capital approach.
- However, the ecological components currently categorised within some frameworks as intermediate and supporting services would be better addressed as integral (and explicit) components of natural capital assets, rather being categorised as a form of services. Understanding of the role of ecological functions and processes in the supply of services and benefits should continue to be pursued to ensure these ecological components are adequately assessed and managed.
- Further experience of using the natural capital approach in practice is required to evaluate fully specific conceptual and assessment frameworks (for, for example, asset and risk registers as well as accounts), as these have not yet been widely applied in a marine context.
- Habitat classifications are not fit for purpose and require modification. The broad benthic habitat categories currently proposed should be further disaggregated particularly to explicitly include vegetated habitats and biogenic reefs and so provide more useful information for the management of marine and coastal ecosystems. The EUNIS classification should be used to ensure this classification is robust and defensible.
- The definition of coastal habitats for the purposes of natural capital assessment should include the supralittoral (splash zone) and littoral (intertidal), to take account of the similarities in existing national monitoring between coastal and terrestrial and the distinct differences in the needs and opportunities for extent and condition monitoring within fully marine habitats. However, the extent and condition assessment for littoral coastal habitats needs to take account of their full intertidal extent and their function as an integral part of the marine environment.
- The inclusion of pelagic habitats in marine natural capital classifications is essential, but has so far been overlooked in the development of frameworks for UK applications. Different pelagic habitats can be defined according to factors such as salinity, stratification and depth.
- Further research effort should be directed towards determining mechanisms to take account within the natural capital approach of mobile species and the interconnected nature of spatially disparate components of the wider marine environment.
- Natural capital frameworks should also avoid describing the underlying assessment units as 'habitats' as this fails to recognise the breadth of ecological factors that contribute to the condition of assets and the provision of services.
- A lack of ecological data means that understanding of basic elements of the marine (subtidal) environment such as the location, extent and quality of benthic habitats (and thus the foundation of natural capital assessment) is lacking. At the national level, a system of natural capital assessment based on the quality and quantity of marine benthic habitats (i.e. following terrestrial strategies such as the NCAI) will therefore be unworkable in practice.
- There is greater potential for the quantity and quality of marine benthic habitats to be understood and monitored at smaller spatial scales, for which lessons can be learned from the work being undertaken within the North Devon Marine Pioneer. However, even at smaller scales ongoing resourcing will be required to maintain an appropriate frequency of monitoring data.
- Alternative methods that use proxies for quality information, based on known pressures, their impacts, and habitat sensitivity, should be explored.

- The opportunity for using remote sensing should be investigated further, as this is a potentially useful and cost effective tool for monitoring changes in the quality of natural capital from pelagic marine habitats at the national level and for mapping coastal habitats when exposed at low tide.
- The potential for citizen science monitoring of coastal habitat quality, and the resource requirement to manage this on a long-term national basis, should be explored.
- Expert judgement is useful and necessary, but there could be benefits to standardising how it is reported (such as the method employed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change to describe confidence in the evidence and the likelihood of an outcome).
- Multiple agencies and institutions within the public sector and academia are contributing to the development of, and attempting to apply, natural capital approaches for the marine environment. There could be significant benefits and efficiency savings from improving the collation and synthesis of relevant data and in improving access to it. The resource requirements for this should be investigated.
- Although there are a growing number of valuation studies in marine context, the coverage is quite patchy with particular evidence gaps for regulating services, cultural services beyond recreation, and in offshore environments. A lack of high quality original studies further constrains the opportunities for defensible benefits transfer.
- Particular areas deficient in valuation data that should be targeted for future valuation in the context of the 25 Year Environment Plan include Highly Protected Marine Areas, net gain across whole systems, and the implications of plastic pollution.
- The conceptual frameworks and methodologies for the application of the natural capital approach in the assessment of value for money and trade-offs are sound. However, these frameworks and methods have rarely been applied in the marine environment and so further field testing is required.
- The lack of robust monetary values limits the extent to which value for money can be assessed and the application of cost benefit analysis.
- Better account should be taken of non-monetary values within policy appraisal. This is already called for within existing guidance, and is required to ensure that important implications for natural capital are not overlooked.
- Ecological information on assets should be considered alongside monetary values and impacts on the quality and quantity of the asset also need to be given a similar level of attention as impacts on monetary value. The natural capital approach should be applied as a coherent whole, not through the isolated application of individual elements of it.
- Application of the natural capital approach requires a range of methods supported by different types of data and evidence, which have not been fully tested in the marine environment. Therefore, a national programme for developing methodologies for specific components of the natural capital approach (including asset registers, risk registers and accounts) should be established, bringing together policy end-users, managers, economists, ecologists, and statisticians from government (across the national and devolved administrations), statutory nature conservation bodies, NGOs and academia. This would ensure the efficient development of methods that are coherent, applicable in a range of contexts, interdisciplinary, and exemplars of best practice. The current piecemeal, sectorally 'siloed' approach is unlikely to achieve such robust outcomes.
- Priorities for such a programme would be an initial detailed review of the goods and services provided by the marine environment and the most appropriate biophysical units for their assessment and reporting, as well as better mapping of data requirements, challenges, and gaps for the different components of marine and coastal natural capital. Dedicated pilot studies for natural capital asset and risk registers are also required to allow for thorough investigation of how these could be implemented in practice at different spatial and temporal scales. Experimental accounts should also be attempted for more goods and services, again at different scales. This process will identify gaps in ecological and valuation data more clearly and support the development of strategies to fill those gaps.
- The Marine Pioneer programme is already working towards goals of piloting the natural capital approach and development of marine natural capital accounts. It is expected that the results of this project will supplement and support the Marine Pioneer programme and the future implementation of the wider marine objectives of the 25 Year Environment Plan.

11 Glossary

Appraisal is “the process of assessing the costs, benefits and risks of alternative ways to meet government objectives.” (HM Treasury, 2018)

Asset register: “an inventory of the natural assets in an area and their condition.” (Natural Capital Committee, 2017)

Benefits: “changes in human welfare (or well-being) that result from the use or consumption of goods, or from the knowledge that something exists.” (Natural Capital Committee, 2017)

Ecosystem condition: “the physical, chemical and biological condition or quality of an ecosystem at a particular point in time.” (Maes *et al.*, 2018)

Ecosystem Services: “functions and products from nature that can be turned into benefits with varying degrees of human input.” (Natural Capital Committee, 2017)

Final Services: “the contributions that ecosystems make to human well-being. These services are final in that they are the outputs of ecosystems (whether natural, semi-natural or artificial) that most directly affect the well-being of people. A fundamental characteristic is that they retain a connection to the underlying ecosystem functions, processes and structures that generate them.” (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2013)

Natural Capital: “the elements of nature that directly or indirectly produce value to people, including ecosystems, species, freshwater, land, minerals, the air and oceans, as well as natural processes and functions.” (Natural Capital Committee, 2017)

Natural capital accounting: “a tool to measure the changes in the stock and condition of natural capital at a variety of scales and to integrate the value of ecosystem services into accounting and reporting systems” (European Commission & European Environment Agency, 2016).

Pressure: “a human induced process that alters the condition of ecosystems.” (Maes *et al.*, 2018)

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Appendix 1: International workshop report

Workshop context, objectives and structure

The workshop was part of a project commissioned by Defra which had the aim to improve understanding of how the natural capital approach can be applied to decision making for the marine environment, particularly in terms of assessing trade-offs and value for money in monitoring, protection and rebuilding of marine assets. In addition to the workshop, a review of existing literature, data and methods was undertaken. Preliminary results of a review of empirical valuations for UK marine goods and services was presented to help inform discussions on data gaps.

The purpose of the workshop was to bring together external experts from a range of backgrounds including academia, policy, marine management, non-governmental organisations and consultancies to share expertise and lessons learned in order to help progress the practical application of the natural capital approach in marine policy decision making. The workshop had two key objectives, which were to:

- i) Explore the opportunities, challenges and needs for using the natural capital approach to address specific marine policy questions.
- ii) identify and prioritise key evidence gaps, in particular those that could be filled by a national survey with the general public.

After plenary presentations on the purpose of wider project and perspectives on the natural capital approach from the international and marine perspectives, the workshop was structured around four key policy questions on how the natural capital approach can:

- i) guide development of solutions and inform investment decisions for mitigating against risks;
- ii) be better used to inform and justify our vision of sustainable development through its inclusion of social, economic and environmental value;
- iii) incorporate transboundary issues;
- iv) allow decision makers to better determine trade-offs and cumulative impacts in management decisions.

These overarching questions were determined through input from Defra and the wider Project Steering Group, which includes representatives from the Marine Management Organisation, Natural England, the Joint Nature Conservation Committee, the Inshore Fisheries and Conservation Authorities, and the Centre for Fisheries and Aquaculture Science. Initial policy questions collated by Defra were examined to distinguish key themes, from which the final four questions evolved.

Each of the four questions (above) was considered by a separate breakout group, with each group considering the same themes of the applicability of the natural capital approach in that policy context, the challenges and opportunities in applying the approach, and evidence gaps. Participants were allocated to different break out groups in such a way as to ensure that each group was mixed in terms of broad expertise (economics, natural science), organisation type (policy, academia, statutory agencies, others) and location (England, wider UK, international). Each group chose one (or more) specific contexts around which to frame their discussions, which were, respectively for each policy question:

- i) the role of salt marshes and sand dunes in flood risk management;
- ii) marine protected areas (MPAs), sustainable fisheries, health and well-being;
- iii) marine spatial planning;
- iv) trade-offs between use and conservation objectives in MPA management.

A concluding plenary session was used to discuss the priorities for collecting new primary valuation data, to support setting the scope for an empirical valuation study to be carried out as part of the wider project.

The following sections of this report represent the overarching views of the workshop participants on the application of the natural capital approach to the marine environment to aid decision making.

Applicability of, and opportunities for, the natural capital approach

One advantage of the natural capital approach is that it provides a holistic process that can employ a broad range of information in making the case for a policy intervention. It is a structured way to consider services, who the beneficiaries are, and where the trade-offs occur. The approach provides disciplined steps to

ensure a decision is well thought through; it can also be used to measure the impact of a policy decision. A further advantage is that it looks at multiple benefits and can be used as a tool to engage local people to ensure the full suite of benefits is accounted for. It also has potential to improve long-term sustainability. The monetary valuation aspect provides a common basis for comparison and a means of communicating with finance directors on their terms. However, natural capital as a whole is a more integrated approach, with physical data underlying any monetisation and the option to use either or both types of information.

The natural capital approach encourages two way flows between environmental concepts and those of other disciplines, and links to other policy areas including health and education as well as the economy. The approach has the potential to facilitate communication across jurisdictional boundaries in, for example, marine spatial planning, and also the recognition that benefits may flow to areas that are distant from their production. One of the strengths of portraying something in terms of marine natural capital is that it helps to make priorities for action and protection become more evident. The approach supports thinking about shared resources, something that is potentially easier to do for marine than terrestrial environments.

Both costs and benefits are encompassed within the natural capital approach. It can give confidence to decision makers in making choices that disadvantage vocal industry sectors, as the wider cultural benefits of an intervention can be demonstrated. Natural capital assessment may also highlight environmental gains from industrial activity, such as for co-location benefits offered by the development of offshore renewables.

Adopting the natural capital approach provides the opportunity to re-think and re-focus data collection. At present, environmental monitoring is focused on regulation and assessment in relation to Directives. This can align with natural capital, for example Good Environmental Status within the Marine Strategy Framework Directive incorporates traditional fishery measures (e.g. Maximum Sustainable Yield) with others like precautionary biomass. However, the natural capital approach provides the opportunity to think more broadly about why we are interested in monitoring and assessing assets, beyond requirements to do so for a specific policy, and also how to link with broader aims such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

Since the natural capital approach is still relatively novel, there is also the opportunity for UK research to innovate and lead the way internationally, for example in developing a natural capital approach to marine spatial planning, and in considering international dependencies on natural capital such as in fisheries and food security.

While workshop participants broadly endorsed the natural capital approach, concerns were expressed that in practice it may focus on ecosystem services and monetary values and not consider ecological aspects. Such applications may not be consistent with achieving a healthy natural environment. To achieve the latter it is important that due consideration is given to indicators of the quantity and quality of ecosystems. Such indicators are inherent in a natural capital approach but may be easily overlooked. In particular, only limited attention has been given to the linkages between assets and services, and yet this is fundamental to understanding how impacts on the ecology will affect goods and benefits.

Role of monetary valuation and cost benefit analysis

It was clear from the workshop discussions that monetary valuation has definite uses and a strong traction with policy makers at the national and international levels. However, participants had concerns (in some cases strong reservations) about the apparent enthusiasm for monetary values; it was mooted that a mind-set focused on these may in itself be a barrier to effective use of the wider natural capital approach. Before monetisation and even quantification, the foundation of the approach is raising awareness, ensuring everyone is engaged in understanding the system, and setting principles and responsibilities for decision making. Other metrics (such as the number of people dependent on a resource) may have greater meaning, and the relative weighting of the attributes involved may be sufficient in making decisions. However, the terms by which natural capital is communicated varies with the audience, and monetary values remain important for interactions with the Treasury. It was also noted that prioritisation is not a question for economists, but is a political or societal choice. Economists can provide answers on how to allocate resources most efficiently in meeting those priorities.

There was also some discussion on the relative merits of valuation methods, as in order to influence the agenda it is necessary to use the method policy makers feel is appropriate. At the international level, policy makers can be very sceptical about stated preference (for legislative and other reasons), and prefer production function and cost-based approaches. However, at the UK level, stated preference studies are accepted as a means of determining welfare value and worth to society as a whole, when market prices are not available. Caveats apply here also, however, particularly the need for data to be robust and peer-

reviewed. The rationale for applying cost benefit analysis to MPAs was challenged, as it was argued that they represent the protection of critical capital and so marginal values are not appropriate. Assessment of the cost effectiveness of achieving the necessary protection was considered more relevant, although, in the UK context it was argued that marginal values are necessary for the decision making process around specific management measures. A fundamental risk of cost benefit analysis was highlighted in that the costs tend to be more easily and comprehensively valued than the benefits, about which less is known. More broadly, the idea of focussing on trade-offs (which tend to follow from monetary valuation and cost benefit analysis) was also questioned. It was considered to be a narrow focus, as account should also be taken dependencies and complementarities between different aspects of natural capital.

Challenges and barriers

There is a difference in language between ecologists and economists (and also between social scientists of different disciplines), so terminology can be a barrier. Wider communication, public understanding, and incentivising people to act differently are also challenges. Perception of value is a cultural artefact, and if public support is required in making an ecological improvement, this may need investment in education and awareness to change the public mind frame; marine plastics was given as a recent example of how the general public has been inspired to find solutions to a marine issue. Linking natural capital objectives to other policy goals (such as employment, health and well-being, cultural heritage and income inequality) may improve outcomes.

Scale and boundaries also present challenges. It is difficult to delineate a meaningful discrete area in the marine environment, particularly in relation to mobile species and the water column. There may also be a mismatch between where ecosystem services are supplied and the location of demand for them; the marine planning process encountered challenges in determining where demand arose. The spatial scale will change depending on the beneficiaries, and this might not fit with administrative boundaries (or data availability). The different governance jurisdictions in the marine environment also add complexity. An ambition for the natural capital approach is that it is scalable, but this presents further challenges. Considerable additional information is needed in changing the scale of an assessment, and data and approaches for the national scale may not be applicable at local levels. For example, data used to define MPAs at the network level may not be appropriate for management decisions at the site scale. National level macro-economic assessments also do not take account of spatial shifts in benefits, but these will be very important regionally.

The availability of evidence was identified as a key issue, but is not the whole problem. The decision making process itself presents a significant challenge, which needs to be solved otherwise progress will be slow and partial. At present, the natural capital approach is supported by aspirations in, for example, the Natural Environment White Paper, but its use is not mandated in any decision-making process, and some preclude it (the Habitats Directive, for example is very prescriptive). This is potentially the biggest impediment to implementation of the natural capital approach. Taking the approach forward in practice requires further assessment of how it relates to existing environmental decision-making, and how the thinking, processes and evidence requirement around this decision-making can be developed. The marine planning process, which currently does not require or take into account the natural capital approach, was one policy area identified for which future iterations could be adapted to support uptake of the approach.

Governance more generally, and the need for strong policy drivers and champions to support marine natural capital thinking, were identified as further issues in practical implementation, as was the need for adequately funded pilots to demonstrate the utility of the approach. The dominance of terrestrial issues, the larger number of people involved in terrestrial natural capital and the current lack of marine emphasis in the 25 Year Environment Plan (which, for example, proposes that each of the 14 terrestrial Area Integrated Plans are migrated to natural capital plans but presents no similar aspiration for marine plans), were also identified as barriers to effective implementation of the natural capital approach in marine decision making.

Evidence gaps

Across the groups, it was emphasised that there is a need to improve natural science evidence on the extent and condition of assets, ecosystem tipping points, and how these link to the provision of ecosystem services, before meaningful valuation of the associated benefits can be undertaken. Further gaps in our fundamental understanding were identified, particularly: i) how to define assets and account for their interdependencies; ii) how to track changes in values over time and what that implies for the choices we have to make; and iii) how to aggregate cumulative impacts and trade-offs. Transboundary issues crossing

terrestrial and marine are also quite neglected, and there has been a further lack of investigations of historical data to examine trends in benefits and environmental status.

Moving more into wider social science aspects, evidence quantifying levels of use of services from marine natural capital is variable depending on the activity and location, and understanding of the social context is also lacking. Health and well-being is an important benefit of natural capital, and while marine studies have been undertaken they have focussed primarily on recreation and collective benefits in particular are often missed. Robust assessment of trade-offs requires accurate understanding of who benefits and who bears the costs, but usually not enough effort is applied in defining the full range of stakeholders, representing a significant gap. The question of whether benefits to different parts of society should be weighted, in order to address the imbalance of influence between dominant stakeholders and small, dispersed beneficiaries was also raised. Better understanding of economic thresholds for different sectors (i.e. at what point their business is no longer viable) and the substitution possibilities (in terms of changes to their activities) is also required. It was also suggested that the stimulus provided by natural capital for economic activity was not well tracked, for example how increased diving activity within MPAs leads to an increase in dive businesses.

The need to use existing data more effectively was another recurring theme, which prompted discussion on the related need to improve access to these data and the lack of awareness within the academic community of data held by DEFRA and statutory agencies (and vice versa). In the context of marine planning and transboundary issues, it was noted that different agencies and administrations each hold databases with economic information but there is no communication between them, and data collected by the Office for National Statistics has not been incorporated into marine planning datasets. Also, there are groups working on natural capital more generally and exploring issues such as data gaps and ensuring consistency. Interaction with, and marine representation in, these groups should be improved.

It was stressed that the evidence required depends on the decision context: simply raising awareness may be sufficient without needing monetary valuation, and high level information can be enough for developing national policy. However, evidence requirements become more stringent when specific decisions are made or these may be open to legal challenges. Scenarios of different risks, and model outputs have a role as tools to support decision making but again, policy makers and managers need to be clear about what evidence is required for decision making and how much uncertainty is acceptable. The gaps in valuation data to support marine decisions cannot all be attended to in a short space of time. Benefits transfer was not considered a viable option without robust underlying valuation data.

Priorities for new valuation data

In trying to identify specific priorities for new valuation data, participants noted that significant effort had already been directed towards valuing fisheries and recreation. Values of saltmarsh in the context of flood risk management were also considered to be fairly well understood. Two priority areas for new valuation data were determined: health and well-being, and the benefits of management interventions at the marine protected area (MPA) scale. The latter was considered particularly important due to the need for this information for policy appraisal and Impact Assessment, and when communicating with affected industry sectors. Several issues that could be explored in this context were mentioned, including determining the welfare values associated with changing ecosystem services as a result of MPA management measures, economic measures for related industries (jobs, value added, production per sector), and the possibility of introducing a weighting scale (as is currently done in cost benefit analysis with respect to the benefits of technological innovation) to better reflect the difficulties in quantifying the importance of MPAs in protecting critical habitat.

Participants

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Appendix 2: Applications of marine ecosystem service classifications

Table A2.1. Examples, and timeline, of frameworks and classifications for the assessment of marine ecosystem services

Year	Study	Purpose	Context	Location	Informed by/ adapted from	Service categories	Number of main service types	Includes abiotic
2006, 2007	Beaumont <i>et al.</i>	Monetary valuation	Marine biodiversity	UK	MEA (2003)	Production, regulation, cultural, supporting	13	No
2010	Hussain <i>et al.</i>	Monetary valuation	Marine protected areas	UK	MEA (2003) Beaumont <i>et al.</i> (2007)	Provisioning, supporting, regulating, cultural	11	No
2010	Everard <i>et al.</i>	Highlighting importance	Sand dunes	UK	MEA (2003)	Provisioning, regulating, cultural, supporting	27	Yes
2010	Saunders <i>et al.</i>	Monetary valuation	Marine estate and UK seas	UK	TEEB (2010) (heavily adapted)	Food, raw materials, energy, space & waterways, physical well-being, psychology/ social well-being, knowledge	27	Yes
2011	Jones <i>et al.</i>	Assessment of national assets	UK coastal habitats	UK	UK NEA (2011)	i) Intermediate, final, goods ii) Provisioning, regulating, cultural, supporting	14	Yes
2011	Austen <i>et al.</i>	Assessment of national assets	i) Plankton ii) Bioturbators iii) Fish	UK	UK NEA (2011)	i) Intermediate, final, goods ii) Provisioning, regulating, cultural, supporting	7	No
2011	Atkins <i>et al.</i>	Development of decision support framework	Management: i) aggregate extraction ii) marine biodiversity	UK	MEA (2003) Beaumont <i>et al.</i> (2007)	Production, regulation, cultural, option use values, over-arching support services	17	Yes
2013	Liquete <i>et al.</i>	Development of indicators	Marine and coastal ecosystem services	Global (EU-based study)	MEA (2003) Beaumont <i>et al.</i> (2007) TEEB (2010) CICES (2012)	Provisioning, regulating & maintenance, cultural	14	Yes
2013	Böhnke-Henrichs <i>et al.</i>	Embedding ecosystem services approach	Marine spatial planning and management	EU	TEEB (2010)	Provisioning, regulating, cultural, habitat	21	Yes
2014	Hooper <i>et al.</i>	Impact assessment	Tidal energy in estuaries	UK	MEA (2003)	Provisioning, regulating, cultural, carrier	11	Yes
2014	Turner <i>et al.</i>	Conceptual framework, developing tools/ approaches	Adaptive management	UK	UK NEA (2011)	i) Intermediate, final, goods/benefits ii) Provisioning, regulating, cultural, supporting	14	No
2014	Dickie <i>et al.</i> (2014b)	Monetary valuation	Benthic ecosystem services	UK	UK NEA (2011) CICES (2012) Turner <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Production, regulation, cultural, supporting	10	No
2015	Hattam <i>et al.</i>	Development of indicators	Dogger Bank	UK	TEEB (2010)	Provisioning, regulating, cultural, habitat	18	No
2015	Turner <i>et al.</i>	Conceptual framework	Coastal management	UK	UK NEA (2011)	i) Intermediate, final, goods; ii) Provisioning, regulating, cultural, supporting	29	No
2018	Norton <i>et al.</i>	Monetary valuation	Coasts, marine, estuaries (national level)	Ireland	CICES (2012)	Provisioning, cultural, regulating & maintenance	17	Yes

Appendix 3: Standardised classification systems for ecosystem services

Common International Classification for Ecosystem Services (CICES)

Table A3.1 The CICES classification of marine-relevant biotic services and abiotic services

A. BIOTIC

1. Provisioning

1.1 Biomass

1.1.2 Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy

- 1.1.2.1 Plants cultivated by *in situ* aquaculture grown for nutritional purposes
- 1.1.2.2 Fibres and other materials from *in situ* aquaculture for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)
- 1.1.2.3 Plants cultivated by *in situ* aquaculture grown as an energy source

1.1.4 Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy

- 1.1.4.1 Animals reared by *in situ* aquaculture for nutritional purposes
- 1.1.4.2 Fibres and other materials from animals grown by *in situ* aquaculture for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)
- 1.1.4.3 Animals reared by *in situ* aquaculture as an energy source

1.1.5 Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy

- 1.1.5.1 Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used for nutrition
- 1.1.5.2 Fibres and other materials from wild plants for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)
- 1.1.5.3 Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used as a source of energy

1.1.6 Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy

- 1.1.6.1 Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) used for nutritional purposes
- 1.1.6.2 Fibres and other materials from wild animals for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)
- 1.1.6.3 Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) used as a source of energy

1.2 Genetic material from all biota (including seed, spore or gamete production)

1.2.1 Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi

- 1.2.1.1 Seeds, spores and other plant materials collected for maintaining or establishing a population
- 1.2.1.2 Higher and lower plants (whole organisms) used to breed new strains or varieties
- 1.2.1.3 Individual genes extracted from higher and lower plants for the design and construction of new biological entities

1.2.2 Genetic material from animals

- 1.2.2.1 Animal material collected for the purposes of maintaining or establishing a population
- 1.2.2.2 Wild animals (whole organisms) used to breed new strains or varieties
- 1.2.2.3 Individual genes extracted from organisms for the design and construction of new biological entities

2. Regulation & Maintenance

2.1 Transformation of biochemical or physical inputs to ecosystems

2.1.1 Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes

- 2.1.1.1 Bio-remediation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals
- 2.1.1.2 Filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals

2.1.2 Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin

- 2.1.2.1 Smell reduction
- 2.1.2.3 Visual screening

2.2 Regulation of physical, chemical, biological conditions

2.2.1 Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events

- 2.2.1.1 Control of erosion rates
- 2.2.1.2 Buffering and attenuation of mass movement
- 2.2.1.3 Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation (Including flood control, and coastal protection)

2.2.2 Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection

- 2.2.2.1 Pollination (or 'gamete' dispersal in a marine context)
- 2.2.2.2 Seed dispersal
- 2.2.2.3 Maintaining nursery populations and habitats (Including gene pool protection)

2.2.3 Pest and disease control

- 2.2.3.1 Pest control (including invasive species)
- 2.2.3.2 Disease control

2.2.4 Regulation of soil quality

2.2.4.2 Decomposition and fixing processes and their effect on soil quality

2.2.5 Water conditions

2.2.5.2 Regulation of the chemical condition of salt waters by living processes

2.2.6 Atmospheric composition and conditions

2.2.6.1 Regulation of chemical composition of atmosphere and oceans

2.2.6.2 Regulation of temperature and humidity, including ventilation and transpiration

3. Cultural

3.1 Direct, *in situ* and outdoor interactions with living systems that depend on presence in the environmental setting

3.1.1 Physical and experiential interactions with natural environment

3.1.1.1 Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through active or immersive interactions

3.1.1.2 Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through passive or observational interactions

3.1.2 Intellectual and representative interactions with natural environment

3.1.2.1 Characteristics of living systems that enable scientific investigation or the creation of traditional ecological knowledge

3.1.2.2 Characteristics of living systems that enable education and training

3.1.2.3 Characteristics of living systems that are resonant in terms of culture or heritage

3.1.2.4 Characteristics of living systems that enable aesthetic experiences

3.2 Indirect, remote, often indoor interactions with living systems that do not require presence in the environmental setting

3.2.1 Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment

3.2.1.1 Elements of living systems that have symbolic meaning

3.2.1.2 Elements of living systems that have sacred or religious meaning

3.2.1.3 Elements of living systems used for entertainment or representation

3.2.2 Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value

3.2.2.1 Characteristics or features of living systems that have an existence value

3.2.2.2 Characteristics or features of living systems that have an option or bequest value

B. ABIOTIC

4. Provisioning

4.2 Water

4.2.1 Surface water used for nutrition, materials or energy

4.2.1.1 Surface water for drinking

4.2.1.2 Surface water used as a material (non-drinking purposes)

4.2.1.3 Freshwater surface water used as an energy source

4.2.1.4 Coastal and marine water used as energy source

4.2.2 Ground water for used for nutrition, materials or energy

4.2.2.1 Ground (and subsurface) water for drinking

4.2.2.2 Ground water (and subsurface) used as a material (non-drinking purposes)

4.2.2.3 Ground water (and subsurface) used as an energy source

4.3 Non-aqueous natural abiotic ecosystem outputs

4.3.1 Mineral substances used for nutritional purposes

4.3.1.1 Mineral substances used for nutritional purposes

4.3.1.2 Mineral substances used for material purposes

4.3.1.3 Mineral substances used for as an energy source

4.3.2 Non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy

4.3.2.1 Non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutritional purposes

4.3.2.2 Non-mineral substances used for materials

4.3.2.3 Wind energy

4.3.2.4 Solar energy

4.3.2.5 Geothermal

5. Regulation & Maintenance

5.1 Transformation of biochemical or physical inputs to ecosystems

5.1.1 Mediation of waste, toxics and other nuisances by non-living processes

5.1.1.1 Dilution by freshwater and marine ecosystems

5.1.1.2 Dilution by atmosphere

5.1.1.3 Mediation by other chemical or physical means (e.g. via Filtration, sequestration, storage or accumulation)

5.1.2 Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin

5.1.2.1 Mediation of nuisances by abiotic structures or processes

5.2 Regulation of physical, chemical, biological conditions

5.2.1 Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events

5.2.1.1 Mass flows

5.2.1.2 Liquid flows

5.2.1.3 Gaseous flows

5.2.2 Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions

5.2.2.1 Maintenance and regulation by inorganic natural chemical and physical processes

6. Cultural

6.1 Direct, *in situ* and outdoor interactions with natural physical systems that depend on presence in the environmental setting

6.1.1 Physical and experiential interactions with natural abiotic components of the environment

6.1.1.1 Natural, abiotic characteristics of nature that enable active or passive physical and experiential interactions

6.1.2 Natural, abiotic characteristics of nature that enable intellectual interactions

6.1.2.1 Natural, abiotic characteristics of nature that enable intellectual interactions

6.2 Indirect, remote, often indoor interactions with physical systems that do not require presence in the environmental setting

6.2.1 Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with the abiotic components of the natural environment

6.2.1.1 Natural, abiotic characteristics of nature that enable spiritual, symbolic and other interactions

6.2.2 Other abiotic characteristics that have a non-use value

6.2.2.1 Natural, abiotic characteristics or features of nature that have either an existence, option or bequest value

National Ecosystem Services Classification System (NESCS)

Table A3.2 The full list of examples provided to illustrate the NESCS structure

Appendix 4: Overarching principals for the natural capital approach

In the UK, the Natural Capital Committee has published broad principles on the application of the natural capital approach, in the form of a ‘How to’ workbook (Natural Capital Committee, 2017). This describes a five step, iterative process (Figure A4.1) that is intended to provide a structured way to (i) measure the natural capital in a particular area and the benefits it can provide; (ii) identify threats and opportunities to natural capital; (iii) weigh up the available options and opportunities to make improvements; and (iv) develop practical plans.

Figure A4.1. The steps in the sequence for natural capital assessment (Natural Capital Committee, 2017)

Overarching principles for natural capital assessment have been developed internationally by other agencies. In particular, the Natural Capital Coalition is a global collaboration of organisations and initiatives from policy, conservation bodies and non-governmental organisations, science and academia, business, civil society (currently with almost 250 members), which seeks to harmonise natural capital approaches. Their Natural Capital Protocol (Natural Capital Coalition, 2016) has four key principles applicable across the whole approach (Table A4.1), and there are four main stages to its application, subdivided into nine steps (Table A4.2).

The Natural Capital Protocol shares common themes with the Natural Capital Committee approach, the core of both being to understand clearly the purpose of any assessment before commencing; to measure and ultimately value change; and to apply the results in order to improve outcomes for natural capital. In both cases it is also expected that implementation of the process will be iterative, with the outcomes of each stage feeding back into, and potentially requiring revision of, earlier steps. The Protocol is designed primarily for businesses, and aims to help them identify dependencies and risks, and to identify their impacts on the environment and how they can mitigate them.

Table A4.1. The four key principles of the Natural Capital Protocol (Natural Capital Coalition, 2016)

Relevance	Ensure that you consider the most relevant issues throughout your natural capital assessment including the impacts and/or dependencies that are most material for the business and its stakeholders.
Rigour	Use technically robust (from a scientific and economic perspective) information, data and methods that are also fit for purpose.
Replicability	Ensure that all assumptions, data, caveats, and methods used are transparent, traceable, fully documented, and repeatable. This allows for eventual verification or audit, as required
Consistency	Ensure the data and methods used for an assessment are compatible with each other and with the scope of analysis, which depends on the overall objective and expected application

Table A4.2. The stages and steps of the Natural Capital Protocol (Natural Capital Coalition, 2016)

Stage	Step	Questions this will answer
FRAME Why?	01 Get started	Why should you conduct a natural capital assessment?
SCOPE What?	02 Define the objective	What is the objective of your assessment?
	03 Scope the assessment	What is an appropriate scope to meet your objective?
	04 Determine the impact and/or dependencies	Which impacts and/or dependencies are material?
MEASURE AND VALUE How?	05 Measure impact drivers and/or dependencies	How can your impact drivers and/or dependencies be measured?
	06 Measure changes in the state of natural capital	What are the changes in the state and trends of natural capital related to your business impacts and/or dependencies?
	07 Value impacts and/or dependencies	What is the value of your natural capital impacts and/or dependencies?
APPLY What next?	08 Interpret and test the results	How can you interpret, validate, and verify your assessment process and results?
	09 Take action	How will you apply your results and integrate natural capital into existing processes?

Appendix 5: The UK NEAFO natural capital asset check

Table A5.1 The steps in the UK NEAFO natural capital asset check (Dickie, Cryle, *et al.*, 2014)

The Asset	<p>Defining natural capital and boundaries of the ‘check’</p> <p>A. Define natural capital asset being checked. B. What is the spatial scale for which the asset check is being conducted? C. Define the timescale for the asset check. D. What are the main ecosystem services the asset provides? (including level of uncertainty)</p>
Integrity of the Asset	<p>Extent and condition, linked to levels of ecosystem services</p> <p>E. What is the extent of the natural capital asset? (including trends and level of uncertainty) F. What is the condition of the natural capital asset? (including trends and level of uncertainty) G. Drivers of changes in extent and condition (type and importance of policy, biophysical, socio-economic and other drivers) H. What are the asset’s main ecosystem functions? I. Integrity test: Is the ability of the asset to support ecosystem services being maintained?</p>
Asset performance	<p>Can the asset give target performance, now and in the future?</p> <p>J. Is there a measure of the current output of ecosystem services from the asset? K. What goods and benefits do these ecosystem services support? L. What evidence exists on the monetary value of some/all of these services? M. What is the target performance from the asset? (including level of uncertainty)</p> <p>Defining performance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What policy targets are there for the asset? - What is the trend in the main services the asset provides? - What types of goods are supported by the asset? - Who benefits from the goods? - What well-being results from the goods? <p>N. Are any future changes in target performance expected? O. Can future target performance be defined?</p>
Asset criticalities	<p>What role the asset performs in supporting human welfare?</p> <p>The ‘check’ is of the performance of this role. Levels of uncertainty and evidence gaps should be included</p> <p>P. What is the trajectory of change for the asset? Q. Are there any standards or agreed limits of change to the asset? R. Are there likely to be any threshold effects? S. What is the reversibility of changes to the asset? T. What is the cumulative effect of impacts on the asset? U. What risks are associated with current trends in the asset integrity? V. What substitutes exist for the main ecosystem services from the asset? W. Tradeoffs? X. Synergies? Y. Sustainability test: is the asset currently able to give the target performance? If yes, can it be sustained? If no, why not? Z. Red flags?</p>
Warning that future performance is at risk?	
Conclusions	<p>Table to summarise key evidence, under the summary headings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - State of the asset (extent, condition) - Drivers/threats to asset - Services - Drivers influencing future services - Future services from the asset - Natural asset integrity test - Current and future target asset performance - Synergies - Thresholds - Cumulative impacts - Reversibility - Uncertainties (missing information) - Sustainability test.

Appendix 6: Asset-benefit relationships for broad-scale coastal margin and marine habitats

Understanding the relationship between the status of each asset and the benefits it provides is a fundamental component of a risk register. The assumptions made by Mace *et al.* (2015) regarding these relationships for coastal margin and marine habitats are outlined below.

Table A6.1 Asset-benefit relationships and their justification for coastal margin habitats (Mace *et al.*, 2015)

Relationship strength: No/negligible relationship Minor/moderate relationship Major relationship

Relationship form: Linear (L) Non-linear (NL) Positive (+) Negative (-)

Broad habitat types: Coastal Margins (CM) Enclosed farmland (EF) Freshwaters (F) Marine (M)
 Mountains, Moorlands and Heaths (MMH) Semi-natural grasslands (SNG) Urban(U) Woodlands (W)

Characteristic	Relationship justification
FOOD	
Quantity	The relationship is considered to be +NL (none/negligible) Older established saltmarsh and sand dune grasslands are used for grazing livestock (predominantly sheep) (UK NEA, 2011). The current provision of food from this A/U is considered to be low when compared to EF and M. Although there is potential to reduce the quantity of these subcomponents through land use change, the ability to increase them is limited as they are the ultimate stage of succession for these habitats.
Quality	The relationship is considered to be +NL (none/negligible) The saltmarsh and sand dunes which support livestock typically have a soil profile to support grass. Anything that affects the store of soil will affect the amount of benefit that can be produced. However, this is considered to be minimal as the grassland successional stage is well established and least vulnerable to erosion.
Spatial configuration	No relationship – the spatial configuration of the A/U cannot be influenced by society-restricted to interface between land and sea.
FIBRE	
Quantity	The relationship is considered to be +NL (none/negligible) Coastal margins are of low importance in providing fibre (wool). Although we could influence the quantity and quality characteristics (spatial configuration cannot be changed), there would be negligible change in total benefit produced from the A/U over the next 25 yrs.
Quality	The relationship is considered to be +NL (none/negligible) Coastal margins are of low importance in providing fibre (wool). Although we could influence the quantity and quality characteristics (spatial configuration cannot be changed), there would be negligible change in total benefit produced from the A/U over the next 25 yrs.
Spatial configuration	No relationship – the spatial configuration of the A/U cannot be influenced by society-restricted to interface between land and sea.
ENERGY	
Quantity	No relationship – the A/U cannot be influenced by society to provide an energy benefit. i.e. we harness what is already in place (tidal).
Quality	
Spatial configuration	
CLEAN WATER	
Quantity	No relationship – Although sand dunes and shingle with a reasonable depth form shallow aquifers of clean water (used for small-scale local abstractions such as golf) (UK NEA), the quantity of the A/U cannot be influenced by society to increase the value of the benefit produced. i.e. we utilise what is there.
Quality	The relationship is considered to be +NL (none/negligible). It is assumed that as the quality of the habitat increases, its ability to purify also increases. It is considered that a limited number of aquifers benefit from this process, with the majority of aquifers in England being inland, and therefore the overall value of an increase in quality is minimal. As stated in the UK NEA, Dungeness is the only shingle site which provides a local source of drinking water. The benefit in purification is to the marine A/U.
Spatial configuration	No relationship – the spatial configuration of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
CLEAN AIR	
Quantity	No relationship – the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to provide a clean air benefit.
Quality	
Spatial configuration	

Application of the natural capital approach in the marine environment

Characteristic	Relationship justification
RECREATION	
Quantity	The relationship is considered to be +L (none/negligible). The ability to increase the quantity is limited e.g. some subcomponents only such as saltmarsh. Minor changes in the quantity of these habitats are not considered to be significantly valued for recreation.
Quality	The relationship is considered to be +NL (major). The quality of coastal margins could significantly affect the active enjoyment of them e.g. litter, poor bathing water standards. The initial unit of coastal margins will be valued, and as the quality improves, this will increase. However, after a certain level of improvements, any additions are no longer as valued i.e. the marginal increase is less. Recreation = f [coasts (limits on bacteria levels (E.coli and streptococci, limits on levels of cyanobacteria, phytoplankton, macro-algae); material capital (management practices e.g. litter collection, maintenance of coastal footpaths, signage/waymarks, maps, information boards, waste bins, toilets, modification for golf courses)]; pressures (industrial, wastewater and sewage related discharges).
Spatial configuration	No relationship – the spatial configuration of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced - restricted to interface between land and sea.
HAZARD PROTECTION	
Quantity	The relationship is considered to be +L (major). The coastal margin protects from erosion, wave and tide damage and coastal flooding. Vegetated saltmarsh can attenuate wave energy; an 80m strip can reduce the height of landward seawalls from 12m to 3m (UK NEA Technical Report). Sand dunes and shingle banks dissipate energy and if wide enough, can replace the need for artificial defences. With schemes such as managed realignment, substantial areas of saltmarsh can be created. The area of these same habitats can be reduced by change in land use e.g. drainage for enclosed farmland, changes for recreational benefits e.g. golf courses, and also reduced through hard engineering flood defence schemes. Therefore the contribution of coastal margins to flood defence is considered to be high, with potentially large increases in area possible which are significantly valued.
Quality	The relationship is considered to be +NL (major). It is assumed that a poor quality habitat would not have the structural integrity to provide effective flood protection e.g. width not sufficient, pioneer communities with limited ability to bind sediments (dunes and saltmarsh). As discussed in the UK NEA for sand dunes, vegetation cover and root mass bind substrate, promote sand deposition and help to build wider and higher dunes. A poor quality habitat would also be vulnerable to erosion and therefore there is a link between quality and quantity. As the quality increases, the amount spent on manufactured capital flood defence will reduce. Although it is considered that the accounting unit can substantially reduce the cost of manufacture capital flood defence, there will always be situations where additional protection is required. Protection from hazards = f [species; coasts (feature is wide and elevated, low creek density (saltmarsh)); ecological communities (colonisers such as <i>Salicornia</i> , sand dune stabilisers e.g. marram grass, tall and dense vegetation); freshwater (sediment); land (coastal morphology, aspect); ocean (tidal submergence, tidal current velocity, salinity, temperature); material capital (hard engineering structures)]
Spatial configuration	No relationship – the spatial configuration of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
EQUITABLE CLIMATE	
Quantity	The relationship is considered to be +L (major). – MAJOR Climate regulation provided by habitats where there is rapid soil development or sediment accumulation (sand dune and saltmarsh). UK saltmarsh have high rates of carbon sequestration storing 0.64–2.19 t c/ha/yr The ability to increase the quantity of the accounting unit is limited; only the proportion of subcomponent habitat that could change. Therefore the contribution of coastal margins to equitable climate (carbon storage in saltmarsh) is considered to be high, with small increases in area that are possible but which are significantly valued.
Quality	The relationship is considered to be +NL (- MAJOR) Sand dune and saltmarsh act as carbon sinks, storing carbon as sediment accumulates and soils develop, with early successional systems having a greater potential to store (UK NEA Technical Report). However, these habitats also release methane and NOx. The net effect on climate regulation is considered to be beneficial, however the overall contribution is limited by the quantity of these habitats. Potential release from degradation however is considered to be significant. Carbon storage = f [coasts (early successional stages); atmosphere (wetter conditions); ecological communities (vegetation fixes CO ₂)] pressures (development erosion).
Spatial configuration	No relationship – the spatial configuration of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.

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Characteristic	Relationship justification
AESTHETIC	
Quantity	The relationship is considered to be +L (none/negligible). The ability to increase the quantity is limited e.g. some subcomponents only such as saltmarsh. Changes in the quantity of these habitats are not considered to be significantly valued for aesthetics.
Quality	The relationship is considered to be +NL (major). The quality of coastal margins could significantly affect the enjoyment of them. It is considered that people will value a heterogeneous landscape with good quality habitats and limited hard engineering structures. The initial unit of coastal margins will be valued, and as the quality improves, this will increase. However, after a certain level of improvements, any additions are no longer as valued i.e. the marginal increase is less. Aesthetics = f [coasts (abundance of habitats); oceans (view, sense of being at seaside); ecological communities (wildlife associated with habitats); material capital (hard engineering, cultural memories, archaeology and heritage)]
Spatial configuration	The relationship is considered to be +NL (major). The aesthetic appeal can be interrupted if the landscape is fragmented by urban area, tall structures or other land uses i.e. anything that interrupts the view. A continuous and connected landscape is considered to be highly valued for aesthetics.
WILDLIFE	
Quantity	The relationship is considered to be +L (major). The A/U quantity can be increased and decreased in relation to some of the subcomponent habitats e.g. saltmarsh, sand dunes etc. With schemes such as managed realignment, substantial areas of saltmarsh can be created. The area of these same habitats can be reduced by change in land use e.g. drainage for enclosed farmland, changes for recreational benefits e.g. golf courses. Therefore the contribution of coastal margins to wildlife is considered to be high, with increases in area possible which are significantly valued.
Quality	The relationship is considered to be +NL (major). 'Pristine' coastal margins are those which have a high level of heterogeneity, supporting a mosaic of habitats, including early successional habitats. These in turn support a range of highly specialised species which can tolerate the harsh conditions (salinity, inundation etc). In habitats such as shingle banks, lichen live on the pebbles and therefore any level of disturbance can affect this. It is considered that people will highly value habitats nearing 'pristine' and although the contribution of additional species may only be of marginal value after this, the value will still increase. Wildlife = f [species (specialised, native, range of successional species); ecological communities (mosaic of habitats, range of successional stages, maintenance of stable systems); freshwater (sediment); land (coastal morphology incl. aspect and gradient); atmosphere (wind); oceans (tidal submergence, water velocity, turbulence, salinity levels, nutrient levels); coasts (stable systems, sediment, soil pH); material capital (management regimes e.g. light grazing, scrub clearance, lack of disturbance on shingle,) pressures (air pollution -acidification from sulphur and nitrogen deposition))]
Spatial configuration	No relationship – the spatial configuration of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced

Table A6.2 Asset-benefit relationships and their justification for marine habitats (Mace *et al.*, 2015)

Characteristic	Relationship justification
FOOD	
Quantity	No relationship – the quantity of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
Quality	The relationship is considered to be +NL (major). The quality of the A/U can affect the yield of fish, shellfish etc. In a poor quality environment e.g. acidified ocean, high salinity levels, low phytoplankton, the numbers of fish etc that could be harvested would be very low, and considerable effort and inputs would be required to harvest this low number. As the water quality improves, the system will become more productive and therefore number of fish/shellfish etc that it can support will increase. Similarly the value of the output from the A/U will increase. However, there will be a critical point where after any further increases in quality will produce marginal benefits. There is an important link with coasts as saltmarsh provide a nursery ground for fish species. Fish/shellfish yield = f [species (fish, shellfish), coasts (nursery ground for fish species), atmosphere (wind), oceans (salinity, currents, tides, waves, temperature, pH), ecological communities (population regulation, food web dynamics), land (morphology), material capital (harvesting effort, harvesting preferences - policy driven, equipment)pressures(pollution)].
Spatial configuration	No relationship – the spatial configuration of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
FIBRE	
Quantity	No relationship – none of the characteristics of the A/U can be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
Quality	
Spatial configuration	
ENERGY	
Quantity	No relationship – none of the characteristics of the A/U can be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
Quality	
Spatial configuration	
CLEAN WATER	
Quantity	No relationship – none of the characteristics of the A/U can be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
Quality	
Spatial configuration	
CLEAN AIR	
Quantity	No relationship – none of the characteristics of the A/U can be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
Quality	
Spatial configuration	
RECREATION	
Quantity	No relationship – the quantity of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
Quality	The relationship is considered to be +NL (minor/moderate). The value of recreation can be improved with artificial reefs (e.g. surfing) and decreased through no-catch zones (angling).
Spatial configuration	No relationship – the spatial configuration of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
HAZARD PROTECTION	
Quantity	No relationship – none of the characteristics of the A/U can be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
Quality	
Spatial configuration	

Characteristic	Relationship justification
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EQUITABLE CLIMATE	
Quantity	No relationship – the quantity of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
Quality	The relationship is considered to be +NL (none/negligible). Marine organisms regulate the climate by acting as a sink for carbon dioxide and facilitating burial of carbon in seabed sediment. This is done by photosynthesis and also storage of carbon in shells (calcium carbonate). The abundance and diversity of marine flora and fauna will be primarily determined by the quality of the water. This will increase up to a critical point, after which any increase in quality, and therefore associated species abundance, will be less valued. However, our ability to change or influence the benefit by human management is considered to be limited. Equable climate = f [species (crustaceans, molluscs); ecological communities (phytoplankton, CaCO ₃ absorption); ocean (salinity, temperature, pH); pressures (pollution)]
Spatial configuration	No relationship – the spatial configuration of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
AESTHETIC	
Quantity	No relationship – the quantity of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
Quality	The relationship is considered to be +NL (none/negligible). The quality of the marine environment, and wider sea views, can be affected by offshore windfarms (perceived as both positive and negative impacts on landscape). The change in value of the benefit is considered to be none/negligible.
Spatial configuration	No relationship – the spatial configuration of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
WILDLIFE	
Quantity	No relationship – the quantity of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.
Quality	The relationship is considered to be +NL (major) The abundance and diversity of marine wildlife will be primarily determined by the quality of the water. This will increase up to a critical point, after which any increase in quality, and therefore associated species diversity and/or abundance, will be less valued. Wildlife = f [species ; ecological communities (population regulation, food web dynamics); land (topography, elevation); atmosphere (wind), oceans (salinity, tides, currents, waves, temperature, pH); pressures (pollution (e.g. oil spills, sewage effluent), invasive species (e.g. ballast water), fish by-catch, damage to benthic communities through trawl fishing)].
Spatial configuration	No relationship – the spatial configuration of the A/U cannot be changed or influenced by human management to increase the value of the benefit produced.

Appendix 7: Causal frameworks and natural capital

To integrate the natural capital in to management there is a requirement to identify the causality between changes in the social (human) system and changes in ecological systems. From roots in the early Stress-Response Environmental Statistical System (S-RESS) initiated by Friend (1979) the European Environment Agency (EAA) defined an operational causal framework, the DPSIR framework (Drivers-Pressures-State-Impact-Response) (EEA, 1999, 2012) as a system-based approach expressing key relationships between society and the environment. See (Cooper, 2013; Gari *et al.*, 2015; Hambling *et al.*, 2011) for a full review of DPSIR origins. The DSPIR framework has become widely applied by the EAA and the European Commission to inform ecosystem-based management in the marine and coastal environment.

More recently, in response to application in environmental management contexts, the DPSIR framework has evolved. There is now recognition that the "Impact" in DPSIR is most commonly expressed in relation to the effects on environmental quality and that this was often merged with "State". "Welfare" replaced "Impact" to become DPSWR to provide definition between impacts on the ecological system (state change) and impacts on the social system (Atkins *et al.*, 2011). DPSWR has emerged as the causal socio-ecological accounting framework (Figure A7.1) that can provide a conceptual starting point to organise information concerned with human–environment interactions and enable analysis of the social–ecological systems at scales relevant to ecosystem change (Cooper, 2013; Mee *et al.*, 2015). DPSWR was adopted by the UKNEA FO and applied to the marine and coastal environment context (Turner *et al.*, 2014).

Figure A7.1. The DPSWR framework (Cooper, 2013; Mee *et al.*, 2015)

DPSWR has been more recently modified within the context of integrated management of the marine environment. Following on from Atkins *et al.*, 2011; Smyth *et al.*, 2015; Wolanski & Elliott, 2015, Elliot *et al.* (2017) have developed and tested DAPSI(W)R(M) (pronounced dap-see-worm) to facilitate the inclusion of ecosystem services and societal benefits into the DPSIR framework. Within DAPSI(W)R(M) "Drivers" of basic human needs require "Activities" which lead to "Pressures". The "Pressures" are the mechanisms of "State change" on the natural system which then leads to "Impacts" (on human Welfare). Those then require "Responses" (as Measures) (see Elliot *et al.*, 2017) (Figure A7.2). DAPSI(W)R(M) provides a framework not only for the ecological structure and function of a system but also physico-chemical processes, ecosystem services and societal benefits (Elliot *et al.*, 2017).

Figure A7.2 The DAPSI(W)R(M) problem structuring framework (Elliott *et al.*, 2017)

Set within a natural capital approach, the DAPSI(W)R(M) causal framework (in all its permutations) is predominantly a tool for informing policy and progress towards sustainable development. DAPSI(W)R(M) has been used as a tool for risk assessment to inform risk-based management strategies, for example, (Burdon *et al.*, 2018). It has previously been highlighted that DPSIR causal frameworks are less prescriptive than natural capital accounting frameworks, providing a flexible comprehensive status of the social-ecological system (Cooper, 2013). Causal frameworks can also bridge the divide between natural and social sciences and enable the identification of pathways towards sustainable management of marine resources (Burdon *et al.*, 2018).

Critiques of the causal framework point to weakness in the application of the causal framework to highlight 'social diversity and local responses making it difficult to examine aggregated impacts' (Carr *et al.*, 2007; Ness *et al.*, 2010). Additionally, that the static nature of a causal framework does not take into account temporal lags between the different categories, e.g. when will a management response result in a welfare response and that there is limited scope for demonstrating the degrees of relational uncertainty between different categories (Cooper, 2013).

The Government's 25-year Environment Plan states a commitment to setting natural capital within a conceptual framework for improving the environment that integrates elements of DPSIR and incorporates a monitoring and evaluation framework. The conceptual framework builds on previous models (Natural Capital Committee, 2014; NERC, 2017) where the assets and benefits from ecological systems are set within and influenced by a complex open system of drivers, pressures and policy/management interventions (Figure A7.3). Through the integration of drivers and pressures, it is considered that the natural capital approach is more systematic in the inclusion of current and future challenges and therefore more suitable for informing policy decisions that involve trade-offs.

*Other capital inputs include manufactured capital (eg. buildings and machines), human capital (eg. labour and education) and social capital (eg. rules and procedures)

Figure A7.3. A conceptual framework for improving the environment (in 25-year Environment Plan – Annex 1)

Appendix 8: Examples of marine-specific natural capital decision support tools

TIDE – Tidal River Development

The Interreg-funded TIDE – Tidal River Development project focused on North Sea estuaries using four case studies including the Humber. This proposed, and provided guidance for, a methodology for ecosystem service assessment (Jacobs *et al.*, 2013), which covered elements such as statistical tests and confidence assessment for expert judgement (something often relied upon in the absence of data for marine and coastal natural capital), and generated a matrix of the ecosystem services provided by different zones within estuaries. This was extended to explore potential trade-offs and synergies between services, leading to the development of a trade-off risks matrix (Figure A8.1). This illustrates the how optimisation for a specific service may reduce (or enhance) the potential for the continued supply of other services.

	"Biodiversity"	Aesthetic information	Climate regulation: Carbon sequestration and burial	Erosion and sedimentation regulation by biological mediation	Erosion and sedimentation regulation by water bodies	Food: Animals	Information for cognitive development	Inspiration for culture, art and design	Opportunities for recreation & tourism
"Biodiversity"	0.00								
Aesthetic information	0.54	0.00							
Climate regulation: Carbon sequestration and burial	1.21	0.87	0.00						
Erosion and sedimentation regulation by biological mediation	1.43	0.95	0.22	0.00					
Erosion and sedimentation regulation by water bodies	0.54	0.73	1.24	1.38	0.00				
Food: Animals	1.83	1.32	0.87	0.83	1.78	0.00			
Information for cognitive development	0.60	0.39	1.18	1.26	0.64	1.56	0.00		
Inspiration for culture, art and design	0.48	0.32	1.10	1.17	0.48	1.51	0.17	0.00	
Opportunities for recreation & tourism	0.77	0.52	0.98	0.98	0.56	1.21	0.38	0.33	0.00

Figure A8.1 An extract from the TIDE trade-off risk matrix (Jacobs *et al.*, 2013)

In addition, TIDE considered conflicts between different uses, management measures and services. A conflict matrix tool including a *pro forma* spreadsheet and guidance (Hemingway & Cutts, 2013) was developed to support identification of:

(b) Conflict score

Figure A8.2. Example outputs from the TIDE conflict matrix (Hemingway & Cutts, 2013)

Open-source software models

Integrated Valuation of Environmental Services and Tradeoffs (InVEST) is a collection of modular open-source software models that can be used to map and value ecosystem goods and services. It can produce outputs in biophysical or monetary metrics, and combine with geographic information system (GIS) tools (including the open-source QGIS) for the visualisation of outputs (Figure A8.3). Models relevant to natural capital in marine and coastal areas include:

- Habitat quality (based on maps of land use and land cover).
- Habitat risk assessment (including cumulative risks).
- Food from fisheries (currently parameterised for North American decapod species).
- Food from aquaculture (marine finfish).
- Coastal blue carbon (based on land cover by coastal vegetation).
- Wave energy production (mapping and valuing wave energy provisioning).
- Offshore wind energy production (energy resource availability, generation potential and value).
- Scenic quality provision (identification of the visual footprint of new offshore development).
- Recreation value (the contribution of different ecosystem attributes to visitation rates).

InVEST also includes an Overlap Analysis Model designed to support spatial planning, which identifies areas important for human use based on the density of activities and their relative importance; a qualitative Coastal Vulnerability Model, which combines generic information on the risk of coastal hazards (erosion, storm inundation) with population density data; and scenario generators for exploring the implications of land cover changes.

Detailed guidance on the structure and use of the models is provided, including specifications of the required input data and sample data sets (Sharp *et al.*, 2018). The models are amenable to user modification, for example that for fisheries can be customised for different species and/or incorporate more advanced fisheries models. Caveats are also documented. Again using the fisheries model example, the developers recognise the complex nature of fisheries population dynamics and stress the purpose of the model is to explore the relative consequences of different decisions, not to provide precise predictions of harvest quantities. The most comprehensive case study to apply InVEST in coastal areas was the design of an integrated coastal zone management plan for Belize that considered the ecosystem services and benefits from corals, mangroves and seagrasses and the effect of human activities on them (Arkema *et al.*, 2015). The coastal plan was approved by the Government of Belize in 2016.

Figure A8.3. Outputs from the InVEST model showing biophysical and economic values and their spatial distribution for three ecosystem services in the current situation and for three future scenarios for integrated coastal zone management in Belize (Arkema *et al.*, 2015)

Other platforms using a similar approach of open-access and user modifiable modelling tools include Artificial Intelligence for Ecosystem Services (AIRES) (Villa *et al.*, 2014), which makes greater use of probabilistic Bayesian approaches (where InVEST is deterministic). AIRES also considers carbon sequestration, coastal flood regulation, fisheries, aesthetic value, proximity to open space and recreation. There are ongoing projects to apply AIRES in marine and coastal contexts for trade-offs in ecosystem-

based fisheries management in the North Sea; the development of green and blue infrastructure in the Intercontinental Biosphere Reserve of Andalusia-Morocco; and valuation of coral reef ecosystem services in Hawaii. ATLANTIS is a more advanced, three dimensional deterministic model that considers biophysical, social and economic components of marine ecosystems in the evaluation of management strategies (Audzijonyte *et al.*, 2017a; 2017b). It has a particular focus on fisheries and the dynamics of fishing fleets, but can also be used to explore pollution, coastal development and broad-scale environmental change (such as climate change and ocean acidification), and has been used in multiple locations contexts to date (particularly temperate marine ecosystems), including for fisheries in the English Channel (Girardin *et al.*, 2018).

Using models for ecosystem service assessment requires at least some expertise in modelling and (where the outputs are spatial) GIS, and tends to have high resource requirements. Bagstad *et al.* (2013) calculated that 275 (InVEST) to 800 (AIRES) person-hours were required for a pilot study on the San Pedro river, although it was noted that improved availability of the relevant input data could reduce this to 80 person-hours. A comparison of InVEST and AIRES outputs from the same pilot study highlighted the differences in metrics and the treatment of ecosystem services, but also showed that the two models supported the same conclusion as to which development option minimised impacts (Waage *et al.*, 2011). Waage *et al.* (2011) also concluded that both tools would benefit from improved interfacing with specific experts and local contexts, noting that this was indeed planned, but also that funding and incentives are needed to support the development of modelling tools.

Appendix 9: Ecosystem service provision by marine habitats

Table A9.1 Correspondence between broadscale habitats and habitats protected under EU and national legislation with their provision of ecosystem services (ES)

Scores from Potts et al. (2014). Greyscale = **parent broadscale habitat**, or **no difference** in ES provision between feature and parent broadscale habitat. Purple = **difference** in ES provision of protected habitat from parent broadscale habitat. Highlighted habitats (orange) show those that, for ES with values, differ on average >1 score class (positive or negative).

The key is provided on p89

Feature Type	EUNIS code Note: Eunis codes were identified using the JNCC EUNIS translation matrix. Some habitats do not have a direct relationship to the EUNIS code and this column should only be used as a guide.	Feature (Bold type represents broadscale habitats, normal type represents habitat FOCI)	Natural capital functions and processes						Regulating Services				
			Primary production	Larval and gamete supply	Nutrient cycling	Water cycling	Formation of species habitat	Formation of physical barriers	Formation of seascape	Biological control	Natural hazard regulation	Waste breakdown and detoxification	Carbon sequestration
E,EU,W	A1.1	High energy intertidal rock	3	3	1	0	3	3	1		3	0	1
S	A3.126, A3.213, A1.15, A3.22, A4.11, A4.25, A5.52	Tide-swept algal communities	0	1	2	0	1	1	1		1	3	2
E	A1.127, A1.223, A4.231	Peat and clay exposures		2		0	1	2					
E	A1.126, A1.243, A1.441, B3.114, B3.115	Littoral chalk communities	2	2		0	1	3				0	
E,EU,W	A1.2	Moderate energy intertidal rock	2	2	1	0	3	3			3	0	1
E,W	A1.2142, A3.2112	Intertidal under boulder communities	1	0		0	1	2			2	0	
E	A1.127, A1.223, A4.231	Peat and clay exposures		1		0	1	2					
E	A1.126, A1.243, A1.441, B3.114, B3.115	Littoral chalk communities	1	1		0	1	3				0	
E,EU,W	A1.3	Low energy intertidal rock	1	1	1	0	3	3			3	0	1
EU, E, NI	A1.32	Estuarine rocky habitats	1	1		0	1	0			1	0	
S	A1.325	Sea loch egg wrack beds	2	1	2	0	1	1			1	3	2
EU	A1.44	Submerged or partially submerged sea caves				0	0	3			3	0	1
E	A1.126, A1.243, A1.441, B3.114, B3.115	Littoral chalk communities	0	0		0	1	3				0	

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Feature Type	EUNIS code Note: Eunis codes were identified using the JNCC EUNIS translation matrix. Some habitats do not have a direct relationship to the EUNIS code and this column should only be used as a guide.	Feature (Bold type represents broadscale habitats, normal type represents habitat FOCI)	Natural capital functions and processes						Regulating Services				
			Primary production	Larval and gamete supply	Nutrient cycling	Water cycling	Formation of species habitat	Formation of physical barriers	Formation of seascape	Biological control	Natural hazard regulation	Waste breakdown and detoxification	Carbon sequestration
E,W	A2.1	Intertidal coarse sediment	1	2	1	0	2	2	2		2	1	
E,W	A2.2	Intertidal sand and muddy sand	1	2	2	0	3	2	3		2	1	1
E,S,W, NI	A2.2, A2.7, A5.6	Blue Mussel beds	0	0	0	0	1	1	1		1	1	1
NI	A2.23 or A5.2	Stable sands with associated fauna	1	1	0	0	1	0	1		0	0	1
E,W	A2.3	Intertidal mud	1	3	2	0	2		2		1	1	2
E,EU	A2.4	Intertidal mixed sediments	1	2	2	0	3	2	2		2	2	1
E,W	A5.43, A2.41, A2.42, A5.44	Sheltered muddy gravels		1	1	0	1	2				0	0
E	A2.5	Coastal saltmarshes and saline reedbeds	3	3	3	1	3	2	2		2	3	3
EU,E,W	A2.6	Intertidal sediments dominated by aquatic angiosperms	3		3	1	3	2	1		2	3	3
All	A5.53, A5.545, A2.61	Seagrass beds	0		0	1	0	1	1		0	1	1
EU,E,W	A2.7	Intertidal biogenic reefs	3	2	2	0	3	2	1		2	2	2
E,S,W, NI	A2.2, A2.7, A5.6	Blue Mussel beds	2	0	0	0	1	1	1		1	0	0
E,W	A2.71, A5.612	Honeycomb worm <i>Sabellaria alveolata</i> reef		1	2	0	0	2			0	2	2
EU,E,W	A3.1	High energy infralittoral rock	2	2		0	3	3			2	0	
S	A3.126, A3.213	Tide-swept algal communities (<i>Laminaria hyperborea</i> , <i>Halidryx siliquosa</i>)	1	0		0	1	1			0	3	
EU,E,W	A3.2	Moderate energy infralittoral rock	2	2		0	3	3			2	0	
E,W	A1.2142, A3.2112	Intertidal under boulder communities	1	0		0	1	2			1	0	
S	A3.126, A3.213	Tide-swept algal communities (<i>Laminaria hyperborea</i> , <i>Halidryx siliquosa</i>)	1	0		0	1	1			0	3	
E	A4.23, A3.21	Subtidal chalk		1		0	0	2				0	

Feature Type	EUNIS code Note: Eunis codes were identified using the JNCC EUNIS translation matrix. Some habitats do not have a direct relationship to the EUNIS code and this column should only be used as a guide.	Feature (Bold type represents broadscale habitats, normal type represents habitat FOCI)	Natural capital functions and processes						Regulating Services			
			Primary production	Larval and gamete supply	Nutrient cycling	Water cycling	Formation of species habitat	Formation of physical barriers	Formation of seascape	Biological control	Natural hazard regulation	Waste breakdown and detoxification
EU,E,W	A3.3	Low energy infralittoral rock	2	2		0	3	3			2	0
	A3.32	Kelp in variable salinity on low energy infralittoral rock										
EU,E,W	A4.1	High energy circalittoral rock	1	2		0	2	1			1	0
E,W, NI	A4.12, A4.13, A4.21	Fragile sponge&anthozoan communities on subtidal rocky habitats		0		0	0	1			1	1
W	A4.131, A4.2122	Subtidal rock with Ross 'coral' <i>Pentapora foliacea</i>		0		0	0	0				1
S	A4.133, A4.211	Northern sea fan and sponge communities				0	0	1			1	1
S	A3.126, A3.213, A1.15, A3.22, A4.11, A4.25, A5.52	Tide-swept algal communities	2	0		0	0	1			1	3
EU,E,W	A4.2	Moderate energy circalittoral rock	1	2		0	2	1			1	0
W	A4.131, A4.2122	Subtidal rock with Ross 'coral' <i>Pentapora foliacea</i>		0		0	0	0				1
S	A4.133, A4.211	Northern sea fan and sponge communities				0	0	1			1	1
E	A4.22, A5.61	Ross worm <i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i> reefs		0		0	1	0			1	1
E	A4.23, A3.21	Subtidal chalk		1		0	1	0				0
E	A1.127, A1.223, A4.231	Peat and clay exposures		1		0	0	0				
E,W, NI	A4.12, A4.13, A4.21	Fragile sponge&anthozoan communities on subtidal rocky habitats		0		0	0	1			1	1
S	A3.126, A3.213, A1.15, A3.22, A4.11, A4.25, A5.52	Tide-swept algal communities	2	0		0	0	1			1	3
EU,E,W	A4.3	Low energy circalittoral rock	1	2		0	2	1			1	0
E,W	A5.1	Subtidal coarse sediment	1	2	2	0	2	1			1	1
E	A5.12, A5.13	Subtidal sands and gravels	0	0	0	0	0	0				1
S	A5.133	Shallow tide-swept coarse sands with burrowing bivalves (<i>Morella</i> sp.)			2	0	2	1				1

Feature Type	EUNIS code Note: Eunis codes were identified using the JNCC EUNIS translation matrix. Some habitats do not have a direct relationship to the EUNIS code and this column should only be used as a guide.	Feature (Bold type represents broadscale habitats, normal type represents habitat FOCI)	Natural capital functions and processes						Regulating Services				
			Primary production	Larval and gamete supply	Nutrient cycling	Water cycling	Formation of species habitat	Formation of physical barriers	Formation of seascape	Biological control	Natural hazard regulation	Waste breakdown and detoxification	Carbon sequestration
E,W	A5.2	Subtidal sand	1	2	2	0	2	1			1	1	
NI	A2.23 or A5.2	Stable sands with associated fauna	1	1	0	0	0	1			1	0	
E,W	A5.3	Subtidal mud	1	2	2	0	2	1			1	2	
E,S, NI	A5.361	Sea-pen and burrowing megafauna communities	0	0	0	0	0	1			0	1	
S	A5.371	Inshore deep mud with burrowing heart urchins	0	0	0	0	0	1			0	1	
EU,E,W	A5.4	Subtidal mixed sediments	1	2	2	0	2	1			1	2	
E,W	A5.43, A2.41, A2.42, A5.44	Sheltered muddy gravels		1	1	0	0	1				0	
E,S	A5.434	Flame/ File shell beds	0	0	1	0	0	0			0	1	
E,S,W, NI	A5.435	Native Oyster <i>Ostrea edulis</i> beds		0	0	0	1	0			1	1	
EU,E,W	A5.5	Subtidal macrophyte-dominated sediment	3	2	3	0	3	1			2	3	2
All	A5.51, A5.511, A5.512, A5.513, A5.514	Maerl beds	1	0	1	0	0	0					
S	A5.5112	Maerl or coarse shell gravel with burrowing sea cucumbers	1	0	1	0	0	0					
S	A5.52	Kelp and seaweed communities on sublittoral sediment	0	0	0	0	1	1			0	0	1
All	A5.53, A5.545, A2.61	Seagrass beds	0	1	0	0	0	0			0	1	0
S	A3.126, A3.213, A1.15, A3.22, A4.11, A4.25, A5.52	Tide-swept algal communities	0	0	0	0	1	1			0	0	1

Feature Type	EUNIS code Note: Eunis codes were identified using the JNCC EUNIS translation matrix. Some habitats do not have a direct relationship to the EUNIS code and this column should only be used as a guide.	Feature (Bold type represents broadscale habitats, normal type represents habitat FOCI)	Natural capital functions and processes						Regulating Services				
			Primary production	Larval and gamete supply	Nutrient cycling	Water cycling	Formation of species habitat	Formation of physical barriers	Formation of seascape	Biological control	Natural hazard regulation	Waste breakdown and detoxification	Carbon sequestration
EU,E,W	A5.6	Subtidal biogenic reefs	3	2	2	0	3	1			2	2	2
E,S,W, NI	A2.2, A2.7, A5.6	Blue mussel beds	2	0	0	0	1	0			1	0	0
E,S,W, NI	A5.62	Horse mussel (<i>Modiolus modiolus</i>) beds	1	0	1	0	0	1			0	1	0
E, NI	A5.63	Cold-water coral reefs		0	1	0	1	0					0
E,W	A2.71, A5.612	Honeycomb worm <i>Sabellaria alveolata</i> reef		1	2	0	0	1			0	2	2
E	A4.22, A5.61	Ross worm <i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i> reefs		0	1	0	0	0			0	1	1
EU	A5.71	Submarine structures made by leaking gases			3	0	3	0			0	0	0
W, NI	A6.5	Mud habitats in deep water	1	2	2	0	2	0			1	1	
E,S	A6.61	Coral Gardens	1	2	2	0	2	1	1	1	0	2	1
	A6.62	Deep-sea sponge aggregations											
S	A6.75	Carbonate mound communities	0	2	2	0	2	0		0	0	2	0
S	A7.4, A7.7	Salinity fronts	3	2	2	0	3	2		1	0	2	1
EU	X02	Saline lagoons		1	2	0	2		2				
S	Various	Low or variable salinity habitats	2	2	3	0	3	1	3	1	3	2	1
E,W	Various	Tide-swept channels		2		0	3	1			0		
W	Various	Sediment habitats with long lived bivalves			3	0	0	0		1		2	
E	N/A	Areas of high planktonic primary productivity	3	1	3	0	0	0		3	1		2

Key

Scale of ES supplied relative to other features

3	Significant contribution
2	Moderate contribution
1	Low contribution
0	No or negligible ES provision
	Not assessed

Relative differentiation in ES provision compared to parent broadscale habitat

	Highly differentiated
	Moderately differentiated
	Slightly differentiated
	Mean difference in ES score class >1 (+ve or -ve) compared to parent broadscale habitat

Feature type

S	Scottish MPA search feature
E	English MCZ feature
W	Welsh HP MCZ feature
NI	Northern Ireland MCZ feature
EU	EU Habitats Directive Annex 1 feature or sub-feature

Table A9.2 Correspondence between broadscale habitats and habitats protected under EU and national legislation with their provision of goods derived from ecosystem services (ES)

Scores from Potts et al. (2014). Greyscale = **parent broadscale habitat**, or **no difference** in ES provision between feature and parent broadscale habitat. Purple = **difference** in ES provision of protected habitat from parent broadscale habitat. Highlighted habitats (orange) show those that, for ES with values, differ on average >1 score class (positive or negative).

The key is provided on p95

Feature Type	EUNIS code Note: Eunis codes were identified using the JNCC EUNIS translation matrix. Some habitats do not have a direct relationship to the EUNIS code and this column should only be used as a guide.	Feature (Bold type represents broadscale habitats, normal type represents habitat FOCI)	Goods/Benefits from												
			Provisioning ES					Regulating ES				Cultural ES			
			Food (wild, farmed)	Fish feed (wild, farmed, bait)	Fertiliser and biofuels	Ornaments and aquaria	Medicines and blue biotechnology	Healthy climate	Prevention of coastal erosion	Sea defence	Waste burial / removal / neutralisation	Tourism and nature watching	Spiritual and cultural well-being	Aesthetic benefits	Education
E,EU,W	A1.1	High energy intertidal rock	2	0	0			1	3	3	0	1	1	1	1
S	A3.126, A3.213, A1.15, A3.22, A4.11, A4.25, A5.52	Tide-swept algal communities	1	0	3			2	1	1	1	2	2	0	1
E	A1.127, A1.223, A4.231	Peat and clay exposures		0								0	0		0
E	A1.126, A1.243, A1.441, B3.114, B3.115	Littoral chalk communities		0	0						0	0	0		0
E,EU,W	A1.2	Moderate energy intertidal rock	2	0	0			1	2	2	0	1	1	1	1
E,W	A1.2142, A3.2112	Intertidal under boulder communities	1	0	0				1	1	0	0	0	1	0
E	A1.127, A1.223, A4.231	Peat and clay exposures		0								0	0		0
E	A1.126, A1.243, A1.441, B3.114, B3.115	Littoral chalk communities		0	0						0	0	0		0
E,EU,W	A1.3	Low energy intertidal rock	2	0	0			1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
EU, E, NI	A1.32	Estuarine rocky habitats	0	0					1	1	0	1	0	2	0
S	A1.325	Sea loch egg wrack beds	1	0	3			2	1	1	1	2	2		1
EU	A1.44	Submerged or partially submerged sea caves		0	0			1	1	1	0	1	0		0
E	A1.126, A1.243, A1.441, B3.114, B3.115	Littoral chalk communities		0	0						0	0	0		0

Application of the natural capital approach in the marine environment

Feature Type	EUNIS code Note: Eunis codes were identified using the JNCC EUNIS translation matrix. Some habitats do not have a direct relationship to the EUNIS code and this column should only be used as a guide.	Feature (Bold type represents broadscale habitats, normal type represents habitat FOCI)	Goods/Benefits from												
			Provisioning ES					Regulating ES				Cultural ES			
			Food (wild, farmed)	Fish feed (wild, farmed, bait)	Fertiliser and biofuels	Ornaments and aquaria	Medicines and blue biotechnology	Healthy climate	Prevention of coastal erosion	Sea defence	Waste burial / removal / neutralisation	Tourism and nature watching	Spiritual and cultural well-being	Aesthetic benefits	Education
E,W	A2.1	Intertidal coarse sediment	1	1	0	2			2	2	1	3	1	3	1
E,W	A2.2	Intertidal sand and muddy sand	2	1	0			1	2	2	1	3	1	3	1
E,S,W, NI	A2.2, A2.7, A5.6	Blue Mussel beds	0	1	0			1	0	0	1	1	1		0
NI	A2.23 or A5.2	Stable sands with associated fauna	0	1	0			1	1	1	0	2	0	2	0
E,W	A2.3	Intertidal mud	2	2	0			2	1	1	2	1	1	2	1
E,EU	A2.4	Intertidal mixed sediments	2	1	0			1	2	2	2	3	1	3	1
E,W	A5.43, A2.41, A2.42, A5.44	Sheltered muddy gravels	1	0	0			0			0	2	0		0
E	A2.5	Coastal saltmarshes and saline reedbeds	3	0	1			3	2	2	3	3	1	3	1
EU,E,W	A2.6	Intertidal sediments dominated by aquatic angiosperms	2	0	2			3	2	2	3	2	1		1
All	A5.53, A5.545, A2.61	Seagrass beds	1	0	0			1	0	0	1	0	1		0
EU,E,W	A2.7	Intertidal biogenic reefs	2	1	1			2	2	2	2	1	1		1
E,S,W, NI	A2.2, A2.7, A5.6	Blue Mussel beds	0	1	1			0	0	0	0	1	1		0
E,W	A2.71, A5.612	Honeycomb worm <i>Sabellaria alveolata</i> reef	2	1				2	2	2	2	1	1		1
EU,E,W	A3.1	High energy infralittoral rock	3	0	0				2	2	0	2	1		1
S	A3.126, A3.213	Tide-swept algal communities (<i>Laminaria hyperborea</i> , <i>Halidrys siliquosa</i>)	0	0	3				0	0	1	1	2		1
EU,E,W	A3.2	Moderate energy infralittoral rock	3	0	0				2	2	0	2	1		1
E,W	A1.2142, A3.2112	Intertidal under boulder communities	2	0	0				1	1	0	1	0		0
S	A3.126, A3.213	Tide-swept algal communities (<i>Laminaria hyperborea</i> , <i>Halidrys siliquosa</i>)	0	0	3				0	0	1	0	1		1
E	A4.23, A3.21	Subtidal chalk		0	0						0	1	0		0

Application of the natural capital approach in the marine environment

Feature Type	EUNIS code Note: Eunis codes were identified using the JNCC EUNIS translation matrix. Some habitats do not have a direct relationship to the EUNIS code and this column should only be used as a guide.	Feature (Bold type represents broadscale habitats, normal type represents habitat FOCI)	Goods/Benefits from													
			Provisioning ES					Regulating ES			Cultural ES					
			Food (wild, farmed)	Fish feed (wild, farmed, bait)	Fertiliser and biofuels	Ornaments and aquaria	Medicines and blue biotechnology	Healthy climate	Prevention of coastal erosion	Sea defence	Waste burial / removal / neutralisation	Tourism and nature watching	Spiritual and cultural well-being	Aesthetic benefits	Education	
EU,E,W	A3.3	Low energy infralittoral rock		0	0					2	2	0	2	1		1
	A3.32	Kelp in variable salinity on low energy infralittoral rock														
EU,E,W	A4.1	High energy circalittoral rock	3	0	0					1	1	0	2	1		1
E,W, NI	A4.12, A4.13, A4.21	Fragile sponge&anthozoan communities on subtidal rocky habitats	2	0	0					1	1	1	0	0		0
W	A4.131, A4.2122	Subtidal rock with Ross 'coral' <i>Pentapora foliacea</i>	2	0	0							1	0	0		0
S	A4.133, A4.211	Northern sea fan and sponge communities		0	0					1	1	1				
S	A3.126, A3.213, A1.15, A3.22, A4.11, A4.25, A5.52	Tide-swept algal communities	0	0	3					1	1	1	1	2		1
EU,E,W	A4.2	Moderate energy circalittoral rock	3	0	0					1	1	0	2	1		1
W	A4.131, A4.2122	Subtidal rock with Ross 'coral' <i>Pentapora foliacea</i>	2	0	0							1	0	0		0
S	A4.133, A4.211	Northern sea fan and sponge communities		0	0					1	1	1				
E	A4.22, A5.61	Ross worm <i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i> reefs	2	0						0	0	1	1	0		0
E	A4.23, A3.21	Subtidal chalk		0	0							0	1	0		0
E	A1.127, A1.223, A4.231	Peat and clay exposures		0									1	0		0
E,W, NI	A4.12, A4.13, A4.21	Fragile sponge&anthozoan communities on subtidal rocky habs	2	0	0					1	1	1	0	0		0
S	A3.126, A3.213, A1.15, A3.22, A4.11, A4.25, A5.52	Tide-swept algal communities	0	0	3					1	1	1	1	2		1
EU,E,W	A4.3	Low energy circalittoral rock	3	0	0					1	1	0	2	1		1
E,W	A5.1	Subtidal coarse sediment	2	3	0					1	1	1		1		1
E	A5.12, A5.13	Subtidal sands and gravels	0	0	0							1		0		0
S	A5.133	Shallow tide-swept coarse sands with burrowing bivalves (<i>Morella</i> sp.)	0	3	0							1		1		1

Feature Type	EUNIS code Note: Eunis codes were identified using the JNCC EUNIS translation matrix. Some habitats do not have a direct relationship to the EUNIS code and this column should only be used as a guide.	Feature (Bold type represents broadscale habitats, normal type represents habitat FOCI)	Goods/Benefits from											
			Provisioning ES					Regulating ES				Cultural ES		
			Food (wild, farmed)	Fish feed (wild, farmed, bait)	Fertiliser and biofuels	Ornaments and aquaria	Medicines and blue biotechnology	Healthy climate	Prevention of coastal erosion	Sea defence	Waste burial / removal / neutralisation	Tourism and nature watching	Spiritual and cultural well-being	Aesthetic benefits
E,W	A5.2	Subtidal sand	2	3	0			1	1	1		1		1
NI	A2.23 or A5.2	Stable sands with associated fauna	0	1	0			0	0	0		0		0
E,W	A5.3	Subtidal mud	2	3	0			1	1	2		1		1
E,S, NI	A5.361	Sea-pen and burrowing megafauna communities	1	3	0			0	0	0		0		0
S	A5.371	Inshore deep mud with burrowing heart urchins	0	3	0			0	0	0		0		0
EU,E,W	A5.4	Subtidal mixed sediments	2	3	0			1	1	2		1		1
E,W	A5.43, A2.41, A2.42, A5.44	Sheltered muddy gravels	1	2	0					0		0		0
E,S	A5.434	Flame/ File shell beds	0	3	0			0	0	1		0		0
E,S,W, NI	A5.435	Native Oyster <i>Ostrea edulis</i> beds	1	3	0			1	1	0		0		0
EU,E,W	A5.5	Subtidal macrophyte-dominated sediment	3	0	2			2	2	2	2	2	1	1
All	A5.51, A5.511, A5.512, A5.513, A5.514	Maerl beds	1	0	1							1	0	0
S	A5.5112	Maerl or coarse shell gravel with burrowing sea cucumbers	1	0	1							1	0	0
S	A5.52	Kelp and seaweed communities on sublittoral sediment	0	0	1			1	0	0	0	1	2	1
All	A5.53, A5.545, A2.61	Seagrass beds	0	0	0			0	0	0	0	0	1	0
S	A3.126, A3.213, A1.15, A3.22, A4.11, A4.25, A5.52	Tide-swept algal communities	0	0	1			1	0	0	1	1	2	1

Application of the natural capital approach in the marine environment

Feature Type	EUNIS code Note: Eunis codes were identified using the JNCC EUNIS translation matrix. Some habitats do not have a direct relationship to the EUNIS code and this column should only be used as a guide.	Feature (Bold type represents broadscale habitats, normal type represents habitat FOCI)	Goods/Benefits from												
			Provisioning ES					Regulating ES				Cultural ES			
			Food (wild, farmed)	Fish feed (wild, farmed, bait)	Fertiliser and biofuels	Ornaments and aquaria	Medicines and blue biotechnology	Healthy climate	Prevention of coastal erosion	Sea defence	Waste burial / removal / neutralisation	Tourism and nature watching	Spiritual and cultural well-being	Aesthetic benefits	Education
EU,E,W	A5.6	Subtidal biogenic reefs	3	0	1	1		2	2	2	1	1	1		1
E,S,W, NI	A2.2, A2.7, A5.6	Blue mussel beds	1	0	1	0		0	0	0	1	1	1		0
E,S,W, NI	A5.62	Horse mussel (<i>Modiolus modiolus</i>) beds	1	0	1	1		0	0	0	1	0	0		0
E, NI	A5.63	Cold-water coral reefs	2	0	1			1				0	0		0
E,W	A2.71, A5.612	Honeycomb worm <i>Sabellaria alveolata</i> reef	3	0				2	2	2	1	1	1		1
E	A4.22, A5.61	Ross worm <i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i> reefs	2	0				1	1	1	0	0	0		0
EU	A5.71	Submarine structures made by leaking gases	1	0	0		2	0	0	0	0		1		1
W, NI	A6.5	Mud habitats in deep water	2	3	0				1	1	2		1		1
E,S	A6.61	Coral gardens	1	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	2	1	1	2	1
	A6.62	Deep-sea sponge aggregations													
S	A6.75	Carbonate mound communities	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	0	0		0
S	A7.4, A7.7	Salinity fronts	2	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	2	2	1		1
EU	X02	Saline lagoons	1	0	0							2	1		1
S	Various	Low or variable salinity habitats	2	0	0	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	2	3	3
E,W	Various	Tide-swept channels		0	0				0	0		1	1		1
W	Various	Sediment habitats with long lived bivalves	2	0	0						2	0	2		1
E	N/A	Areas of high planktonic primary productivity	3	3	0			2	0	0	1	1	0		0

Key

Scale of ES supplied relative to other features

3	Significant contribution
2	Moderate contribution
1	Low contribution
0	No or negligible ES provision
	Not assessed

Relative differentiation in ES provision compared to parent broadscale habitat

	Highly differentiated
	Moderately differentiated
	Slightly differentiated
	Mean difference in ES score class >1 (+ve or -ve) compared to parent broadscale habitat

Feature type

S	Scottish MPA search feature
E	English MCZ feature
W	Welsh HP MCZ feature
NI	Northern Ireland MCZ feature
EU	EU Habitats Directive Annex 1 feature or sub-feature

Table A9.3 Alignment of ecosystem service categories used in the matrices (Potts et al. 2014) with CICES v5.1 typology

Marine relevant ecosystem service categories from CICES v5.1	Ecosystem service categories used in matrices (Potts et al. 2014)	
	Intermediate	Goods/Benefits
1.1.2.1 Plants cultivated by in- situ aquaculture grown for nutritional purposes		Food (wild and farmed)
1.1.2.2 Fibres and other materials from in-situ aquaculture for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)		Fish feed (wild, farmed, bait)/ Fertiliser and biofuels/Medicines and blue biotechnology
1.1.2.3 Plants cultivated by in- situ aquaculture grown as an energy source		Fertiliser and biofuels
1.1.4.1 Animals reared by in-situ aquaculture for nutritional purposes		Food (wild and farmed)
1.1.4.2 Fibres and other materials from animals grown by in-situ aquaculture for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)		Fish feed (wild, farmed, bait)/Medicines and blue biotechnology
1.1.5.1 Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used for nutrition		Food (wild and farmed)
1.1.5.2 Fibres and other materials from wild plants for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)		Fish feed (wild, farmed, bait)/ Fertiliser and biofuels/Medicines and blue biotechnology
1.1.5.3 Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used as a source of energy		Fertiliser and biofuels
1.1.6.1 Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) used for nutritional purposes		Food (wild and farmed)
1.1.6.2 Fibres and other materials from wild animals for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)		Fish feed (wild, farmed, bait)/Ornaments and aquaria/Medicines and blue biotechnology
2.1.1 Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Nutrient cycling/waste breakdown & detoxification	Waste burial /removal/neutralisation
2.2.1 Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Formation of physical barriers/Natural hazard regulation	Prevention of coastal erosion/sea defence
2.2.1.3 Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation (Including flood control, and coastal protection)	water cycling	
2.2.2.1 Pollination (or 'gamete' dispersal in a marine context)	Larval and gamete supply	
2.2.2.3 Maintaining nursery populations and habitats (Inc. gene pool protection)	Formation of species habitat	
2.2.3 Pest and disease control	Biological control	
2.2.6 Atmospheric composition and conditions		Healthy climate
2.2.6.1 Regulation of chemical composition of atmosphere and oceans	Carbon sequestration	
3.1 Direct, in-situ and outdoor interactions with living systems that depend on presence in the environmental setting	Formation of the seascape	Tourism and nature watching/
3.1.2 Intellectual and representative interactions with natural environment		Education
3.1.2.4 Characteristics of living systems that enable aesthetic experiences		Aesthetic benefits
3.2.1 Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment		Spiritual and cultural wellbeing

Appendix 10: Marine ecosystem service indicators

Table A10.1 Potential indicators for marine ecosystem services, examples of data sources and policies driving data collection

Generic ecosystem service indicator	Metric (unit)	References	Examples of UK data sources	Policy driver for data collection
Wild animals, plants, algae, & outputs				
Fish and shellfish populations	Biomass (t km ⁻² or abundance (n km ⁻²) of fish and shellfish, area (m ²)	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015), Maes <i>et al.</i> 2016, Bohnke-Henrichs <i>et al.</i> 2013, Hooper <i>et al.</i> 2015, Broziet <i>et al.</i> 2017	MMO landings data, FAO statistics, ONS, DCF, ICES	CFP, MSFD
Seaweed stock	Biomass (t km ⁻²) seaweed	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015), Maes <i>et al.</i> 2016, Bohnke-Henrichs <i>et al.</i> 2013, Hooper <i>et al.</i> 2015, Broziet <i>et al.</i> 2017	MMO landings data, FAO statistics, ONS, DCF, ICES	CFP, MSFD
Quality of fish, shellfish, seaweed stock	Species composition, age profile; length profile; % affected by disease; mortality rates	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015), Maes <i>et al.</i> 2016, Hooper <i>et al.</i> 2015, Broziet <i>et al.</i> 2017	MMO landings data, FAO statistics, ONS, DCF, ICES	CFP, MSFD
Aquaculture				
Fish and shellfish populations	Biomass (t km ⁻² or abundance (n km ⁻²) of fish and shellfish, area (m ²))	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015), Maes <i>et al.</i> 2016, Bohnke-Henrichs <i>et al.</i> 2013, Hooper <i>et al.</i> 2015, Broziet <i>et al.</i> 2017	MMO landings data, FAO statistics, ONS, DCF, ICES	CFP, MSFD
Seaweed stock	Biomass (t km ⁻²) seaweed	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015), Maes <i>et al.</i> 2016, Bohnke-Henrichs <i>et al.</i> 2013, Hooper <i>et al.</i> 2015, Broziet <i>et al.</i> 2017	MMO landings data, FAO statistics, ONS, DCF, ICES	CFP, MSFD
Quality of the fish, shellfish stock	% affected by disease; mortality rates	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015), Maes <i>et al.</i> 2016, Bohnke-Henrichs <i>et al.</i> 2013, Hooper <i>et al.</i> 2015, Broziet <i>et al.</i> 2017	MMO landings data, FAO statistics, ONS, DCF, ICES	CFP, MSFD
Water supply				
Capacity of water storage of habitat	Water storage capacity (m ³ /area) for different intertidal habitats (e.g. saltmarsh, sediment)	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Relevant Environment Agencies (EA, SEPA, NIEA, NRW)	National/regional flood defence policies
Water quality				
Absolute levels of waste in the water column and within species	Chemical content analysis (contaminant concentrations) and visual analysis	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015), Maes <i>et al.</i> 2016, Broziet <i>et al.</i> 2017	Relevant Environment Agencies (EA, SEPA, NIEA, NRW)	WFD
Amount of heavy metals in water and sediment	mg l ⁻¹	Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)		WFD
Number of shellfish closures	No units given	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Relevant Environment Agencies (EA, SEPA, NIEA, NRW)	Shellfish Waters Directive
Presence of pathogens; outbreaks of <i>E. coli</i> infections; hospital admissions	Total coliforms or other pathogens (mg l ⁻¹)	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Relevant Environment Agencies (EA, SEPA, NIEA, NRW)	WFD
Benthic biodiversity levels/ratios/ no sensitive species, community bioturbation potential	Biodiversity indices	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Relevant Environment Agencies (EA, SEPA, NIEA, NRW)	WFD

Generic ecosystem service indicator	Metric (unit)	References	Examples of UK data sources	Policy driver for data collection
Water quality (cont)				
Harmful algal bloom outbreaks	Remote sensing, water sampling to detect frequency and extent; modelling to determine future frequency and extent	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Relevant Environment Agencies (EA, SEPA, NIEA, NRW)	WFD?
Assimilate capacity	No units given	Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)		
Biological oxygen demand	mg O ₂ ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Relevant Environment Agencies (EA, SEPA, NIEA, NRW)	WFD
Oxyrisk	No units given	Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015), Maes <i>et al.</i> (2014)		
Amount of organic matter in water and sediment	mg l ⁻¹	Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Relevant Environment Agencies (EA, SEPA, NIEA, NRW)	WFD
Mass stabilisation & Flood protection				
Reduction of wave energy by nearshore and intertidal habitats	Change in wave energy (Joules m ⁻²) attributed to different intertidal and nearshore habitats	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015), Maes <i>et al.</i> (2016)	UK SeaMap (2006–2010) MESH Atlantic (2004–2008), 2010–2014)	National/regional flood defence policies
Changing shoreline	Change in beach profile (slope (gradient) and width (m) and stability) over time determined empirically from photos, satellite, LiDAR, ARGUS camera and modelled	Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015), Maes <i>et al.</i> (2016)		National/regional flood defence policies
Pest & disease control				
Presence/absence/frequency of pests (e.g. algal blooms, foam, sea lice on farmed salmon)	count data	Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	published and grey literature	WFD
Pest control	Distribution (km ²) of alien species	Maes <i>et al.</i> 2016	NNSS	MSFD
Quality of pest control species	Abundance, health status	Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	DASSH, published and grey literature, industry	
Climate regulation				
Air-sea and sediment water fluxes of carbon and CO ₂	mg C ⁻² d ⁻¹	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Site specific published and grey literature	UNFCCC
Air-sea fluxes of other greenhouse gases	µg greenhouse gases m ⁻² d ⁻¹	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Site specific published and grey literature	UNFCCC
Levels of carbon in different components of the ecosystem	biomass of carbon (gm ⁻²), dissolved organic and inorganic carbon (mg C m ⁻³ , burrier particulate organic or inorganic carbon (mg C m ⁻²)	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Site specific published and grey literature	UNFCCC
Permanence of carbon sequestration	% of annual carbon turnover from sediments	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Site specific published and grey literature	UNFCCC
Carbon stock	ton C	Maes <i>et al.</i> 2016	Site specific published and grey literature	UNFCCC
C sequestration	ton C year ⁻¹	Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015), Maes <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Site specific published and grey literature	UNFCCC
Assimilative and recycling capacity	No units given	Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Site specific published and grey literature	UNFCCC
pH	Change in units	Maes <i>et al.</i> 2016	Site specific published and grey literature	UNFCCC

Generic ecosystem service indicator	Metric (unit)	References	Examples of UK data sources	Policy driver for data collection
Cultural Services				
Sea space available for recreation	Number of km ² of sea with safe water quality available for recreational use	Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015), Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015)		
Number of designated sites	Count data	Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	JNCC, UNEP-WCMC	CBD
Number per area of specific seascape features	N / area	Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	ONS, Economic and Social Data Service (ESDS)	
% total natural seascape	% of natural area in a specific area	Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	JNCC	CBD
Number and quality of beaches	Number and size of blue flag beaches	Hattam <i>et al.</i> (2015), Atkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Defra	Bathing Waters Directive
Abundance and diversity of key species of recreational interest	Number of participants /year; number of facilities (n visitors/facility/yr); amount of time spent participating (hours/days)	Atkins <i>et al.</i> 2015, Hattam <i>et al.</i> 2015	ONS, UK Centre for Economic & Environmental Development (CEED), Great Britain Tourism Survey, OBIS SEAMAP, RSPB statistics, Royal Yachting Association	MSFD biodiversity descriptors (1, 4, 6) species biodiversity components (Birds, mammals)
Area of biotopes of key interest to recreational users	For example, extent of seagrass, maerl or kelp beds (km ²)	Atkins <i>et al.</i> 2015, Hattam <i>et al.</i> 2015		
Uniqueness of a site	1/(Number of sites with similar features)	Atkins <i>et al.</i> 2015, Hattam <i>et al.</i> 2015	JNCC	CBD/OSPAR
Abundance of key species of individual interest	count data	Atkins <i>et al.</i> 2015, Hattam <i>et al.</i> 2015	ONS, UK Centre for Economic & Environmental Development (CEED), Great Britain Tourism Survey, OBIS SEAMAP, RSPB statistics, Royal Yachting Association	MSFD biodiversity descriptors (1, 4, 6) species biodiversity components (Birds, mammals)
Area of biotopes of key interest to individuals	For example, extent of seagrass, maerl or kelp beds (km ²)	Atkins <i>et al.</i> 2015, Hattam <i>et al.</i> 2015	EMODnet, DASSH, BRCs, SNCBs	Habitats Directive

Appendix 11: Habitat extent and conditions indicators

Table A11.1 Extent and conditions indicators for coastal assets and services (Lusardi *et al.*, in press)

Asset attribute	Indicator category	Indicator
Quantity	Extent	Beach
Quantity	Extent	Coastal lagoons
Quantity	Extent	Mudflats
Quantity	Extent	Salt marsh
Quantity	Extent	Sand dunes
Quantity	Extent	Sea cliff
Quantity	Extent	Shingle
Quality	Nutrient (& chemical) status	Nutrient & chemical status of coastal lagoons
Quality	Nutrient (& chemical) status	Sediment/soil nutrient status
Quality	Soil/sediment processes	Soil/sediment biota
Quality	Soil/sediment processes	Sediment supply/availability (including type, grain size)
Quality	Soil/sediment processes	Sediment stabilisation
Quality	Species Composition	Naturalness of biological assemblage number of trophic levels & community composition in each level
Quality	Species Composition	Invasive non-native species
Quality	Vegetation	Cover of vegetation/bare soil (esp. dunes, shingle, dynamic between saltmarsh/mudflat)
Quality	Vegetation	Natural strandline – triggers formation of new dunes & saltmarsh
Spatial configuration		Transition, connectivity from subtidal to terrestrial habitats
Spatial configuration		Width/area/location for dynamic movement and development of coastal habitats e.g. saltmarsh, dunes
Spatial configuration		Width/area/location of habitats providing flood protection – for housing and infrastructure
ES flow		Carbon sequestered & greenhouse gases fixed
ES flow		Maintenance of sustainable ecosystems/life cycle stages
ES flow		Reduced inundation of terrestrial areas from marine flooding
ES flow		Sediment stabilisation
Quantity	Nature	Visibility of wildlife
Quantity	Nature	Presence of flagship species
Quantity	Nature	Presence of rare (red list) species
Quantity	Nature	Species diversity
Quantity	Nature	Favourable condition of SSSIs
Quantity	Nature	Favourable condition of designated geosites
Quality	Environmental setting	Size of environmental space (ha)
Quality	Culture & history	Designated Historic Environment Assets (World Heritage Sites, Scheduled monuments)
Quality	Accessibility	Mean number of perimeter access points per km
Quality	Accessibility	Public rights of way/permissive paths; footpaths, bridleways, byway – length, density (km/ha)
Quality	Accessibility	Presence of paths accessible to all – e.g. wheelchairs, pushchairs – length, density (km/ha)
Quality	Formative geological processes	Active geomorphological processes
Spatial configuration		% of population who can access 2ha of green space within 2 miles of home
ES flow	Experiential & physical use	Number of visits
ES flow	Experiential & physical use	Duration of visits
ES flow	Experiential & physical use	Range of activities undertaken (number of people, frequency)
ES flow	Scientific/educational	Number of research projects; PhD/Masters projects
ES flow	Scientific/educational	Number of school visits

Table A11.2 Extent and conditions indicators for marine assets and services (Lusardi *et al.*, in press)

Asset attribute	Indicator category	Indicator
Quantity	Extent	Deep sea habitats
Quantity	Extent	Intertidal rock
Quantity	Extent	Intertidal sediment
Quantity	Extent	Maerl beds
Quantity	Extent	Reefs
Quantity	Extent	Sea grass beds
Quantity	Extent	Shallow subtidal sediment
Quantity	Extent	Shelf subtidal sediment
Quantity	Extent	Subtidal rock
Quality	Nutrient (& chemical) status	Bacteriological & viral water quality
Quality	Nutrient (& chemical) status	Carbon content of sediment
Quality	Nutrient (& chemical) status	Dissolved oxygen
Quality	Nutrient (& chemical) status	Nutrient status of sediment & sea water (N, P, Si & water turbidity)
Quality	Nutrient (& chemical) status	pH
Quality	Soil/sediment processes	Sediment biota
Quality	Species composition	Amount & number of decomposers/decomposition rate (kg/ha/year)
Quality	Species composition	Naturalness of biological assemblage number of trophic levels & community composition in each level
Quality	Species composition	Net productivity by species (kcal/ha/yr)
Spatial configuration		Transition and connectivity from subtidal to coastal and terrestrial habitats
ES flow		Carbon sequestered & greenhouse gases fixed
ES flow		Fish, shellfish, seaweed and other products (tonnes)
ES flow		Maintenance of sustainable ecosystems/life cycle stages
ES flow		Water quality (chemical & biological, including viral & bacterial)
Quantity	Extent	Reefs
Quantity	Extent	Sea grass beds
Quantity	Nature	Visibility of wildlife
Quantity	Nature	Presence of flagship species
Quantity	Nature	Presence of rare (red list) species
Quantity	Nature	Species diversity
Quantity	Nature	Favourable condition of SSSIs
Quantity	Nature	Favourable condition of designated geosites
Quality	Nature	Quality of bathing waters
Quality	Facilities	Number of organised events
Quality	Facilities	Presence of clubs, schools, training centres
Quality	Culture & history	Designated Historic Environment Assets (World Heritage Sites, Scheduled monuments)
Quality	Formative geological processes	Active geomorphological processes
ES flow	Experiential & physical use	Number of visits
ES flow	Experiential & physical use	Duration of visits
ES flow	Experiential & physical use	Range of activities undertaken (number of people, frequency)
ES flow	Scientific/educational	Number of research projects; PhD/Masters projects
ES flow	Scientific/educational	Number of school visits

Appendix 12: A comparison of habitat typologies used for natural capital assessments

Table A12.1 Comparison of habitat types included in natural capital or ecosystem service assessments cross tabulated against MSFD benthic broad habitat types and habitats of conservation importance (OSPAR threatened and declining habitats and MCZ HOCI)

	MSFD Benthic Broad Habitat 2017	Associated OSPAR T&D habitats	Associated MCZ HOCI	UK NEA		UK NEAFO	MAES		
				Broad habitat	Component habitat		Ecosystem type	Pelagic habitats:	Benthic habitats:
Transitional & coastal margin	MSFD does not deal with transitional waters		Estuarine rocky habitats				Marine inlets & transitional waters	Low/reduced salinity water (of lagoons)	Littoral rock and biogenic reef
								Variable salinity water (of coastal wetlands, estuaries and other transitional waters)	Littoral sediment
				Coastal margins	Sea cliffs	Cliffs and small islands (B3)		Marine salinity water (of other inlets)	Shallow sublittoral rock and biogenic reef
					Sand dunes	Dunes (B1.3–B1.8)			Shallow sublittoral sediment
					Shingle	Beaches (B1.1, B1.2, B1.3)			
					Machair	Machair (B1.9)			
					Saltmarsh	Salt and tidal marshes (A2.5)			
					Coastal lagoons	Lagoons (Z02, X03)			

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	MSFD Benthic Broad Habitat 2017	Associated OSPAR T&D habitats	Associated MCZ HOCl	UK NEA		UK NEAFO	MAES		
Intertidal	Littoral rock & biogenic reef	Litoral chalk communities; Intertidal <i>Mytilus edulis</i> beds on mixed and sandy sediments;	Blue mussel beds; Estuarine rocky habitats; Honeycomb worm reefs; Intertidal under boulder communities; Littoral chalk communities; Peat and clay exposures; Tide-swept channels	Marine	Intertidal rock	Rocky bottom (A1, A2.1, X31)	Coastal	Coastal waters	Littoral rock and biogenic reef
	Littoral sediments	Intertidal mudflats; <i>Zostera</i> beds	Seagrass beds; Sheltered muddy gravels		Intertidal sediments	Mudflats (A2.2, A2.3) Seagrass beds (A2.6)			Littoral sediment
Shallow subtidal	Infralittoral rock & biogenic reef	<i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i> reefs; <i>Modiolus modiolus</i> beds	Blue mussel beds; Estuarine rocky habitats; Peat and clay exposures; Subtidal chalk; Tide-swept channels Tide-swept channels		Subtidal rock	Kelp forest (A3.2)			Shallow sublittoral rock and biogenic reef
	Infralittoral coarse sediment	Maerl beds	Seagrass beds; Subtidal sands and gravels		Shallow subtidal sediment	Seagrass beds (A5.53)			Shallow sublittoral sediment
	Infralittoral sand	<i>Zostera</i> beds	Maerl beds; Seagrass beds						
	Infralittoral mud	Maerl beds; Seapen and burrowing megafauna communities; <i>Zostera</i> beds	File shell beds; Sheltered muddy gravels; Maerl beds; Native oyster						
	Infralittoral mixed sediment	Maerl beds; <i>Ostrea edulis</i> beds							
	Circalittoral coarse sediment		Subtidal sands and gravels						
	Circalittoral sand		Subtidal sands and gravels						
	Circalittoral mud	Seapen and burrowing megafauna communities	Mud habitats in deep water Sheltered muddy gravels						
	Circalittoral mixed sediment								
	Circalittoral rock & biogenic reef	<i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i> reefs; <i>Modiolus modiolus</i> beds	Blue mussel beds; Fragile sponge and anthozoan communities; Horse mussel beds; <i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i> reefs; Subtidal chalk; Peat and clay exposures; Tide-swept channels		Subtidal rock				

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	MSFD Benthic Broad Habitat 2017	Associated OSPAR T&D habitats	Associated MCZ HOCl	UK NEA	UK NEAFO	MAES		
Shelf/offshore	Offshore circalittoral rock & biogenic reef		Cold-water coral reef		Coastal shelf (EEZ)	Shelf	Pelagic habitats:	Shelf waters
	Offshore circalittoral sand Offshore circalittoral mud Offshore circalittoral mixed sediment Offshore circalittoral coarse sediment		Subtidal sands and gravels Mud habitats in deep water Subtidal sands and gravels				Benthic habitats:	Shelf sublittoral rock and biogenic reef Shelf sublittoral sediment
					Open ocean		Pelagic habitats:	Oceanic waters
Deep Sea	Upper bathyal rock & biogenic reef	Coral gardens; <i>Lophelia pertusa</i> reefs; Carbonate mounds; Deep-sea sponge aggregations; Seamounts	Cold-water coral reef; Coral gardens; Deep sea sponge aggregations	Deep sea habitats	Open ocean (beyond EEZ)		Benthic habitats:	Upper bathyal rock & biogenic reef
	Upper bathyal sediment	Coral gardens; Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents/fields	Coral gardens; Mud habitats in deep water; seapens and burrowing megafauna				Upper bathyal sediment	
	Lower bathyal rock & biogenic reef	Coral gardens; <i>Lophelia pertusa</i> reefs; Carbonate mounds; Deep-sea sponge aggregations; Seamounts	Cold-water coral reef; Coral gardens; Deep sea sponge aggregations				Lower bathyal rock & biogenic reef	
	Lower bathyal sediment	Coral gardens; Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents/fields	Coral gardens; Mud habitats in deep water; seapens and burrowing megafauna				Lower bathyal sediment	
	Abyssal rock & biogenic reef	Coral gardens; <i>Lophelia pertusa</i> reefs; Carbonate mounds; Deep-sea sponge aggregations; Seamounts	Cold-water coral reef; Coral gardens; Deep sea sponge aggregations				Abyssal rock & biogenic reef	
	Abyssal sediment	Coral gardens; Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents/fields	Coral gardens; Mud habitats in deep water; seapens and burrowing megafauna				Abyssal sediment	

Appendix 13: Natural capital valuation methods

Table A13.1 The strengths and constraints of the monetary valuation methods used in studies deriving values for UK marine and coastal features

Method	Definition (source: eftec & Environmental Futures Ltd, 2006)	Advantages	Limitations
Stated preference	<p>Choice Modelling: “<i>Choice modelling is based around the notion that goods and services can be described in terms of characteristics (or ‘attributes’) and the levels that these characteristics take. For example, a lake may be described in terms of its ecological quality, chemical water quality, number and type of species it provides habitat for, and so on. A choice modelling questionnaire presents respondents with different combinations of these attributes and asks them to choose their most preferred combination, or rank their preferences in order. As each combination has a ‘price’ attached, subsequent analysis of respondents’ choices reveal their WTP or WTA for each of the characteristics (or attributes) presented to them.</i>”</p> <p>Contingent valuation: “<i>The contingent valuation method is a survey-based approach to valuing environmental goods and services. The approach entails the construction of a hypothetical, or ‘simulated’, market via a questionnaire where respondents answer questions concerning what they are willing to pay (or willing to accept) for a specified environmental change. The approach defines the environmental goods and services as a bundle of different characteristics (quality, quantity, different services etc.) and seeks to elicit willingness to pay for the entirety of the bundle.</i>”</p>	<p>Stated preference approaches are able to capture use and non-use values (Defra, 2007). They are widely applicable (and widely used), allow the reasons behind preferences to be explored, can be applied <i>ex ante</i>, and the methods are relatively easy to describe and explain to policy makers (Fujiwama & Campbell, 2011).</p>	<p>Surveys are costly, and can be subject to several forms of bias that arise from the framing of the survey context and questions, and from the method by which it is undertaken (Fujiwama & Campbell, 2011). The hypothetical nature of stated preference approaches is also a major weakness (particularly if participants are responding to unfamiliar situations and lack complete information) and may lead to respondents giving trivial answers (Whitehead et al., 2008).</p>

Method	Definition (source: eftec & Environmental Futures Ltd, 2006)	Advantages	Limitations
Revealed preference	<p>Hedonic pricing: <i>“Hedonic property pricing is based on the notion that the price at which a property sells is determined, in part, by the environmental characteristics of the surrounding location. The economic value of the environmental characteristics is estimated by regressing the sale price against all factors thought to affect the price.”</i></p> <p>Travel cost: <i>“The travel cost method is a survey based technique that uses the cost incurred by individuals travelling to and gaining access to a recreation site as a proxy for the recreational value of that site. Costs considered are travel expenditures, entrance fees, and the value of time.”</i> [Note: this technique involves complex statistical analysis that includes data on other factors that affect visits to estimate a demand curve]</p>	<p>Values are based on actual choices made by individuals in real markets, and these studies may be more cost-effective than stated preference due to lower survey pre-testing requirement (Fujiwama & Campbell, 2011).</p>	<p>Hedonic pricing relies on a number of assumptions that do not necessarily hold in real housing markets, and outcome may not relate to marginal changes (Fujiwama & Campbell, 2011). It also requires large amounts of data on property prices and characteristics (eftec & Environmental Futures Ltd, 2006).</p> <p>Travel cost surveys are usually limited to recreational uses (Defra, 2007). They may underestimate the values held by those living close to the site, and the approach has limited application as it can only be used to value attributes that can be perceived by users (eftec & Environmental Futures Ltd, 2006). Travel cost is also limited to historical data and so may not be applicable for new policies (Whitehead et al., 2008).</p>
Market price/cost	<p><i>“Market price approaches consider the costs that arise in relation to the provision of environmental goods and services which may be observed directly from actual markets. These costs can take the form of opportunity costs or the cost of alternative provision as well as mitigation costs or the costs of avertive behaviour and shadow project costs.”</i></p>	<p>Market data is readily available and robust (Defra, 2007)</p>	<p>Valuation is limited to goods and services for which markets exist (Defra, 2007). Also, market prices cannot be used to determine non-use values; they can be distorted through, for example, monopoly or subsidies; and approaches such as mitigation costs do not fully value the environmental implications of failure to address impacts (eftec & Environmental Futures Ltd, 2006). Cost-based approaches may also overestimate value (Defra, 2007).</p>
Production function	<p><i>“The production function approach focuses on the (indirect) relationship that may exist between a particular ecosystem service and the production of a marketed good. Here, environmental goods and services are considered as inputs to the production process and their value is inferred by considering the</i></p>	<p>The approach provides a means of explicitly estimating the importance of environmental attributes in generating market goods and services, and also the impacts that environmental damage can have on this</p>	<p>Determining production functions requires a large amount of data and expertise, and difficulties arise due to uncertainty and a lack of understanding of how services are delivered and their interactions (eftec & Environmental Futures Ltd, 2006).</p>

	<i>changes in production process of market goods that result from an environmental change.”</i>	process (eftec & Environmental Futures Ltd, 2006).	
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Appendix 14: Protocol used for the review of UK empirical valuations

Objective of the literature review

The objective of this review is to assemble and analyse available literature dealing with coastal and marine valuation within the UK and highlights evidence gaps. More precisely it aimed at answering two main questions:

- 1) **What are the existing monetary and non-monetary values of UK marine and coastal natural capital and ecosystem services?**
- 2) **What are the differences in valuation approaches and outcomes across different assets and ecosystem services?**

The population of our study (i.e. the focus of our study) was **coastal and marine ecosystem services and assets (species and habitats) within the UK** such as:

- provisioning services: fisheries, building materials;
- supporting services: life-cycle maintenance for both fauna and local, element and nutrient cycling;
- regulating services: carbon sequestration and storage, erosion prevention, waste-water treatment, moderation of extreme events;
- cultural services: tourism, recreational, aesthetic, and spiritual benefits.

The literature review aimed at recording the **occurrence** (i.e. the patterns of occurrence) and the **condition of interest** (that is what is assessed or measured in the population) of the valuation study.

The literature review only focused on study using primary data, thus excluding studies using benefit transfer or trade-off methods.

Method

Searching and screening method

A comprehensive search was performed using multiple information sources to capture an as exhaustive as possible list of reference. Both academic and non-academic database were searched. The search string for academic scoping was tested against a set of 22 papers found on the Marine Ecosystem Service Partnership databased. The exercise resulted in the selection of the following search terms:

- *Location*

TITLE-ABS-KEY ((england OR uk OR "United Kingdom" OR wales OR scotland OR ireland OR british OR irish OR scottish OR welsh OR lundy))

- *Type of environmental asset*

TITLE (coast OR marine* OR wetland* OR beach* OR water* OR sea OR ocean* OR sand* OR dune* OR bay OR estuar* OR gulf* OR island* OR isle* OR saltmarsh* OR machair* OR shingle* OR seagrass* OR littoral* OR coral* OR fish* OR seal OR dolphin OR (bird W/5 (sea OR coast* OR marine)) OR mussel OR oyster OR crab OR lobster OR "marine plan" OR "marine protected area" OR "marine conservation zone" OR "natura 2000" OR "cliff" OR shore* OR lagoon OR "mudflat" OR kelp OR *tidal OR *sea OR "MPA" OR "world heritage" OR "special area of conservation")*

- *Valuation methods*

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Avoided cost" OR "cost of illness" OR "travel cost" OR "replacement cost" OR "substitute cost" OR "shadow project cost" OR "restoration cost" OR "opportunity cost" OR "prevention cost" OR (transfer W/3 (benefit OR value OR unit)) OR "Contingent valuation" OR "Calibrated model" OR "conjoint analysis" OR "Choice experiment" OR "Damage

assessment" OR "Discrete choice" OR "Expenditure analysis" OR "Productivity method" OR "Random utility" OR "Referendum method" OR "Non-monetary" OR "Non-monetary valuation" OR non-market OR "Willingness to pay" OR wtp OR "stated-revealed preference model" OR "stated preference" OR "revealed preference" OR "contingent Behaviour*" OR "cost-benefit" OR "Multinomial logit models" OR "market price" OR "production function" OR "net factor income" OR "random utility" OR "productivity loss" OR "dose response" OR "revealed preference" OR "stated preference" OR "avoided cost" OR "damage costs avoided" OR "averting behaviour" OR "defensive behaviour" OR "averting expenditure" OR "defensive expenditure" OR "hedonic pric*" OR "productivity gain" OR "choice modelling" OR "citizen jur*" OR "deliberative monetary valuation" OR "place based valuation" OR "health valuation" OR "indicator approach" OR "Q method*" OR "qualitative semi-structured survey" OR "group deliberative discussions" OR "focus group" OR "delphi survey" OR "systematic review" OR "cost-benefit analysis" OR "cost-effectiveness analysis" OR "environmental impact assessment" OR "health impact assessment" OR "social impact assessment" OR "social accounting" OR "social return on investment" OR "outcome map*" OR "social multi-criteria evaluation" OR "qualitative participatory deliberation" OR "multi-criteria map*" OR "computable general equilibrium" OR "input-output" OR "payment for ecosystem" OR pse OR (valu* W/3 (economic* OR ecosystem* OR "ecosystem service*" OR envrionment* OR "natural capital" OR nature OR service* OR resource* OR benefit* OR use* OR non-use* OR option* OR existence* OR bequest* OR non-market*)) OR (econom* W/3 (valu* OR assessment* OR estimat* OR demand)) OR (estimat* W/5 (benefit OR value OR impacts OR monetary))

No time or document type restrictions were applied but only English literature has been searched for. This search string has been used in Scopus and Science Direct.

Non-academic literature databases searched are the following:

- Marine ecosystem services partnership database
- National ocean economics program
- Environmental Valuation Reference Inventory
- eftec database
- TEEB database

Google scholar (scholar.google.com) as well as google Custom International Governmental Organizations (<https://cse.google.com/cse/home?cx=006748068166572874491:55ez0c3j3ey>) and Google Custom Non-Governmental Organizations (<https://cse.google.com/cse/home?cx=012681683249965267634:q4g16p05-ao>) were searched.

Paper screening and selection process

Figure A13.1 gives an overview of the papers screening and inclusion. All the papers retrieved have been screened (title, keyword, and abstract) and included or excluded according to the following criteria:

1) Relevant subjects, population

We considered studies that value marine or coastal assets (based on UK NEA):

- Sand dunes, Machair, Saltmarsh, Shingle, Sea cliff, Coastal lagoons, Beaches, Coastal waters, Wetland, Rockpool, Maerl, Seaweed, Seagrass;
- Intertidal Rock (rock and biogenic reefs), Intertidal Sediments (Saltmarshes, Intertidal muds, Intertidal sands and muddy sands, Intertidal coarse and mixed sediment, Intertidal seagrass beds), Subtidal Rock (Infralittoral rock, Circalittoral rock, Subtidal biogenic reefs), Shallow and Shelf Subtidal Sediments (Shallow muds, Shallow sands and muddy sands, Shallow coarse and mixed sediment, Macrophyte-dominated sediment (seagrasses, maerl, seaweeds), Shelf Subtidal Sediment (Shelf muds, Shelf sands and muddy sands, Shelf coarse and mixed sediment), Deep-sea Habitats (Deep-sea rock, Deep-sea bioherms, Deep-sea sediments)
- Marine and coastal species (fishes, mammals, birds)

We considered studies valuing UK environment:

- England, Wales, Scotland, Northern Ireland and Republic of Ireland

- 2) Relevant occurrence/ Condition of interest:
- Valuation method used: monetary or non-monetary valuation, Avoided cost method, Benefit transfer method, Contingent valuation, Calibrated model, Conjoint analysis, Choice experiment, Damage assessment, Discrete choice method, Expenditure analysis, Productivity method, Random utility, Referendum method, Travel cost method, Payment card, Stated preference method, Revealed preference Method, OR Contingent Behaviour, Cost-benefit Analysis;
 - Type of data used: primary or secondary data
 - Outcome of the valuation: type of metrics used,

3) Relevant languages

Only papers in English were reviewed.

Once selected, all the papers were reviewed by the review team and when relevant, data has been extracted. Papers referring to the same paper study, with the same outcome have been excluded. When a grey literature report and a peer reviewed paper were dealing with the same study, only the peer-reviewed has been kept for the literature review.

Figure A13.1. Overview of article inclusion and screening

In the end, 69 studies have been included in the literature review.

Data extraction

For each paper selected, the following information has been extracted and collated in a database:

- Full citation
- Year of publication
- Year of data production
- Type of literature (academic or peer-reviewed)
- Policy context (funder, reference to policy)
- Location and scale (country, scale – national, regional, local)

Country	Scale
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - England - Scotland - Wales - Northern Ireland - Republic of Ireland - UK wide 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local (case study) - Regional (county or region level) - National

- Type of environmental asset (group – habitat, species, management measure, other)

Group type	Detailed	Broad ecosystem service	Detailed ecosystem service	Zone
Habitat	Saltmarsh Beach Coastal Coral reef Marine Wetland Sand dune Machair Saltmarshes Underwater rocky habitats Estuary Coastline Estuarine intertidal mudflat Underwater muddy habitats Underwater sandy habitats	Regulating	Hazard reduction Recreation Climate regulation Pest control Water regulation	Transitional Coastal Inshore (0–12 nautical miles) Offshore
Species	Fish Cetaceans Bass Bird Invertebrates Algae Seal Octopus Enhanced biodiversity Marine wildlife	Provisioning	Food Other Materials Energy Recreation Non-use	
Management measure	Water quality coastal defence MPA GES Species protection Site protection Fishing techniques ban Sustainable fishing techniques	Cultural	Recreation Visual amenity Non-use Non-specific/aggregated Health Research & education	
Other	Recreational opportunity Marine-coastal environment General environment Water quality Cost of microplastic Estimate the cost of degradation of marine water Loss due to oil spill			

- The way it is valued

Broad category of valuation method	Valuation method used
Price-based approach Stated Preference Non monetary valuation Revealed Preference Cost-based approach Not Specified	Market prices/analysis Contingent Valuation questionnaires Choice modelling Q-Methodology (QME) Stakeholder mapping placing blocks on inshore grid of Wales as values Hedonic pricing Travel cost Place based valuation Indicator approach input-output Expenditure survey Production function approach Opportunity costs Marxan with Zones, design cost-effective networks of MPAs that incorporate conservation and socioeconomic principles Participatory workshop Avoidance/prevention cost

- The outcome of the valuation (Payment vehicle, Payment unit, Payment frequency, Payment duration, Currency, Value type, Value estimate type)

Application of the natural capital approach in the marine environment

Reference	Country	Scale	Zone	Habitat/species/sector	ES section	ES broad category	ES details
Morrissey <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Rol	C	C	General environment	Provisioning	Food	Capture fisheries
Morrissey <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Rol	C	C	Aquaculture	Provisioning	Food	Aquaculture
Morrissey <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Rol	C	C	Seafood processing	Provisioning	Food	Seafood processing
Morrissey <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Rol	C	C	Algae	Provisioning	Other materials	Seaweed & biotechnology
Morrissey <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Rol	C	C	Oil and Gas	Provisioning	Energy	Oil and Gas
Morrissey <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Rol	C	C	Renewable energy	Provisioning	Energy	Renewable energy
Morrissey <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Rol	C	C	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	General
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	E, W	C	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	E, W	C	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	E, W	C	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	E, W	C	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	E, W	C	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	E, W	C	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	E, W	C	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	E, W	C	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	E, W	C	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	E, W	C	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	E, W	C	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	E, W	C	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	E, W	C	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	E, W	C	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Parsons <i>et al.</i> (2003)	S	R	C, I	Cetaceans	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Parsons <i>et al.</i> (2003)	S	R	C, I	Cetaceans	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Parsons <i>et al.</i> (2003)	S	R	C, I	Cetaceans	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Grilli <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Rol	N	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Voke <i>et al.</i> (2013)	W	L	I	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	General
Voke <i>et al.</i> (2013)	W	L	I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	General
Curtis (2003)	Rol	N	I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Other water-based
Curtis (2003)	Rol	N	I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Other water-based
Curtis (2003)	Rol	N	I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Other water-based
Curtis (2003)	Rol	N	I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Other water-based
Roberts <i>et al.</i> (2017)	E	N	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Roberts <i>et al.</i> (2017)	E	N	I	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	E	L	C, I, O	Marine mammals	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	E	L	C, I, O	Seabirds	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	E	L	C, I, O	Invertebrates	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	E	L	C, I, O	Fish	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	E	L	C, I, O	Algae	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	E	L	C, I, O	Marine mammals	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	E	L	C, I, O	Seabirds	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	E	L	C, I, O	Fish	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	E	L	C, I, O	Invertebrates	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	E	L	C, I, O	Algae	Cultural	Non-use	Existence

Application of the natural capital approach in the marine environment

Reference	Country	Scale	Zone	Habitat/species/sector	ES section	ES broad category	ES details
Blakemore <i>et al.</i> (2008)	W	L	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Visual amenity	Coastal scenery
Blakemore <i>et al.</i> (2008)	W	L	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Visual amenity	Coastal scenery
Marine Planning Consultants Ltd (2013)	W	L	I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	General & water-based
Marine Planning Consultants Ltd (2013)	W	L	I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	General & water-based
Polyzos and Minetos (2007)	E	L	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	General
Polyzos and Minetos (2007)	E	L	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	General
Polyzos and Minetos (2007)	E	L	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	General
Ropars-Collet <i>et al.</i> (2015)	UK	R	C	General environment	Cultural	Non-specific/aggregated	
Ropars-Collet <i>et al.</i> (2015)	UK	R	C	General environment	Cultural	Non-specific/aggregated	
Ropars-Collet <i>et al.</i> (2015)	UK	R	C	General environment	Cultural	Non-specific/aggregated	
Ropars-Collet <i>et al.</i> (2015)	UK	R	C	General environment	Cultural	Non-specific/aggregated	
Ropars-Collet <i>et al.</i> (2015)	UK	R	C	General environment	Cultural	Non-specific/aggregated	
Ropars-Collet <i>et al.</i> (2015)	UK	R	C	General environment	Cultural	Non-specific/aggregated	
Hanley and Kristrom (2002)	S	R	I	Coastal water	Cultural	Recreation	Clean bathing water
Hanley and Kristrom (2002)	S	R	I	Coastal water	Cultural	Recreation	Clean bathing water
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
McVittie and Moran (2010)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Mangi <i>et al.</i> (2011)	E	L	T, C	Wetland, saltmarsh	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Sea defence
Mangi <i>et al.</i> (2011)	E	L	T, C	Wetland, saltmarsh	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Sea defence
Mangi <i>et al.</i> (2011)	E	L	T, C	Wetland, saltmarsh	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Sea defence
Mangi <i>et al.</i> (2011)	E	L	T, C	Wetland, saltmarsh	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Sea defence

Application of the natural capital approach in the marine environment

Reference	Country	Scale	Zone	Habitat/species/sector	ES section	ES broad category	ES details
Lawrence (2005)	E	R	C, I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Lawrence (2005)	E	R	C, I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Lawrence (2005)	E	R	C, I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Lawrence (2005)	E	R	C, I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2014b)	E	L	O	Offshore sand bank	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2014b)	E	L	O	Offshore sand bank	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2014b)	E	L	O	Offshore sand bank	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2014b)	E	L	O	Offshore sand bank	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2014b)	E	L	O	Offshore sand bank	Regulating	Pest control	Invasive species
Barry <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Rol	L	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	General access
Garrod and Willis (1994)	E	L	C	Sand dunes, saltmarsh	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Lee (2015)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	Maritime industry			
Lee (2015)	UK	N	T, C, I, O	Aquaculture	Provisioning	Food	Shellfish
eftec (2002)	E, W	N	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
eftec (2002)	E, W	N	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
eftec (2002)	E, W	N	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
eftec (2002)	E, W	N	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
eftec (2002)	E, W	N	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Coastal and flood plain	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Coastal and flood plain	Cultural	Research & education	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Coastal and flood plain	Regulating	Climate regulation	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Coastal and flood plain	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Coastal and flood plain	Cultural	Recreation	General
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Coastal and flood plain	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Coastal and flood plain	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Maritime cliffs	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Maritime cliffs	Cultural	Research & education	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Maritime cliffs	Regulating	Climate regulation	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Maritime cliffs	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Maritime cliffs	Cultural	Recreation	General
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Maritime cliffs	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Maritime cliffs	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Sand dune, shingle	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Sand dune, shingle	Cultural	Research & education	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Sand dune, shingle	Regulating	Climate regulation	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Sand dune, shingle	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Sand dune, shingle	Cultural	Recreation	General
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Sand dune, shingle	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Sand dune, shingle	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Intertidal mudflat, saltmarsh	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Intertidal mudflat, saltmarsh	Cultural	Research & education	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Intertidal mudflat, saltmarsh	Regulating	Climate regulation	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Intertidal mudflat, saltmarsh	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Intertidal mudflat, saltmarsh	Cultural	Recreation	General
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Intertidal mudflat, saltmarsh	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Intertidal mudflat, saltmarsh	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Coastal and flood plain	Cultural	Non-use	Existence

Application of the natural capital approach in the marine environment

Reference	Country	Scale	Zone	Habitat/species/sector	ES section	ES broad category	ES details
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Coastal and flood plain	Cultural	Research & education	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Coastal and flood plain	Regulating	Climate regulation	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Coastal and flood plain	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Coastal and flood plain	Cultural	Recreation	General
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Coastal and flood plain	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Coastal and flood plain	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Maritime cliffs	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Maritime cliffs	Cultural	Research & education	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Maritime cliffs	Regulating	Climate regulation	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Maritime cliffs	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Maritime cliffs	Cultural	Recreation	General
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Maritime cliffs	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Maritime cliffs	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Sand dune, shingle	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Sand dune, shingle	Cultural	Research & education	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Sand dune, shingle	Regulating	Climate regulation	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Sand dune, shingle	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Sand dune, shingle	Cultural	Recreation	General
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Sand dune, shingle	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Sand dune, shingle	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Intertidal mudflat, saltmarsh	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Intertidal mudflat, saltmarsh	Cultural	Research & education	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Intertidal mudflat, saltmarsh	Regulating	Climate regulation	
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Intertidal mudflat, saltmarsh	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Intertidal mudflat, saltmarsh	Cultural	Recreation	General
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Intertidal mudflat, saltmarsh	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Christie and Rayment (2012)	E, W	N	C	Intertidal mudflat, saltmarsh	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Rocky tide swept channels	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Rocky tide swept channels	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Endangered/vulnerable species	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Endangered/vulnerable species	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Fish	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Seabirds	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Seabirds	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Seal	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Octopus	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Octopus	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Rock formation	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Rocky seafloor, oyster,mussel , flame shellbeds	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Rocky sea floor with large kelp and seaweeds	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Rocky sea floor with large kelp and seaweeds	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Rock with anemones, soft corals, sponges	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Rock with anemones, soft corals, sponges	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling

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Reference	Country	Scale	Zone	Habitat/species/sector	ES section	ES broad category	ES details
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Mud, sea-pens, burrowers, fireworks anemones	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Mud, sea-pens, burrowers, fireworks anemones	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Sand/gravel, honeycomb/ross worm colonies	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Rock, honeycomb/rossworm colonies	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Rock, honeycomb/rossworm colonies	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Sand/gravel with seagrass or eel grass beds	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Sand/gravel with seagrass or eel grass beds	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Mud with burrowing sea urchins, brittlestars	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Sand/gravel with scallops and sea urchins	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Sand/gravel with scallops and sea urchins	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Sand/gravel in tide swept channel	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Rocky seafloor with rocky habitats in estuary	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Shipwreck	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	Shipwreck	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	E, W, S	N	C, I, O	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	S	R	O	Deep sea	Provisioning	Other materials	Medicinal products
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	S	R	O	Deep sea	Provisioning	Other materials	Medicinal products
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	S	R	O	Deep sea	Provisioning	Non-use	Existence
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	S	R	O	Deep sea	Provisioning	Non-use	Existence
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	S	R	O	Deep sea	Provisioning	Non-use	Existence
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	S	R	O	Deep sea	Provisioning	Non-use	Existence
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	S	R	O	Deep sea	Provisioning	Other materials	Medicinal products
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	S	R	O	Deep sea	Provisioning	Non-use	Existence
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	S	R	O	Deep sea	Provisioning	Non-use	Existence
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Rol	N	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Rol	N	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Rol	N	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Rol	N	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Rol	N	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Recreation	Clean bathing water
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Rol	N	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Recreation	Clean bathing water
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Rol	N	C, I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Rol	N	C, I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Rol	N	C, I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Hanley <i>et al.</i> (2003)	S	L	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Recreation	General
Bosetti and Pearce (2003)	E	R	I	Seal	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Bosetti and Pearce (2003)	E	R	I	Seal	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Bosetti and Pearce (2003)	E	R	I	Seal	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	E	L	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	E	L	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	E	L	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	E	L	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	E	L	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	E	L	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	E	L	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	E	L	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Health	Clean bathing water
Farrell <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Rol	N	C	Coastal water	Cultural	Non-specific/aggregated	

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Reference	Country	Scale	Zone	Habitat/species/sector	ES section	ES broad category	ES details
Chae <i>et al.</i> (2012)	E	L	I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	General
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2015)	E , W	L	I	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2015)	E , W	L	I	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2015)	E , W	L	I	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Non use	Existence
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Rol	N	I	Coastal water	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Rol	N	I	Coastal water	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Rol	N	I	Coastal water	Regulating	Pest control	Invasive species
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Rol	N	I	Coastal water	Regulating	Pest control	Invasive species
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Rol	N	I	Coastal water	Provisioning	Food	Capture fisheries
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Rol	N	I	Coastal water	Provisioning	Food	Capture fisheries
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Rol	N	I	Coastal water	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Rol	N	I	Coastal water	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Rol	N	I	Coastal water	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Rol	N	I	Coastal water	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
King (1995)	E	L	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	General
King (1995)	E	L	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	General
King (1995)	E	L	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	General
King (1995)	E	L	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	General
Soliño <i>et al.</i> (2013)	E, W	N	T, C	Coastal water	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Soliño <i>et al.</i> (2013)	E, W	N	T, C	Coastal water	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Soliño <i>et al.</i> (2013)	E, W	N	T, C	Coastal water	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Soliño <i>et al.</i> (2013)	E, W	N	T, C	Coastal water	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Sogn-Grundvåg (2013)	S	L	I, O	Fish	Provisioning	Food	Capture fisheries
Sogn-Grundvåg (2013)	S	L	I, O	Fish	Provisioning	Food	Capture fisheries
Ruiz-Frau <i>et al.</i> (2013)	W	N	I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Ruiz-Frau <i>et al.</i> (2013)	W	N	I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Other water-based
Ruiz-Frau <i>et al.</i> (2013)	W	N	I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Ruiz-Frau <i>et al.</i> (2013)	W	N	I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Loureiro and Loomis (2013)	UK	N	C	Coast, seabird, marine mammal	Cultural	Non use	Existence
Rees <i>et al.</i> (2010)	E	L	C, I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Rees <i>et al.</i> (2010)	E	L	C, I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving
Rees <i>et al.</i> (2010)	E	L	C, I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Rees <i>et al.</i> (2010)	E	L	C, I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Rees <i>et al.</i> (2010)	E	L	C, I	General environment	Cultural	Recreation	Scuba diving, sea angling
Paltriguera <i>et al.</i> (2018)	E	L	C, I	Marine mammals	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Paltriguera <i>et al.</i> (2018)	E	L	C, I	Marine mammals, rare seabirds	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Paltriguera <i>et al.</i> (2018)	E	L	C, I	Marine mammals	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Paltriguera <i>et al.</i> (2018)	E	L	C, I	Marine mammals, rare seabirds	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Christie and Gibbons (2011)	W	L	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Visual amenity	Coastal scenery
Christie and Gibbons (2011)	W	L	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Surfing
Christie and Gibbons (2011)	W	L	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	General
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	S	N	C	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	S	N	C	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	S	N	C	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	S	N	C	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Recreation	Wildlife watching
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	S	N	C	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	S	C	C	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling

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Reference	Country	Scale	Zone	Habitat/species/sector	ES section	ES broad category	ES details
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	S	C	C	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	S	C	C	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	S	C	C	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	S	C	C	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	S	C	C	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	S	C	C	Marine wildlife	Cultural	Recreation	Sea angling
Abell and Bromham (2009)	E, W	C	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Other water-based
Abell and Bromham (2009)	E, W	C	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Other water-based
Mills (2013)	UK	N	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Surfing
Mills (2013)	UK	N	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Surfing
Mills (2013)	UK	N	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Surfing
Mills (2013)	UK	N	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Surfing
Mills (2013)	UK	N	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Surfing
Mills (2013)	UK	N	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Surfing
Mills (2013)	UK	N	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Surfing
Mills (2013)	UK	N	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Surfing
Mills (2013)	UK	N	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Surfing
Abell and Mallett (2008)	E	R	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Surfing
Abell and Mallett (2008)	E, W	R	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Surfing
Abell and Mallett (2008)	E, W	R	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Recreation	Surfing
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	E	L	T	Wetland	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	E	L	T	Wetland	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	E	L	T	Wetland	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	E	L	T	Wetland	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	E	L	T	Wetland	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	E	L	T	Wetland	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	E	L	T	Wetland	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	E	L	T	Wetland	Regulating	Hazard reduction	Flood risk
Hooper (2014)	E	L	T	Intertidal mudflat	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Hooper (2014)	E	L	T	Intertidal mudflat	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Hooper (2014)	E	L	T	Intertidal mudflat	Cultural	Non-use	Existence
Ergin <i>et al.</i> (2011)	UK	N	C	Beach/Coast	Cultural	Visual amenity	Coastal scenery
Kindermann and Gormally (2013)	S, Rol	L	C	Sand dune, machair	Cultural	Recreation	General
Ruiz-Frau <i>et al.</i> (2011)	W	N	I	General environment	Cultural	Non-specific/aggregated	
Rees <i>et al.</i> (2013)	E	R	I	General environment	Cultural	Non-specific/aggregated	
Ruiz-Frau <i>et al.</i> (2015)	W	N	I	General environment	Cultural	Non-specific/aggregated	
Pike <i>et al.</i> (2015)	E	L	C	General environment	Cultural	Non-specific/aggregated	
Pike <i>et al.</i> (2011)	E, W	L	C	General environment	Cultural	Non-specific/aggregated	
Holt <i>et al.</i> (2011)	S	L	T	Estuary	Cultural	Non-specific/aggregated	
Farrell <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Rol	C	C, I	General environment	Cultural	Non-specific/aggregated	

Table A15.2 The valuation context, method, payment details and value estimate from the empirical valuation studies reviewed

 Grey literature

Method – general: Stated Preference (SP), Revealed Preference (RP), Price-based (PB)

Method – detail: Avoidance/prevention cost (AC) Contingent valuation (CV), Market prices (MP), Travel cost (TC), Choice modelling (CM), Production function (PF), Hedonic Pricing (HP)

Reference	Valuation context/Measure of change	Method - general	Method - detail	Subsample	Payment unit	Payment frequency	Value estimate
MacDonald <i>et al.</i> (2017)	marginal effect of 180ha of salt marsh habitat	RP	AC			per year	163,187
MacDonald <i>et al.</i> (2017)	marginal effect of 180ha of salt marsh habitat	RP	AC			per year	1,718
MacDonald <i>et al.</i> (2017)	marginal effect of 180ha of salt marsh habitat	RP	AC			one off	18.27
MacDonald <i>et al.</i> (2017)	marginal effect of 180ha of salt marsh habitat	RP	AC			per year	51,020
MacDonald <i>et al.</i> (2017)	marginal effect of 180ha of salt marsh habitat	RP	AC			per year	3,4170
MacDonald <i>et al.</i> (2017)	marginal effect of 387ha of intertidal habitat	RP	AC			per trip	3.71
MacDonald <i>et al.</i> (2017)	marginal effect of 387ha of intertidal habitat	RP	AC			per year	9,505
MacDonald <i>et al.</i> (2017)	marginal effect of 387ha of intertidal habitat	PB	MP			per year	21,5360
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Value of Enjoyment estimate	SP	CV	All sample	per person	per day	8.63
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Value of Enjoyment estimate	SP	CV	Residents	per person	per day	8.77
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Value of Enjoyment estimate	SP	CV	Day visitors	per person	per day	7.98
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Value of Enjoyment estimate	SP	CV	Staying visitors	per person	per day	11.02
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	loss from the Value of Enjoyment estimate from beach erosion	SP	CV	All sample	per person	per day	2.34
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	loss from the Value of Enjoyment estimate from beach erosion	SP	CV	Residents	per person	per day	2.61
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	loss from the Value of Enjoyment estimate from beach erosion	SP	CV	Day visitors	per person	per day	1.81
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	loss from the Value of Enjoyment estimate from beach erosion	SP	CV	Staying visitors	per person	per day	3.20
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Gain in Value of Enjoyment under coastal protection scheme A	SP	CV	All sample	per person	per day	1.06
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Gain in Value of Enjoyment under coastal protection scheme A	SP	CV	Residents	per person	per day	1.10
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Gain in Value of Enjoyment under coastal protection scheme A	SP	CV	Day visitors	per person	per day	1.05
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Gain in Value of Enjoyment under coastal protection scheme A	SP	CV	Staying visitors	per person	per day	1.08
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Gain in Value of Enjoyment under coastal protection scheme B	SP	CV	All sample	per person	per day	1.06
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Gain in Value of Enjoyment under coastal protection scheme B	SP	CV	Residents	per person	per day	1.16
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Gain in Value of Enjoyment under coastal protection scheme B	SP	CV	Day visitors	per person	per day	1.01
Whitmarsh <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Gain in Value of Enjoyment under coastal protection scheme B	SP	CV	Staying visitors	per person	per day	0.64
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998a)	all beaches in the region meet new European standard	SP	CV	Norfolk (full sample)	Per household	per year	42.29
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998a)	all beaches in the region meet new European standard	SP	CV	Gt Yarmouth (full sample)	Per household	per year	32.22
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998a)	all beaches in the region meet new European standard	SP	CV	Gt Yarmouth (local resident)	Per household	per year	20.17
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998a)	all beaches in the region meet new European standard	SP	CV	Gt Yarmouth (day tripper)	Per household	per year	28.30
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998a)	all beaches in the region meet new European standard	SP	CV	Gt Yarmouth (holiday maker)	Per household	per year	37.71
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998a)	all beaches in the region meet new European standard	SP	CV	Lowestoft (full sample)	Per household	per year	31.84
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998a)	all beaches in the region meet new European standard	SP	CV	Lowestoft (local resident)	Per household	per year	37.41
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998a)	all beaches in the region meet new European standard	SP	CV	Lowestoft (day tripper)	Per household	per year	27.55
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998a)	all beaches in the region meet new European standard	SP	CV	Lowestoft (holiday maker)	Per household	per year	32.84
Armstrong <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Spend per day	PB	MP		per person	per year	1,394
Armstrong <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Spend per day	PB	MP		All anglers	per year	1,210,000,000
Armstrong <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Spend per day	PB	MP		GVA	per year	980,000,000

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Reference	Valuation context/Measure of change	Method - general	Method - detail	Subsample	Payment unit	Payment frequency	Value estimate
Morrissey <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Direct and indirect GVA	PB	MP		GVA		168,647
Morrissey <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Direct and indirect GVA	PB	MP		GVA		70,959
Morrissey <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Direct and indirect GVA	PB	MP		GVA		155,239
Morrissey <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Direct and indirect GVA	PB	MP		GVA		14,552
Morrissey <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Direct and indirect GVA	PB	MP		GVA		220,758
Morrissey <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Direct and indirect GVA	PB	MP		GVA		7,108
Morrissey <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Direct and indirect GVA	PB	MP		GVA		826,650
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	extra WTP for the same experience before abandoning angling	SP	CV	club members	per person	per year	645
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	extra WTP for the same experience before abandoning angling	SP	CV	non-club members	per person	per year	484
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	extra WTP for the same experience before abandoning angling	SP	CV	shore anglers	per person	per year	380
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	extra WTP for the same experience before abandoning angling	SP	CV	charter boat anglers	per person	per year	552
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	extra WTP for the same experience before abandoning angling	SP	CV	anglers using own boat	per person	per year	885
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	TCM per trip to reach embarkation point	RP	TC	all sample	per person	per trip	8.62
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	TCM per trip to reach embarkation point	RP	TC	shore anglers	per person	per trip	8.86
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	TCM per trip to reach embarkation point	RP	TC	charter boat anglers	per person	per trip	10.02
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	TCM per trip to reach embarkation point	RP	TC	anglers using own boat	per person	per trip	5.53
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	TCM per trip to reach embarkation point	RP	TC	anglers equal use shore/boat	per person	per trip	11.44
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	TCM per trip plus parking and boat costs	RP	TC	all sample	per person	per trip	24.36
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	TCM per trip plus parking and boat costs	RP	TC	shore anglers	per person	per trip	10.99
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	TCM per trip plus parking and boat costs	RP	TC	charter boat anglers	per person	per trip	43.30
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	TCM per trip plus parking and boat costs	RP	TC	anglers using own boat	per person	per trip	31.74
Shorney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	TCM per trip plus parking and boat costs	RP	TC	anglers equal use shore/boat	per person	per trip	34.24
Parsons <i>et al.</i> (2003)	Expenditure on wildlife watching, accomodation, food, drink	RP	TC		per person	per trip	85.25
Parsons <i>et al.</i> (2003)	Expenditure on accomodation, food and drink	RP	TC		per person	per trip	59.25
Parsons <i>et al.</i> (2003)	Value of whale watching to economy					per year	23,500,000
Grilli <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Trip cost	RP	TC		Per angler	Per day	48.00
Voke <i>et al.</i> (2013)	to maintain the area at its current standard	SP	CV		per person	per trip	6.70
Voke <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Trip cost	RP	TC		per person	per trip	115.67
Curtis (2003)	demand for water based leisure activity	RP	TC		per person	per trip	5.92
Curtis (2003)	demand for water based leisure activity	RP	TC		per person	per trip	15.44
Curtis (2003)	demand for water based leisure activity	RP	TC		per person	per trip	8.76
Curtis (2003)	demand for water based leisure activity	RP	TC		per person	per trip	1.60
Roberts <i>et al.</i> (2017)	total annual trip spend per angler	RP	TC		per person	per year	761.00
Roberts <i>et al.</i> (2017)	none total annual major item spend per angler	RP	TC		per person	per year	633.00
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	WTP to prevent reduction in species richness of the group	SP	CV	Residents	per person	one off	70.00
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	WTP to prevent reduction in species richness of the group	SP	CV	Residents	per person	one off	63.00
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	WTP to prevent reduction in species richness of the group	SP	CV	Residents	per person	one off	61.00
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	WTP to prevent reduction in species richness of the group	SP	CV	Residents	per person	one off	59.00
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	WTP to prevent reduction in species richness of the group	SP	CV	Residents	per person	one off	75.00
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	WTP to prevent reduction in species richness of the group	SP	CV	Visitors	per person	one off	62.00
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	WTP to prevent reduction in species richness of the group	SP	CV	Visitors	per person	one off	56.00
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	WTP to prevent reduction in species richness of the group	SP	CV	Visitors	per person	one off	54.00
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	WTP to prevent reduction in species richness of the group	SP	CV	Visitors	per person	one off	52.00
Ressurreição <i>et al.</i> (2012)	WTP to prevent reduction in species richness of the group	SP	CV	Visitors	per person	one off	66.00

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Reference	Valuation context/Measure of change	Method - general	Method - detail	Subsample	Payment unit	Payment frequency	Value estimate
Blakemore <i>et al.</i> (2008)	scenery impact	SP	CV			per trip	1.62
Blakemore <i>et al.</i> (2008)	scenery impact	SP	CV			per trip	1.91
Marine Planning Consultants Ltd (2013)	Watersports business revenue	PB	MP	Dale	per year		840,278
Marine Planning Consultants Ltd (2013)	Watersports business revenue	PB	MP	St David's	per year		1,561,513
Polyzos and Minetos (2007)	change in enjoyment of beach with/without coastal protection	SP	CV	Locals			7.60
Polyzos and Minetos (2007)	change in enjoyment of beach with/without coastal protection	SP	CV	Day visitors			11.30
Polyzos and Minetos (2007)	change in enjoyment of beach with/without coastal protection	SP	CV	Staying visitors			13.10
Ropars-Collet <i>et al.</i> (2015)	fishing boats (presence or absence)	SP	CM		per person	per trip	4.76
Ropars-Collet <i>et al.</i> (2015)	coastal walks (presence or absence)	SP	CM		per person	per trip	6.37
Ropars-Collet <i>et al.</i> (2015)	direct sale of seafood (presence or absence)	SP	CM		per person	per trip	3.10
Ropars-Collet <i>et al.</i> (2015)	beach (presence or absence)	SP	CM		per person	per trip	7.66
Ropars-Collet <i>et al.</i> (2015)	marina (presence or absence)	SP	CM		per person	per trip	3.08
Ropars-Collet <i>et al.</i> (2015)	architectural heritage (presence or absence)	SP	CM		per person	per trip	4.20
Hanley and Kristrom (2002)	improving water quality - Irvine	SP	CV		per person	per year	5.26
Hanley and Kristrom (2002)	improving water quality - Ayr	SP	CV		per person	per year	8.84
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Halt loss of biodiversity	SP	CM	England	per household	per year	69.49
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Halt loss of biodiversity	SP	CM	Scotland	per household	per year	20.92
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Halt loss of biodiversity	SP	CM	Wales	per household	per year	107.39
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Halt loss of biodiversity	SP	CM	N. Ireland	per household	per year	33.90
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Increased biodiversity	SP	CM	England	per household	per year	69.16
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Increased biodiversity	SP	CM	Scotland	per household	per year	23.76
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Increased biodiversity	SP	CM	Wales	per household	per year	61.04
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Increased biodiversity	SP	CM	N. Ireland	per household	per year	38.22
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Halt loss of environmental benefits	SP	CM	England	per household	per year	30.79
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Halt loss of environmental benefits	SP	CM	Scotland	per household	per year	16.16
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Halt loss of environmental benefits	SP	CM	Wales	per household	per year	139.08
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Halt loss of environmental benefits	SP	CM	N. Ireland	per household	per year	18.35
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Increased environmental benefits	SP	CM	England	per household	per year	34.27
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Increased environmental benefits	SP	CM	Scotland	per household	per year	19.45
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Increased environmental benefits	SP	CM	Wales	per household	per year	158.53
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Increased environmental benefits	SP	CM	N. Ireland	per household	per year	30.65
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Moderate restrictions	SP	CM	England	per household	per year	3.98
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Moderate restrictions	SP	CM	Scotland	per household	per year	3.49
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Moderate restrictions	SP	CM	Wales	per household	per year	28.11
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Moderate restrictions	SP	CM	N. Ireland	per household	per year	-12.91
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Highly restricted	SP	CM	England	per household	per year	-3.87
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Highly restricted	SP	CM	Scotland	per household	per year	-3.27
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Highly restricted	SP	CM	Wales	per household	per year	17.20
McVittie and Moran (2010)	Highly restricted	SP	CM	N. Ireland	per household	per year	-17.01
Mangi <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Protection of coastal wetland in their area	SP	CV		per person	per year	213.00
Mangi <i>et al.</i> (2011)	improved wetlands: roughly 25% hard defence and 75% wetland	SP	CM		Revenue	per year	7,092
Mangi <i>et al.</i> (2011)	new hard defences: roughly 75% hard defence, 25% wetlands	SP	CM		Revenue	per year	7,833
Mangi <i>et al.</i> (2011)	a mixture: roughly 50% hard defence and 50% wetlands	SP	CM		Revenue	per year	10,547

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Lawrence (2005)	WTP to increase catch of favourite species from 0-1 fish per day	SP	CM		WTP per trip	Per trip	13.56
Lawrence (2005)	WTP for additional fish on top of this	SP	CM		WTP per trip	Per trip	2.03
Lawrence (2005)	WTP for one more fish of any species other than their favourite	SP	CM		WTP per trip	Per trip	1.02
Lawrence (2005)	WTP for a 50% increase in the size of individual fish	SP	CM		WTP per trip	Per trip	13.27
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2014b)	Increase in species diversity by 10% on the Dogger Bank	SP	CM		per household	per year	4.19
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2014b)	Increase in species diversity by 25% on the Dogger Bank	SP	CM		per household	per year	7.76
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2014b)	Porpoises, seals, seabirds protected on 25% percent of the area	SP	CM		per household	per year	24.02
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2014b)	Porpoises, seals, seabirds protected on 50% percent of the area	SP	CM		per household	per year	30.32
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2014b)	Wide (as opposed to restricted) spread of invasive species	SP	CM		per household	per year	-25.39
Barry <i>et al.</i> (2011)	WTP for access to additional beach area and trail improvements	RP, SP	TC, CV		per person	per year	111.15
Garrod and Willis (1994)	one extra reserve in each of the habitats specified	SP	CV		per person		1.66
Lee (2015)	estimated potential aggregated costs	PB	PF				54,000,000
Lee (2015)	estimated potential aggregated costs	PB	PF				34,000,000
eftec (2002)	1% reduction in risk of a stomach upset	SP	CM		per household		1.10
eftec (2002)	avoid 1 day of poor water quality	SP	CM		per household	per year	0.90
eftec (2002)	Advisory note in place to advertise poor water quality days	SP	CM		per household	per year	5.60
eftec (2002)	Avoiding the presence of some litter/dog mess	SP	CM		per household	per year	6.00
eftec (2002)	Improving amenities and safety from average to good	SP	CM		per household	per year	3.40
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.00
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.15
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.04
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.13
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.09
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.48
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.09
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.00
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.04
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.02
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.00
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.02
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.12
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.02
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.00
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.04
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.06
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.04
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.03
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.17
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.04
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.02
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.42
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.52
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.59
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.15
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	1.23
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Prevent decline	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.17
Christie and Rayment (2012)	25% increase in Nature's gifts	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.00

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Reference	Valuation context/Measure of change	Method - general	Method - detail	Subsample	Payment unit	Payment frequency	Value estimate
Christie and Rayment (2012)	35% expansion of research and education	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.23
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Absorb 100k tonnes of CO2 (0.1% of all UK CO2 emissions)	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.07
Christie and Rayment (2012)	65,000 fewer people at risk of flooding	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.24
Christie and Rayment (2012)	33% inc in the area of SSSI habitats maintained in condition	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.14
Christie and Rayment (2012)	20% inc in populations/range of threatened charismatic species	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.32
Christie and Rayment (2012)	25% inc in populations/range of threatened non-charismatic sp	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.09
Christie and Rayment (2012)	25% increase in Nature's gifts	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.00
Christie and Rayment (2012)	35% expansion of research and education	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.07
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Absorb 100k tonnes of CO2 (0.1% of all UK CO2 emissions)	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.03
Christie and Rayment (2012)	65,000 fewer people at risk of flooding	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.00
Christie and Rayment (2012)	33% inc in the area of SSSI habitats maintained in condition	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.03
Christie and Rayment (2012)	20% inc in populations/range of threatened charismatic species	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.08
Christie and Rayment (2012)	25% inc in populations/range of threatened non-charismatic sp	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.02
Christie and Rayment (2012)	25% increase in Nature's gifts	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.00
Christie and Rayment (2012)	35% expansion of research and education	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.05
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Absorb 100k tonnes of CO2 (0.1% of all UK CO2 emissions)	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.10
Christie and Rayment (2012)	65,000 fewer people at risk of flooding	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.06
Christie and Rayment (2012)	33% inc in the area of SSSI habitats maintained in condition	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.04
Christie and Rayment (2012)	20% inc in populations/range of threatened charismatic species	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.10
Christie and Rayment (2012)	25% inc in populations/range of threatened non-charismatic sp	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.03
Christie and Rayment (2012)	25% increase in Nature's gifts	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.03
Christie and Rayment (2012)	35% expansion of research and education	SP	CM		Per household	per year	1.08
Christie and Rayment (2012)	Absorb 100k tonnes of CO2 (0.1% of all UK CO2 emissions)	SP	CM		Per household	per year	1.62
Christie and Rayment (2012)	65,000 fewer people at risk of flooding	SP	CM		Per household	per year	1.85
Christie and Rayment (2012)	33% increase in area of SSSI habitats maintained in condition	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.39
Christie and Rayment (2012)	20% inc in populations/range of threatened charismatic species	SP	CM		Per household	per year	1.39
Christie and Rayment (2012)	25% inc in populations/range of threatened non-charismatic sp	SP	CM		Per household	per year	0.27
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM				23.85
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM				25.14
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	WTP for one endangered/vulnerable species to be protected	SP	CM		Per species		0.44
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	WTP for one endangered/vulnerable species to be protected	SP	CM		Per species		0.30
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Dredging, trawling, potting and gillnetting prohibited at the site	SP	CM			per trip	4.28
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Dredging, trawling, potting and gillnetting prohibited at the site	SP	CM			per trip	4.76
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Dredging, trawling, anchoring and mooring prohibited at the site	SP	CM			per trip	6.12
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Species of interest (fish) is present (cf absent)	SP	CM			per trip	7.64
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Species of interest (fish) is present (cf absent)	SP	CM			per trip	23.58
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Species of interest (seabirds) is present (cf absent)	SP	CM			per trip	7.02
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Species of interest (seabirds) is present (cf absent)	SP	CM			per trip	-4.17
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Species of interest (seal) is present (cf absent)	SP	CM			per trip	15.97
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Species of interest (octopus) is present (cf absent)	SP	CM			per trip	13.42
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Species of interest (octopus) is present (cf absent)	SP	CM			per trip	-4.17
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Feature of interest (rock formation) is present (cf absent)	SP	CM			per trip	5.05
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	7.61
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	6.75
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	14.15
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	15.49
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	9.22

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Reference	Valuation context/Measure of change	Method - general	Method - detail	Subsample	Payment unit	Payment frequency	Value estimate
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	8.64
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	6.77
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	20.04
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	10.81
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	22.79
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	7.10
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	7.72
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	-9.13
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	7.71
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	19.70
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	7.85
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Landscape mostly this (cf another of conservation importance)	SP	CM			per trip	7.53
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Feature of interest (shipwreck) is present (cf absent)	SP	CM			per trip	18.98
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Feature of interest (shipwreck) is present (cf absent)	SP	CM			per trip	8.87
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	WTP to protect a site with variable characteristics	SP	CV		per person		8.83
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	WTP to protect a site with variable characteristics	SP	CV		per person		8.29
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	High potential for new medicines, with fisheries restrictions	SP	CM		Per household		35.95
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	High potential for new medicines, fisheries, oil & gas restrictions	SP	CM		Per household		34.81
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	1300 species protected (cf 1000 species), fisheries restrictions	SP	CM		Per household		23.64
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	1300 species protected (cf 1000), fisheries & oil & gas restrictions	SP	CM		Per household		21.17
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	1600 species protected (cf 1000 species), fisheries restrictions	SP	CM		Per household		36.38
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	1600 species protected (cf 1000), fisheries & oil & gas restrictions	SP	CM		Per household		33.04
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	High potential for new medicinal products (cf unknown potential)	SP	CM		Per household		37.85
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	1300 deep-sea species under protection (cf 1000 species)	SP	CM		Per household		26.28
Jobstvøgt <i>et al.</i> (2013)	1600 deep-sea species under protection (cf 1000 species)	SP	CM		Per household		38.70
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Small improvement in benthic health	SP	CM		Per visit	per year	4.77
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Large improvement in Benthic health	SP	CM		Per visit	per year	4.84
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Health risk: 5% - Good water quality achieved	SP	CM		Per visit	per year	4.08
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Health risk: virtually zero - Excellent water quality achieved	SP	CM		Per visit	per year	9.03
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Debris management: prevention	SP	CM		Per visit	per year	6.60
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Debris management: collection and prevention	SP	CM		Per visit	per year	7.20
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2017)	demand for sea angling recreation	RP	TC		Per trip		159.41
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2017)	demand for sea angling recreation	RP	TC		Per trip		261.00
Hynes <i>et al.</i> (2017)	demand for sea angling recreation	RP	TC		Per trip		420.00
Hanley <i>et al.</i> (2003)	Improvement in water quality	SP	CV		per person		5.81
Bosetti and Pearce (2003)	Entrance fee to visit seal sanctuary	SP	CV		per person	per trip	8.13
Bosetti and Pearce (2003)	Fee to go seal watching	SP	CV		per person	per trip	8.84
Bosetti and Pearce (2003)	Conservation fee (no further details provided)	SP	CV		per person	per trip	4.65
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	To raise failing bathing water quality to pass European standards	SP	CV	all sample	Per household		12.64
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	To raise failing bathing water quality to pass European standards	SP	CV	holiday makers	Per household		14.16
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	To raise failing bathing water quality to pass European standards	SP	CV	Day visitors	Per household		10.24
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	To raise failing bathing water quality to pass European standards	SP	CV	local residents	Per household		9.33
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	To keep bathing water at level of passing European standards	SP	CV	all sample	Per household		14.32
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	To keep bathing water at level of passing European standards	SP	CV	holiday makers	Per household		14.49
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	To keep bathing water at level of passing European standards	SP	CV	Day visitors	Per household		14.53
Georgiou <i>et al.</i> (1998b)	To keep bathing water at level of passing European standards	SP	CV	local residents	Per household		13.50

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Reference	Valuation context/Measure of change	Method - general	Method - detail	Subsample	Payment unit	Payment frequency	Value estimate
Farrell <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Aquatic ecosystem health	SP	CM		per person	per year	110.00
Chae <i>et al.</i> (2012)	Travel cost (Helicopter/ferry and basic motoring cost)	RP	TC		per trip		130.00
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2015)	10 more species to settle in and around the new OWF	SP	CM		Per household		12.91
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2015)	30 more species to settle in and around the new OWF	SP	CM		Per household		15.84
Börger <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Cabling buried at 2 m (no impact on marine mammals)	SP	CM		Per household		26.49
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Biodiversity maintained at current levels	SP	CM		per person	per year	-16.70
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Biodiversity decreases	SP	CM		per person	per year	-2.74
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Existing non-native species remain	SP	CM		per person	per year	-27.63
Norton and Hynes (2014)	New invasive species	SP	CM		per person	per year	-25.3
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Safe to eat but non-sustainable fisheries	SP	CM		per person	per year	-26.67
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Unsafe to eat and non-sustainable fisheries	SP	CM		per person	per year	-73.04
Norton and Hynes (2014)	No change in pollution levels	SP	CM		per person	per year	-28.26
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Increase in pollution	SP	CM		per person	per year	-74.37
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Moderate damage	SP	CM		per person	per year	-21.37
Norton and Hynes (2014)	Wide scale damage	SP	CM		per person	per year	-42.74
King (1995)	Entrance fee to use the beach in its current condition	SP	CV	Total sample	per person	per visit	1.78
King (1995)	Entrance fee to use the beach in its current condition	SP	CV	Residents	per person	per visit	2.02
King (1995)	Entrance fee to use the beach in its current condition	SP	CV	Day visitors	per person	per visit	1.61
King (1995)	Entrance fee to use the beach in its current condition	SP	CV	Staying visitors	per person	per visit	1.67
Soliño <i>et al.</i> (2013)	75% high quality in 8 years.	SP	CV		Per household	per year	76.99
Soliño <i>et al.</i> (2013)	95% high quality in 8 years.	SP	CV		Per household	per year	78.32
Soliño <i>et al.</i> (2013)	75% high quality in 8 years.	SP	CV		Per household	per year	55.73
Soliño <i>et al.</i> (2013)	95% high quality in 8 years.	SP	CV		Per household	per year	56.34
Sogn-Grundvåg (2013)	Premium on certified line caught fish vs non-labelled products	RP	HP		Price premium		0.18
Sogn-Grundvåg (2013)	Premium on certified line caught /MSC labelled vs non-labelled	RP	HP		Price premium		0.10
Ruiz-Frau <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Total travel cost	RP	TC		per person	per trip	71.00
Ruiz-Frau <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Total travel cost	RP	TC		per person	per trip	27.00
Ruiz-Frau <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Total travel cost	RP	TC		per person	per trip	44.00
Ruiz-Frau <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Total travel cost	RP	TC		per person	per trip	28.00
Loureiro and Loomis (2013)	reduction in oiling of coastline, birds, mammals, beaches	SP	CV				69.22
Rees <i>et al.</i> (2010)	Business turnover	PB	MP		per business	per year	150,888
Rees <i>et al.</i> (2010)	Total travel cost	RP	TC		per person	per trip	61.00
Rees <i>et al.</i> (2010)	Total travel cost	RP	TC		per person	per trip	30.00
Rees <i>et al.</i> (2010)	Total travel cost	RP	TC		per person	per trip	56.00
Rees <i>et al.</i> (2010)	Business turnover	PB	MP		per business	per year	39,883
Paltriguera <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Increased chance to see	SP	CM	2014	per person	per visit	2.07
Paltriguera <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Increased chance to see	SP	CM	2014	per person	per visit	6.19
Paltriguera <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Increased chance to see	SP	CM	2015	per person	per visit	6.40
Paltriguera <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Increased chance to see	SP	CM	2015	per person	per visit	9.97
Christie and Gibbons (2011)	Wooden groynes replaced with underwater solution	SP	CM		Per household	per year	81.70
Christie and Gibbons (2011)	Improved	SP	CM		Per household	per year	14.10
Christie and Gibbons (2011)	Improved for e.g. swimming, paddling	SP	CM		Per household	per year	33.10
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	Coastal wildlife watching	PB	MP		Expenditure	Per year	100,000,000
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	Coastal wildlife watching	PB	MP		Income	Per year	56,000,000
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	Boat-based wildlife watching	PB	MP		Expenditure	Per year	63,000,000
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	Boat-based wildlife watching	PB	MP		Income	Per year	36,000,000
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	total angler expenditure	PB	MP		All anglers	per year	140,868,000
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	total angler expenditure	PB	MP		All anglers	per year	22,623,000

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Reference	Valuation context/Measure of change	Method - general	Method - detail	Subsample	Payment unit	Payment frequency	Value estimate
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	total angler expenditure	PB	MP		All anglers	per year	25,294,000
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	total angler expenditure	PB	MP		All anglers	per year	24,126,000
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	total angler expenditure	PB	MP		All anglers	per year	15,477,000
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	total angler expenditure	PB	MP		All anglers	per year	11,160,000
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	total angler expenditure	PB	MP		All anglers	per year	26,896,000
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	total angler expenditure	PB	MP		All anglers	per year	9,190,000
Scottish Government Social Research (2010)	total angler expenditure	PB	MP		All anglers	per year	6,102,000
Abel and Bromham (2009)	Watersports business turnover	PB	MP		per business	Per year	25,000,000
Abel and Bromham (2009)	Watersports business turnover	PB	MP		per business	Per year	80,000,000
Mills (2013)	Average spend on equipment, accessories, material and clothing	PB	MP		per person	Per year	495.21
Mills (2013)	Average spend on carpark	PB	MP		per person	Per year	222.86
Mills (2013)	Average spend on food at surf break per year	PB	MP		per person	Per year	708.45
Mills (2013)	Average spend at local shops	PB	MP		per person	Per year	587.30
Mills (2013)	Average spend on fuel	PB	MP		per person	Per year	966.27
Mills (2013)	Average spend UK hotels and accommodation	PB	MP		per person	Per year	169.00
Mills (2013)	Average yearly spend (exc. Fuel, accommodation and travel)	PB	MP		per person	Per year	2,013.82
Mills (2013)	Total yearly spend for 500,000 surfers (excluding travel)	PB	MP		All surfers	Per year	1,006,910,000
Mills (2013)	Total yearly spend for 500,000 surfers including fuel	PB	MP		All surfers	Per year	1,490,045,000
Mills (2013)	Total spend (500,000 surfers) inc. fuel, accomm., foreign travel	PB	MP		All surfers	Per year	1,812,385,000
Abnell and Mallett (2008)	Surfing related expenditure for North Devon residents	PB	MP		Per surfer	Per year	1,358
Abnell and Mallett (2008)	Surfing related expenditure in North Devon for non-residents	PB	MP		Per surfer	Per year	1,121
Abnell and Mallett (2008)	Total spend for 42,000 surfers	PB	MP		All surfers	Per year	52,100,000
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	maximum amount they would be WTP for flood defences	SP	CV	all sample	per person	Per year	21.75
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	maximum amount they would be WTP for flood defences	SP	CV	Distance zone 1	per person	Per year	39.34
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	maximum amount they would be WTP for flood defences	SP	CV	Distance zone 2	per person	Per year	27.67
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	maximum amount they would be WTP for flood defences	SP	CV	Distance zone 3	per person	Per year	13.67
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	maximum amount they would be WTP for flood defences	SP	CV	Distance zone 4	per person	Per year	14.72
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	maximum amount they would be WTP for flood defences	SP	CV	holiday makers	per person	Per year	27.86
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	maximum amount they would be WTP for flood defences	SP	CV	Day visitors	per person	Per year	25.65
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	maximum amount they would be WTP for flood defences	SP	CV	Never visited	per person	Per year	12.29
Bateman <i>et al.</i> (1995)	maximum amount they would be WTP for flood defences	SP	CV	all sample	per person	one off	50.86
Hooper (2014)	Reduce loss of habitat by 70ha	SP	CV		per person	Per year	31.47
Hooper (2014)	Reduce loss of habitat by 140ha	SP	CV		per person	Per year	35.95
Hooper (2014)	Reduce loss of habitat by 70ha	SP	CM		per person	Per year	17.76